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**REPRESENTATION OF HISTORY IN ITS VARIOUS FORMS: A STUDY OF
SALMAN RUSHDIE'S SELECTED NOVELS**

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Doctor of Philosophy
(Humanities)

Submitted along with the **declaration of originality and research ethics** by
Tara Prasad Adhikari
fulfills all the standard requirements for a Doctoral Dissertation of Pokhara
University, thus endorsed for its final examination
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Salman Rushdie's Selected Novels

Tara Prasad Adhikari

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By
Tara Prasad Adhikari

A dissertation submitted to the Council for Doctoral Studies in partial fulfillment for the requirements of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy

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ABSTRACT

“Representation of History in its Various Forms: A Study of Salman Rushdie’s Selected Novels” investigates how Salman Rushdie develops a comprehensive theorization of history and fiction through his writings. The study argues that Rushdie, through his novels, proves that history is not just a factual piece of writing. Facts and figures are a part of history, but facts and figures alone do not constitute historical documents. Questioning the notion of so-called objectivity in history, Rushdie proposes another model of history, that is, history as story. What he means by this is that history uses certain narrative techniques to systematize the available data. Using their imagination and speculations, historians try to create meaning out of the collected resources of the past. They may even add or omit certain information in order to recreate the past. Rushdie identifies another form of history as well, that is, history as myth/magic. All historical documents may contain little bits of myth/magic. When historians try to recreate pre-historical times, they often resort to myths. When historians try to recreate what has been already lost, they may resort to fantasy or magic. Sometimes historians use magical mode of representation in order to create an alternative version of the past. Finally, Rushdie affirms that history may manifest itself, at times, as lies and gossip. Historical narrative contains some amount of lies and gossip as well. Some of the historians may include them unknowingly or due to human limitation, whereas some historians may use lies and gossip as a method of historical representation. Some historians may deliberately distort truth for their vested interest. We call such historical documents propaganda. What Rushdie writes about history also applies to fiction. Any fictional narrative may contain little bits of fact, story, myth/magic, and lies. In this regard, history and fiction are very similar. Rushdie himself has confirmed in many of his interviews that some readers read his novels as history books, whereas some read them as fiction.

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CONTENTS

	Page
Abstract	I
Acknowledgements	II
Content	III
I BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY	1-27
II REPRESENTATION IN HISTORY AND LITERATURE	28-69
III MODES OF HISTORICAL REPRESENTATION	70-90
IV REPRESENTATION OF HISTORY IN <i>MIDNIGHT'S CHILDREN</i>	91-130
V REPRESENTATION OF HISTORY IN <i>THE ENCHANTRESS OF FLORENCE</i>	131-161
VI REPRESENTATION OF HISTORY IN <i>GRIMUS</i>	162- 197
VII RUSHDIAN HISTORICAL PRISM	198-217
WORK CITED	218-228

Chapter I

Background of the Study

Introduction

This research work examines the nuances of history in Salman Rushdie's novels. It attempts to understand how Rushdie depicts history in its varied forms. The major forms of history that are seen in Rushdie's novels are: history as a record of past events, history as narrative, history as gossip, and history as magic. This research also explores how history has been understood in the past and how it has been understood now. The focus of the study is on Rushdie's conception of history or historiography. It also explores how culture, myths, religion, tradition, imagination come together and create a new reality in Rushdian texts.

Salman Rushdie does not merely regard history as a set of fixed and objective facts. He is strongly against the idea of pure and objective history because he believes that historians must interpret data and make them intelligible to the reader. No historian can be totally unbiased. As human beings we must have some biases and prejudices. In this sense, history and fiction look alike since they are the perspectives of an author/historian. We don't have any absolute history; instead, there may be different versions of the same event. Therefore, what we have is not *a* history but histories. In order to explain the very concept in a concrete way, Rushdie amalgamates different things just the way chutney is made. Salman Rushdie thus enforces the idea that history is very much like a multiple-faced hydra. By depicting history in its various forms, or by opening up the possibilities of multifaceted history, Rushdie reinvents history in his own way. With all his facts,

statistics, his clever plots and complex allusions, and his magnificent imageries, he has fashioned an excellent story. Thus, he opens up multiple possibilities of history. And in doing so he has paradoxically installed and subverted history itself.

Unlike other post-colonial writers of South Asia, Rushdie retells the history of the region from a postmodern perspective in which heterogeneity and difference are foregrounded where individuals emerge from a matrix of religions, cultures and histories. In order to present a total picture as far as possible, he devised his own unique historiography to subvert and install history. In one of his interviews he says:

I have begun to feel more and more that because of many things –mass migration, international mayhem, and economic globalization –the world’s stories are no longer separate but commingled, and have set myself the challenge of exploring the literary consequences of taking on this newly frontier-less world. (Prasannarajan 89)

Rushdie’s notion of history is a syncretic one. He is a storyteller of prodigious powers, able to conjure up whole geographies, causalities, climate, creatures, and customs, out of thin air. He aspires for a comprehensive notion of history. He wants balance. The protagonist of *Midnight’s Children* Saleem Sinai, Rushdie’s mouthpiece, also says: “I am balanced once more –the base of my isosceles triangle is secure. I hover at the apex, above present and past . . .” (*Midnight’s Children* 232).

How to capture so many things as a historian? How to find the great balance? Rushdie says that he achieves the aforementioned objective by cleverly blending history, autobiography, and magic. Rushdie himself considers his novel *Midnight’s Children* as an authority in the genre of history writing and he expects the

future aspirant historians to come to this book for guidance and inspirations, “this source book, this Hadith or Purana or Grundrisse” (*Midnight’s Children* 354).

Merging fantasy and naturalism is one way of representing at least two separate realities, both of which are relevant and neither of which presents the complete truth. Rushdie asserts, “we remake the past to suit our present purposes, using memory as our tool” (*Imaginary Homelands* 24). While liberating history from the shackles of traditional historiography, Rushdie somehow undermines the power and authority of the long-established institution of history itself.

Salman Rushdie’s Background

Salman Rushdie, a fiction writer, born in 1947, makes a great contribution in the field of modern historiography. He has also given a new impetus to Indian writings in English. He came into limelight immediately after the publication of *Midnight’s Children* in 1981. He is hailed as a trailblazer or even a trendsetter. He has given a new direction not only to Indian novels but also to world literature, by blending fact and fiction distinctively. A quick survey of his novels will bear testimony to this point.

Just in about three decades, Rushdie produced more than ten novels that have consolidated his position in world literature. *Grimus* (1975) was his first novel, a fantasy that describes the journey of “Flapping Eagle” in search of truth. With the publication of *Midnight’s Children* in 1981, Rushdie became strongly visible in the literary arena. *Midnight’s Children* is a story of the post-partition India and its unique feature is that the story has been told in the form of a complex comic allegory. It not only won the Booker Prize and the Booker of Bookers but also it is being continuously adapted for movies theatrical performances.

Shame, Rushdie's third novel, published in 1983, is a magic realist allegorical text, which deals with the socioeconomic turmoil of Pakistan around the 1980s. In this novel Rushdie creates characters that very much resemble Pakistani politicians of that era. Just like in *Midnight's Children*, here also Rushdie uses the tale of a family as a metaphor for the whole country.

The Jaguar Smile is a non-fiction published in 1987 that depicts the clashes between the individuals and the state. *The Satanic Verses* was Rushdie's fourth novel published in 1988. This allegorical novel deals with Pakistan and Muslim worldview that evoked anger and hatred in some of the Muslim population during the time of its publication. They took this novel as an insult to Muslim worldview. One of its consequences was the declaration of a fatwa in 1989 over Rushdie himself by the Iranian leader Ayatollah Khomeini. The novel was also banned for a long time. It forced Rushdie to live in hiding for many years.

In *Haroun and the Sea of Stories*(1990), a novelistic allegory, Rushdie strategically denounces censorship against his writings. His short prose *Is Nothing sacred?* (1990) explores the history of language and culture. *In Good Faith* (1990) explores the history and effects of fundamentalism. *The Wizard of Oz* (1992) exposes the history of adult inadequacy to cope with the children.

Rushdie's *Imaginary Homelands* (1992) is a collection of essays dealing with the politics of India and Pakistan, identity, race, religion, and the modern films – a whole panorama of world events. In 1995 he wrote a book of short stories *East, West* and the central burden of these nine stories is the depiction of the interface of fiction and history. Another text, *The Moor's Last Sigh* (1995) is a novel that examines the contemporary India through the life of a Jewish-Christian family. It particularly

focuses on how Hindu terrorism has made the life of minorities in India unbearable. *The Ground Beneath Her Feet* (1999) presents a wonderful picture of the crash of realism. In 2001 Rushdie published his other novel titled *Fury*, which, with the help of science fiction, explores Rushdie's postcolonial theme of exile and identity. His nonfiction *Step Across this Line* (2002) presents the dance of history in the contemporary world.

Rushdie's 2005 novel *Shalimar the Clown* deals with the issues of Kashmir. Here Rushdie deals with his romanticized version of Kashmir and contrasts it with the harsh realities of Kashmir after the partition. In 2008, he published *The Enchantress of Florence*, which is a romantic fantasy of 16th-century East and West. It moves to and fro from the tales of Mughal India to Renaissance Italy. Here Rushdie mixes history and myths in order to promulgate a notion of new histories. *Luka and the Fire of Life*, Rushdie's work published in 2010, is about a character named Luka, the younger brother of Haroun and his struggle to save his father from a possible doom.

In 2012, Rushdie published his autobiographical book titled *Joseph Anton: A Memoir*. Rushdie uses his pseudo name, which he used during his years of hiding from Iranian governments, as the title of this novel. This book gives readers a picture of how Rushdie survived during his difficult days. The book also tells us how and why Rushdie entered into one relation after another, especially with different women.

Rushdie published his other novel titled *Two Years Eight Months and Twenty-Eight Nights* in 2015. It deals with jinn and humans. The novel creates a world of fantasy, pervaded by magic and the supernatural. It creates a spellbinding story, blending fact and fiction, and presents the Rushdiean fragmentation of reality. History is again the theme of *The Prophet's Hair* (2016).

In 2017, Rushdie seems to have returned to realism and the contemporary society with his new novel titled *The Golden House*. It is set against the backdrop of contemporary American society. It is a story of love and terror. Intensely satirical, the novel revolves round a character called Nero Golden, a billionaire, who comes and settles in New York City and ultimately creates havoc.

Statement of Problem

Rushdie, in his fictional world, presents a unique view of history. This leads to several questions: Why does he depict history in varied forms sometimes as a record of past events, sometimes as a narrative, or as gossip, and at other times as magic? How does he succeed in depicting history in such varied forms? What does he want to prove by showing multiple faces of history? Why does he question and crumble the long-cherished notion of history and historiography? The research work will revolve around the above raised questions. How Rushdie represents history in his novels is the problem this research will attempt to address to.

Objectives of the Study

This research attempts to explore how Salman Rushdie represents history in its various forms and why he does so. It intends to explore how Rushdiean notion of history and historiography challenges the already established versions of history as well as the definitions of history. The study will also shed light on how Rushdiean perspective on history and historiography get reflected in his selected fictions.

Hypothesis

By mixing up history and fiction, Salman Rushdie creates a new historiography to represent the contemporary world in the form of history as history as facts, as narrative, as gossip and lies, and as magic.

Methodology

The major tools of methodology for this dissertation work will mainly be a thorough and deep textual reading of *Midnight's Children*, *The Enchantress of Florence*, and *Grimus*. Postmodernism and New Historicism will be used as tools to analyze selected texts of Rushdie. Qualitative desk research will be the main method of study.

Relevance of Study

We need to understand the past in order to truly understand anything in the present. Human beings ignorant of the past are no better than animals. Our present stands on the shoulder of our own past. But past comes to us always mediated. Various disciplines attempt to represent the past in various ways. Rushdie, as a novelist, knows how and why literature is produced and similarly, as a historian, knows how and why history is produced. As a very contemporary writer, Rushdie has been able not just to synthesize the ideas of major historians and creative writers but also has been able to redefine history and fiction altogether.

Scope for Future Research

This dissertation explores the give and take between history and fiction and redefines them in a more comprehensive way. It attempts to develop, through a thorough study of Rushdie's major texts, a syncretic model of studying history and literature. Though this study primarily focuses on only three selected texts of Rushdie, the conclusion that it will draw at the end would be applicable to the study of a wide range of literary and non-literary texts concerning history written by Rushdie and others.

Delimitations

A dissertation project like this requires critical study and research that

undoubtedly would be very time consuming. But due to time restraints, and lack of resources, the research work will inevitably have certain limitations. It will primarily focus on the three novels by Salman Rushdie: *Midnight's Children*, *Grimus*, and *Enchantress of Florence*. These three novels will be used as examples to illustrate Rushdiean historiography.

Literature Review: Representation and Historiography

Representation refers to an act of describing or portraying of something or someone. There are various modes of representation as there are various ideas and objects to represent. The mode that may be very suitable to represent an idea may not be so suitable to represent an object. This is why different disciplines have developed different methodologies to represent various kinds of realities. James O. Young offers a comprehensive definition of representation as, “ R is a representation of some object O if and only if R is intended by a subject S to stand for O and an audience A (where A is not identical to S) can recognize that R stands for O” (128). James further elaborates:

So defined. There are three necessary conditions of something's being a representation. For a start, if something is a representation of some object, it must stand for the object. Second. If something is a representation, it must be intentionally used as a representation. This may be called the intentionality condition. Finally, there is the recognition condition: nothing is a representation of an object unless it can be recognized as standing for the object by someone other than the person (or persons) who intends that it be a representation of the object. (128)

Literature is a distinct discipline, in fact the oldest discipline in the history of humankind. Human beings started to produce and consume literature since time immemorial. Literature has its own tools and techniques to represent our societies and its people. In literature, there are hosts of “isms” such as classicism, romanticism, symbolism, realism, surrealism, naturalism, idealism, modernism, postmodernism, historicism, and many more. All these “isms” propose their own methodologies for the act of representation.

Salman Rushdie often chooses historical and literary modes in order to represent the society, cultures, and people. He has devised his own unique theory of history and literature. But let us first discuss how critics have defined history as a mode of representation. In *The Discourse of History*, Roland Barthes writes that “the historian is not so much a collector of facts as a collector and relater of signifiers; that is to say, he organizes them with the purpose of establishing positive meaning and filling the vacuum of pure, meaningless series”(19). Historians need to create meanings out of what they collect. Salman Rushdie, in an interview with the *New Yorker*, professes:

The truth is that truth has always been a contested idea. As a student of history, at Cambridge, I learned at an early age that some things were “basic facts” –that is, unarguable events, such as that the Battle of Hastings took place in 1066, or that the American Declaration of Independence was adopted on July 4, 1776. But the creation of a historical fact was the result of a particular meaning being ascribed to an event.

Rushdie's view on historical representation is similar to the views Jameson forwards.

F. Jameson asserts that third world texts represent reality often in an allegorical form.

He opines that third world texts are to be read as allegories. Jameson writes,

Third-world texts, even those which are seemingly private and invested with a properly libidinal dynamic –necessarily project a political dimension in the form of national allegory: the story of the individual destiny is always an allegory of the embattled situation of the public third-world culture and society. (69)

In Rushdie's texts also, we find individual and personal histories intertwined. As Jago Morrison and Susan Watkins write:

Rushdie is here the historian of the people's voices raised in fierce, personal witness against the elitist histories of the Ghandi clan and the bureaucratic/military/intellectual complex of a country whose history has stubbornly resisted subaltern voices. Rushdie grants the power to his characters to wrest and re-form history in their own images. (21)

Morrison views Rushdie's novels as allegorized history of the nations. However Neil Ten Kortenaar reads Rushdie's novels as postcolonial representations. He argues:

The magic and realism in Rushdie's novel are mutually constitutive: they are both equally Indian and equally modern. They are not separate functions that Rushdie combines in a postcolonial hybrid but are each required in order to think the other and to think the nation. It is a mistake to divide magic and realism, myth and history, along national lines. (24)

The fictional worlds that authors create often try to promote the plurality of worlds and offer a vision. They may not always try to give us directions. As an art object, they may focus on the aspects of beauty and ugliness. Roosevelt writes:

Literature may be defined as that which has permanent interest because both of its substance and its form, aside from the mere technical value that inheres in a special treatise for specialists. For a great work of literature, there is the same demand now that there always has been; and in any great work of literature, the first element is great imaginative power. The imaginative power demanded for a great historian is different from that demanded for a great poet; but it is no less marked . . . on the contrary, very accurate, very real and vivid, presentation of the past can come only from one in whom the imaginative gift is strong. (8)

Imagination is important for both historians and novelist. Myth is the area where imagination and reality often intermingle. In historical representation of reality, historians use myths as evidences or interpretative tools. Myths and history do overlap in most of the Indian novels, as well as in books of history. Patricia Waugh gives the above-mentioned idea as, “history consists of multiple worlds which are fictional” (104). Mixing of history, myths, and fiction gives birth to a new type of writing. Rushdie’s writings also exhibit these features. Rushdie’s texts certainly try to represent the realities of the Indian subcontinent and at times they also depict the world scenarios. They undoubtedly represent history in its various forms. Hutcheon in this regard writes,

The present time consists of the past time and future time. Similarly the novels of Rushdie, Tharoor, Chandra, Ghosh and Ashwin display the status that “the

present, as well as past, is always already irremediably textualised for us, and the overt intertextuality of historiographic metafiction serves as one of the textual signals of this post modern realization. (128)

Hutcheon's conceptualization of history and fiction provides readers and critics with a basis to interpret history and fiction as narratives. Arpana Mahanta in "Allegories of the Indian Experience: The Novels of Salman Rushdie" discusses about the uses and abuses of history, especially in the novels of Salman Rushdie. She draws ideas from different sources such as historiography, Modern and postmodern theories in order to see the interrelation between history and fiction in the works of Rushdie, an immigrant intellectual. Her article includes discussions of British Raj and the systems that they highly prioritized. She criticizes British colonizers and also Rushdie. She calls Rushdie an illegitimate son of the British Empire and tags his writings distorted representation of the East. She writes, "Rushdie's novels are for and about a tiny stratum of India's and Pakistan's elite, inheritors of the British mantle, the deracinated, speaking English, thinking English, dreaming English, Indian terrified, horrified, revolted by Indians and India, yet unable to escape the umbilical bonds" (244). Arpana Mahanta seems in favor of post-colonial historiography and she does not consider Rushdie a true postcolonial thinker.

Rukmini Bhaya Nair in "Text and Pre-Text: History as Gossip in Rushdie's Novels" argues that Rushdie's three main novels – *The Midnight's Children*, *Shame*, and *The Satanic Verses* – constitute a single coherent text, which creatively reorganizes the so-called official history of Indian subcontinent. The writer has provided an explanation in order to counter the abuses hurled upon Rushdie's *The Satanic Verses* as well as other novels. Nair has done so basically by using the term

gossip, which can be, used as a powerful tool to refute so the so-called official history. Regarding the truthfulness in Rushdie's writings, she writes:

In selecting a formal technique of illusionist representation, the writer may well be committed, by the very terms of his craft, to the appropriation of reality that is reified in other powerful codes of conduct such as the religious, and/or other dominant modes of discourse such as the historical. (50)

Nair forwards a claim that like all satire, *The Satanic Verses* works best when it wounds most. Gossip is often taken as something of less importance. It is underrated as conversational medium. Rushdie uses it purposefully as a devastating literary weapon against the claims of historical "truth" and religious morality. Regarding history as a mode of representation, in *Imaginary Homelands*, Rushdie himself writes:

History is always ambiguous. Facts are hard to establish, and capable of being given many meanings. Reality is built on our prejudices, misconceptions and ignorance as well as on our perceptiveness and knowledge. The reading of Saleem's unreliable narration might be, I believed, a useful analogy for the way in which we all, every day, attempt to "read" the world. (96)

It appears that different critics have viewed Rushdie differently. Some critics have taken his philosophy of history positively whereas some have criticized him vehemently. Whatever it is, one thing is for sure i.e., Rushdie is an important voice of our time. Let us be more specific on three selected texts by Rushdie.

Review of *Midnight's Children*

Salman Rushdie is famous all around the world mainly as a postcolonial writer. He has been able to develop some theoretical basis for postcolonial writings and he has also applied many postcolonial agendas in his own writings. Like other

postcolonial writers, he also tries to refute Eurocentric discourses. Instead of Eurocentric history, he has proposed an alternative model of history. Jennifer Santos expresses this view in her acclaimed essay entitled “Historical Truth in Salman Rushdie’s *Midnight’s Children*: A Question of Perspective”:

In *Midnight’s Children*, Rushdie undermines conventional forms of history, narrative, and truth. The validity of memory as a truthful account of history is offered as an alternative to ur-history. Rushdie presents a fragmented view of history that stems from the imperfect and partial nature of memory, as evinces in Saleem’s narcissistic narration.

Santos considers *Midnight’s Children* as a challenge to Eurocentric notion of history. She believes that memory plays a vital role in Rushdie’s writings. Rushdie’s history is in stark opposition to the history written by European masters as well as by national elites.

Similarly, Elleke Boehmer focuses on nationalist historiography that Rushdie attempts to explain in *Midnight’s Children*. In order to resist Eurocentric notion of history, Rushdie draws heavily from Indian myth and folklores. It has been believed that colonial regime destroyed the history of the colonized systematically in order to establish their superiority upon natives. Boehmer writes:

Salman Rushdie’s *Midnight’s Children* comprises a medley of images and stories drawn from Indian myth, legend, film, history, bazaar culture, and conventions of pickle-making images, which separately and together are made to correlate with national self- perception. (198-99)

Boehmer, thus, opines that Rushdie forwards a counter history in order to resist colonialist discourse. One of the ways of doing this is by exploiting the native culture.

Undoubtedly myth and folklores represent the core values of natives and Rushdie is not unknown to this fact. That is why in *Midnight's Children*, Rushdie fuses Indian history with Indian myths.

Similarly, Shirley Chew, an academician who has played a major role in the evolution of Commonwealth and postcolonial studies in both Britain and beyond, describes *Midnight's Children* as a text that focuses on hybridity. She thinks that *Midnight's Children* contains multiple voices with multiple perspectives. It is a kind of encounter between East and West. She comments:

The novel explores the problems of postcoloniality, depicted in the novel as the difficulties in assigning one's point of personal or national origin, the problems in determining one's personal and national history, and the impossibility of finding and achieving personal and national "authentic" identity. The novel expresses these themes of the creation and telling of history, identity, and stories, while simultaneously introducing the problems of postcolonial identity, through connected and dependent forms of hybridity.

(71)

Chew finds Rushdie's strategy of history writing interesting. She thinks that Rushdie foregrounds multiplicity in order to question western modes of historiography.

Post-Colonial perspective is not the only lens that fits Rushdie's texts. For example, many critics and scholars have read *Midnight's Children* as a postmodern novel. Postmodern themes such as hybridity, identity, historical writing and rewritings resonate in this novel. The use of magic realism has also propelled the critics to see *Midnight's Children* as a postmodern novel.

In *Imaginary Homelands*, Rushdie says that *Midnight's Children* is merely his version of India. There may be other versions of India too. Rushdie writes: "What I was actually doing was a novel of memory, so that my India was just that my India, a version and so more than one version of all the hundreds of millions of possible versions" (10). Similarly, Neil Ten Kortenaar discusses the postmodern aspect of the novel by saying:

Rushdie's novel engages in the subversion of every form of convention and authority. It very nearly falls apart –but not quite. It must resist chaos even as it resists tyranny. Liberal freedom is also under threat from the forces of anarchy, in the guise. The forces of chaos are embodied in Shiva, the genetic son of Ahmed and Amina Sinai who has been raised in extreme poverty and is now filled with a violent resentment. The two enemies, tyranny and chaos, are linked: Shiva becomes Indira Gandhi's henchman. (55-56)

Kortenaar thus views *Midnight's Children* as a challenge to colonizer's historiography. He basically focuses on how Rushdie subverts traditional notions of history. O.P. Dwivedi reads *Midnight's Children* from linguistic perspective. He thinks that *Midnight's Children* began a new trend in the history of Indian novel. He appreciates Rushdie's writing style as:

Midnight's Children is being regarded as a foundational text of postcolonialism. The reason for this immeasurable popularity of Rushdie's *Midnight's Children* is to be found in its unique style. Finally, there appeared an Indian writer who told the story, the way it should be told, and who did not write about village life and social ills. (502)

Thus, Dwivedi considers unique story telling techniques and other stylistic devices as Rushdie's strengths. He thinks that the way Rushdie chutnified English language is pretty interesting.

T.N. Dhar also highlights upon Rushdie's post-modernist writing style that is characterized by self-reflexivity. Rushdie has drawn reader's attention to the act of writing itself. By doing this, he has made us aware of the art of writing. Dhar further says:

Midnight's Children exemplifies in a large measure the aesthetic style of postmodernism. It is characterized by a high degree of self-consciousness, because Rushdie uses the techniques of defamiliarization and self-reflexivity. The narrative is addressed to Padma who as an interlocutress also stands for a listener/reader who has old-style notions about art. In response to her constant questionings, Saleem explains and clarifies his art of writing to her, even while he is writing his own account. Through this mechanism, Rushdie also increases the reader's responsibility for understanding the novel. (98)

Rushdie's *Midnight's Children* is undoubtedly a rich mine where multifarious meanings are hidden. Different critics have highlighted different aspects of the novel. Critics have often dealt with obvious issues such as postcoloniality, post modernity, intertextuality, myth, etc. Research works on seemingly minor areas still deserve big attention.

Review of The Enchantress of Florence

The Enchantress of Florence received mixed reviews. Though Rushdie was highly optimistic about this novel, it could meet only little bit of his expectations. Anyway, the novel beautifully depicts the relationship between history and fiction. In this sense, this novel can be a veritable mine for any students of history and literature.

JoAnn Conrad treats the novel as a fictionalized history. She mentions that in *The Enchantress of Florence* readers find “no clear-cut boundary between reality and fantasy” (433). Though the boundary has been effectively blurred, she opines that *The Enchantress of Florence* “is not so much fictionalizing this interconnected world, that spreads on several continents], but bringing it to light” (433). Conrad’s perspective seems to be a bit different from many other Rushdie critics in the sense that the former views *The Enchantress of Florence* more as history, though an alternative one. She does not take fictionalization as something negative for she believes it is at the heart of every human being. We all, as human beings, create, propagate, and believe on fictions.

Similarly, Christopher Hitchens writes, “. . . the worlds of illusion and enchantment seem to collapse in upon themselves, leaving a rich compost of legend and myth for successor generations” (135). *The Enchantress of Florence* uses a lot of historical information but these facts are often blended with imaginative details in order to create a kind of metahistorical document. Hitchens reads this novel as a new history, and even as a new myth or legend. Facts and legends are blended in the novel with such mastery that hardly few readers will be able to draw the line that separates them.

Andrew Martino tags *The Enchantress of Florence* as a substandard novel in Rushdie’s corpus. He believes that Rushdie fails to give a novel as good as

Midnight's Children. Martino asserts that the novel “at best a wonder of intertextual thought, and, at worst, a burdensome game [in which] postmodern calisthenics defeat the number one rule of storytelling: keep the reader captivated” (70-71). Thus, Martino appears very unhappy with what Rushdie accomplishes in *The Enchantress of Florence*.

Not only Martino, Justin Neuman also belittles *The Enchantress of Florence* by calling it an inferior version of *Satanic Verses*. Neuman declares that *The Enchantress of Florence* “eschews the significant stylistic innovation and overt, high stakes cultural commentary that energizes Rushdie’s *The Satanic Verses*” (675). Neuman had expected that Rushdie would give readers even a better novel than *Midnight's Children*, but with *The Enchantress of Florence*, he believes, Rushdie has degraded himself as a writer. At the same time, he does not completely ignore the strength of the novel. It becomes evident as he writes, “Fiction and narrative are powerful transformative forces; narrative is less a means of representing the world than a mode of apprehension, a metaphysical hammer he uses to smash certainties of causality, a forge of the alternate real. For Rushdie, fictions are the world entire” (680). Neuman knows that Rushdie’s fictions are more than fictions. They are the mirrors of the society as well, of past and present. In this light, Neuman considers *The Enchantress of Florence* as a narrative history that represents the society in a unique manner.

William Deresiewicz considers *The Enchantress of Florence* as a simple and straightforward novel. In his words it “exhibits none of the complex allegorical structures, dense system of allusions or broad political implications, in short, none of the satanic ambitions, that both weigh down his major work and give them weight, . .

. it is probably Rushdie's most coherent and readable novel" (34). Deresiewicz finds this novel very fascinating as well as informative. He views *The Enchantress of Florence* as "a powerful tale that has the power to affect our own definitions of reality" (34).

In Johan Huizinga's opinion *The Enchantress of Florence* wonderfully arranges language and events in order to weave a beautiful and at the same time informing tale. Any writer should first and foremost try to, in Huizinga's words, "enchant the reader and hold him spellbound" (132). He believes that Rushdie has been able to achieve that in *The Enchantress of Florence*. Another critic Martin McQuillan, in "Salman Rushdie: Contemporary Critical Perspectives" praises *The Enchantress of Florence* as "a story about storytelling and the intrigue it engenders" (82). In the same book "Salman Rushdie: Contemporary Critical Perspectives" Kenan Malik writes, "the truth that emerges from Rushdie's writing is the truth of the experience of that in-between world, the world of migration and *mélange*, belonging to more than one place, multiple rather than singular" (viii). In Malik's view Rushdie freely works with his knowledge and imagination in order to create his own postcolonial vision of the world. In Rushdie's texts, Malik opines, memory, history, imagination collide.

Salman Rushdie himself makes his philosophy and vision clear in his autobiography titled *Joseph Anton* as he writes:

He needed to connect those worlds to the very different world in which he had made his life. He was beginning to see that this, rather than India and Pakistan or politics or magic realism, would be his real subject . . . the great matter of how the world joined up, not only how the East flowed into the West and the West into the East, but how the past shaped the present while the present

changed our understanding of the past, and how the imagined world, the location of dreams, art, invention and, yes, belief, leaked across the frontier that separated it from the everyday, “real” place in which human beings mistakenly believed they lived. (68-69)

Thus, Rushdie’s *The Enchantress of Florence* has invited a number of favorable as well as unfavorable reviews. Critics have often tried to judge it in comparison to his masterpiece *Midnight’s Children*. However, most of them have often failed to delve deep into the novel and reckon its beauty. This novel is, in fact, a good sourcebook for the students of history and literature. Rushdie himself has told us in many of his interviews that this is his most researched book. How can we, as readers and critics, overlook this scholarly document, just as a figment of Rushdie’s mind?

Review of *Grimus*

Grimus is Rushdie’s first novel, and so far the only novel by Rushdie that looks completely otherworldly. It is a science fiction, a work of fantasy. Though it is not specifically set in any particular time and space, it does forward Rusdhie’s views on literature and history very conspicuously.

Timothy Brennan in “Salman Rushdie and the Third World” writes, “*Grimus* is a volatile playground of western and eastern literary sources that mix together uneasily in a sustained and un-interpretable allegory” (70). Brennan is of course not much happy with Rushdie’s complex writing style.

Catherine Cundy however reads *Grimus* as a powerful philosophical novel that outlines how history and literature are to be viewed and interpreted. She asserts that *Grimus* contains a “bold and unrestrained use of the fantastic and adventure is

internally motivated, justified by, and devoted to a purely ideational and philosophical end” (134). She finds elements of Sufism in the novel that bind everything of the text in a coherent whole.

Another critic James Harrison appears more interested in Rushdie’s *Grimus* for a very different reason. He does not call *Grimus* a complex novel, rather, he asserts that *Grimus* provides readers with “a plethora of possible readings, none of which fits perfectly but all of which are interestingly if in some cases only marginally relevant” (38). Harrison even tries to relate Rushdie’s *Grimus* to Nietzschean idea of the death of the god. In *Grimus* we have a self-proclaimed god.

Ib Johansen considers *Grimus* as a novel that deals with a different world, not ours. He writes that *Grimus* is “a strange blend of mythical or allegorical narrative, fantasy, science fiction, and Menippean satire” (29). He further adds that *Grimus* “deals less with people as such than with mental attitudes” (29). He does not just call *Grimus* a good satirical work, but also calls it an intensely philosophical text.

Uma Parameswaran ponders upon the grotesque elements that are used abundantly in *Grimus* as, “action combines imaginative flights of science fiction, extravagance of fantasy, and clever twists of sexual humor” (“Reading Rushdie”55). She even adds that *Grimus* clearly draws a dividing line between its world and our world. Anyway, in Parameswaran’s view *Grimus* symbolizes mankind’s history, using a fantasy mode of narration. Syed Mujeebuddin highlights the novels otherworldliness as well as web of intertextuality. He writes:

Strange and esoteric at times, *Grimus* has a referential sweep that assumes easy acquaintance with such diverse texts as Farid U d ‘Din Attar’s *The Conference of the Birds* and Dante’s *Divina Commedia* as well as an unaffected

familiarity with mythologies as different as Hindu and Norse. (“Warped Mythologies” 135)

Mujeebuddin tries to expose the text’s links with other myths and legends, especially Hindu and Norse mythologies. Margareta Petersson considers *Grimus* as a collection of disparate elements. She writes:

The novel contains a patchwork of myths collected from different parts of the world. Several scholars suggest that the myths lack inner coherence. I, on the contrary, see them as subordinated to one myth or one symbolic language, the language of alchemy, which also plays a part in Rushdie’s later works. The alchemical tradition is essential in the interpretation of Rushdie’s works because it contests the accusation against him for taking part in western orientalism. It also shows his universal ambitions over and above his more local political and satirical ambitions. (1)

Margareta Petersson is probably right about the alchemy that Rushdie attempts in *Grimus*. It was his first novel and he might have been more ambitious then. In this sense *Grimus* can be taken as a great synthesis of many things, history and literature. Joel Kuortti views *Grimus* as a postcolonial novel. He opines that *Grimus* deals with the issues of identity and human migration. It encompasses a vision of history as well since it deals with the history of mankind symbolically. Kuortti writes:

. . . One could argue that migration is a basic experience of many characters in Rushdie's texts, and migration is seen as a wholly revolutionary process. It leads cultures to mix and change, and for humans to be transformed. Migration means that old certainties are questioned, which in turn leads to doubt and the necessity of compromise – this is one of the themes of *The*

Satanic Verses. All these themes are comprehensible without reference to alchemy. However, this tradition elucidates the themes and clothes them in a powerful symbolic language while at the same time also dressing them in existential and political dimensions.(24-25)

Migration and hybridity are of course very recurring motifs of Rushdie's writings. He constantly deals with issues such as diaspora and multiplicity. The protagonist of *Grimus*, The Flapping Eagle, symbolizes all human beings' desire to search for a better future, and a search for a better history. This is, in fact, Rusdhie's search also.

Research Framework

This dissertation studies Rushdie's novels with a view to showing how he highlights the possibilities of various histories, shattering the traditional objectivist notion of authenticity and homogeneity. In a broader sense, the aim of this dissertation is to study the give and take between history and fiction, using New Historicist and Postmodernist theoretical framework developed by various thinkers such as Friedrich Nietzsche, Michel Foucault, Hayden White, Louis Mink, and Linda Hutcheon etc. The study analyzes a few selected texts from the New Historicist and at times Postmodernist perspectives in order to understand how Rushdie breaks the boundaries between fact and fiction and what its aftereffects are. It forwards an argument that history not only presents past events but also furnishes them with new meanings. Documented history, written from the rulers' perspective, makes a selection of past events from a particular national ideological perspective and presents them as per its need. This sort of act inevitably leads to the suppression of many other marginal voices. Such documented history tends to be monolithic.

This research work contends that Rushdie's novels question the long-cherished notion of history and objectivity by effectively blurring the demarcation line between history and fiction. Thus, we can read Rushdie's novels as subversive texts. His novels are heteroglossic and self-reflexive.

Historical fictions fictionalize historical events and that is what makes them unique. They treat history as a form of discourse written in a beautiful narrative. Borrowing ideas from postmodernist and New Historicist schools, such historical novels effectively interrogate the positivist approach to history and historiography, and denies the validity of empiricist's notion of history. Rushdie's notion of history seems to be very much influenced by the theories of history as theorized by E. H Carr, Hayden white, Linda Hutcheon, and others. The fact is that his novels are highly self-reflexive which ultimately expose how history is also a construct, just like any work of fiction.

In *Midnight's Children*, *Grimus*, and *The Enchantress of Florence*, Salman Rushdie takes history as his material artifact and works on it in order to recreate imaginatively what had been already lost. These novels help us understand how fact and fiction intermingle and give birth to a new reality. Readers can easily figure out how the characters in Rushdie's novels challenge the univocal history writing of the West. Rushdie, in these novels, involves fantasy, magic realism, and parody in a subversive way to challenge not only historical representation but also the definition of history itself. He has given a new name to history, depicting it in various forms.

The study is structured in seven chapters of which the first provides the background to this research work. The second chapter introduces writing as an art of representation. Moreover, it will introduce historiography as a sub mode of

representation. The third chapter deals with the methods of representation of reality. It introduces a syncretic model of understanding history and fiction against which the three selected novels are interpreted. Together these two chapters lay the theoretical framework for the study of Rushdie's novels. The following chapters make a detailed study of the selected novels on the theoretical model developed in chapters three and four. The last chapter presents a final assessment of Rushdie's representations of history in his works.

Chapter II

Representation in History and Literature

Writing as a Mode of Representation

Artists try to represent the reality that they experience or imagine. Therefore, representation is the primary concern of any art. Writers or artists may represent situations and events, actions and issues in different ways. There are various modes of representation available to writers or artists. These modes of representation are ways of organizing texts in relation to some traditions or conventions. We have many conventional or traditional modes of representing reality at our disposal and some new modes of representing reality are also being invented or discovered continually. These new modes of representing reality often convey a fresh, new perspective on reality.

Literature is one mode of representing reality. Fine art is another mode. Similarly, there are various other modes of representing reality. Within the domain of literature, there exist multiple sub modes of representation. Literature broadly represents reality in two ways, poetic mode and historical mode. Most of the imaginative pieces of writings fall under the poetic mode of representation, whereas most of the non-fictional works belong to the historical mode of representation. Postmodern writers have questioned these clear-cut boundaries these days, as we can easily find out lots of instances where poetry contains history and history contains poetry.

A Brief History of Representation in the West

Plato is considered to be one of the most ancient scholars who defined art in relation to the representation of reality. He named representation as mimesis. Plato's disciple Aristotle also discussed over the issue of mimesis but with a little twist. Plato and Aristotle agree on the idea that art mostly imitates or represents nature.

When an artist attempts to imitate an object in nature, s/he will have to choose a certain method and that particular method of representation would require certain tools and techniques and demand certain procedures. What we are being given at the end is after all not the reality but the representation of reality. Plato believes that the "representation intervenes between the viewer and the real, creating illusions, taking viewers away from the real things" (*The Republic* 125). It is because when a viewer or a reader is provided with an art object, his/her options are limited. The viewer will have to rely on what the artist/representor chooses to disclose. What an artist chooses to give us rests upon the various factors embedded in the artist's brain. It is author's choice. The kind of reality artists want to represent to us and the way they want to represent that reality affects the readers' or the viewers' experience of the art.

The most complicated question about the process of representation is –what factors affect the representor or the artist to represent the object the way he or she does? The answer is not so simple and it involves many issues such as the artist's psychosocial conditions, his/her beliefs and values, perceptions, and so on. One thing is for sure that his/her socio-economic conditions affect the artist's choice of representation.

In *Poetics*, Aristotle lays down the blueprint for mimesis. He distinguishes between various art forms by the virtue of the vehicle of representation they use, the

facets of real and imaginary life they symbolize, and lastly the manner of representation. They are:

- a. The means of imitation (the medium such as painting or language)
- b. The object of imitation (some aspect of human action)
- c. The mode of imitation (how something is imitated)

This is how Aristotle segregates the possible modes of representation:

- a. An artist may imitate by narration, either take another personality or speak in his own voice.
- b. An artist may present all his character as living and moving before us.

Hence the modes of narration vary in terms of telling or showing. In fact, mimetic theories conceive of narration as the presentation of spectacle. When Aristotle spoke of mimesis, he was referring to poetry, fine art, and drama, which were the main art forms of arts of his day. Different types of art could use different forms of representation. They interact with reality differently. Miming no doubt had preliterate origins in rituals and imitation of nature.

Plato who was the most influential classical exponent of mimetic theory used the concept of “mimesis” to condemn art. The works of art according to Plato were “thrice removed from the truth” (*The Republic*⁷). According to him since art only imitates, it has no substance or subject of its own and is misleading. Plato thus deprives art of its autonomy. For Plato, art should correspond to the idea, a standard to which all human endeavors aspire. Since art appealed to the senses and not so much a product of the intellect, for Plato, it was an inferior form of representation of human reality.

Aristotle set out to reclaim mimesis as a viable theory of art in his seminal works. After distinguishing between poetic and musical arts, he focused on the object of mimesis or imitation. What can be the possible object of imitation? Aristotle in *Poetics* says that it is possible to imitate men either as superior than in real life, or as inferior, or as they are. Again, he enlarges the scope of imitation and the range of the artist when he says that the artist imitates one of the three objects, “Things as they are or were, things as they are said or thought to be, or things as they ought to be” (6). Thus, the test of mimetic skill is not historical accuracy but instead the skill of the poet to mimic probable human behavior.

In Plato’s understanding, the world of poetry is thus the world of fiction, the world of illusions and fantasies. It is the world of airy nothing and the dimensions of time and place do not bind it. In this sense, imitation for Aristotle is an image-making faculty whereas for Plato, an inferior production. Imitation in Aristotle therefore means an idealized representation of human life.

Another significant contributor in this debate is Sir Philip Sydney who received and used Aristotle’s comments in a little different context. According to Sidney, creative literature can be warranted if it communicates historical or philosophical or moral truths in an energetic pleasing manner. Even the untruths can either be interpreted allegorically as ways of representing an underlying general truth or in the case of the historical poet, as plausible reconstruction of what might well have occurred (*An Apology for Poetry*¹²). The poet, according to Sidney, does not imitate or represent or express things that already exist; he invents new things. He further says in his *An Apology for Poetry* (1595) that the world created by the poet is a better world than the real one. This imaginative world is certainly not the mere

exercise of his imagination, but it has a capacity to reflect our societies and it may also give us some ideas how to rectify them. Only the poet can, by his innovation, construct something that goes beyond nature. He is not imitating the idea as reflected palely in real life, but is directly embodying his own vision of the ideal.

This development in argument leads Sidney away from the Aristotelian notion of imitation. He almost proceeds to develop a theory of “ideal imitation,” the notion that the poet imitates not the mere appearances of reality but the hidden reality behind them. He maintains that the artist constructs a better world than the one we actually live in. Thus, Sydney transfers the Aristotelian notion of imitation from the poet to the reader. The poet does not imitate but creates. It is the reader who imitates what the poet creates.

For Plato, the poet’s world was second-hand imitation of reality and therefore of no value. For Aristotle, the poet could, by proper selection and organization of incident achieve a reality more profound than the actual; for Sidney, the poet creates a world morally better than the real world, for the moral improvement of the reader.

Dryden's *Essay of Dramatic Poesy*(1580) outlines a play as “A just and lively image of human nature, representing its passions and humors, and the changes of fortune to which it is subject for the delight and instruction of mankind”(9). Dryden agrees with Aristotle in describing poetry as a process of imitation but he lays particular emphasis on the fact that a poet can imitate things also as they are said to be or thought to be. He follows Sidney in his belief that poetry is an imitation not only of nature but also of the best in nature and that poetry unites all the scattered beauties of nature, without its deformities. In other words, like Plato he believes that poetry does not merely imitate things as they are but the ideal pattern behind the

appearances and therefore is higher than history. According to Dryden the function of poetry is not only to imitate well but also to affect the soul, or to excite the passions. Poetry heightens the beauties of nature. The poet therefore is neither merely a teacher nor an imitator but essentially a creator.

Dr. Johnson, in his *Preface to the Plays of Shakespeare* (1765) puts forward plays as a better mode of representing social reality. He believes that drama captures just and lively image of human beings in context. Plays have a universal appeal and they affect all human beings differently. The dialogues in the plays give readers or viewers an impression that they are observing their own lives. Dr. Johnson also believes that authors should present an idealized version of the world. This is why he calls artists a moral guide to the society. Regarding Shakespeare, he writes, “the greatness of his reputation has stood the test of time; his highest praise is that he holds up to his readers a faithful mirror of manners and of life” (321). In his view, plays represent reality more faithfully and among plays Shakespearean plays are better in this regard.

However, Romanticism defined art and literary representation a bit differently. Romantic poets and critics gave more emphasis on the creativity of the author. They mostly wrote what they experienced or imagined. They gave more emphasis to poetry than other genres of literature. Because they shifted the focus of art from mimesis to artists’ state of mind, they were not much concerned with the society they lived in. In fact, they were utterly frustrated with their society and the era. Despite all these frustrations, they wrote a lot about nature –internal and external. They worshipped nature as a source of inspiration. They considered nature as God.

Not only nature, they also considered artists as divine for artists could also create a new world, at least imaginatively.

After the Romantics came the Victorians who were very much influenced by the romantic philosophy, so their views also resembled the views of the romantic poets. Victorian era also witnessed some growth in the field of literary representation. Thinkers like Arnold, Ruskin, and Carlyle outlined some important guidelines for literature and literary representation. They were all vehemently against western materialism, and sought spiritual regrowth. In Victorian era, a new mode of representation appeared and that was “Psychological Realism.” Psychological realism attempted to delve deeper into human psyche and represent the inner side of our existence.

T.S Eliot, a twentieth century poet and critic, highly emphasized the idea of objectivity. Like Aristotle he demanded for the faithful mimesis of the everyday reality. Eliot’s this very focus on objectivity in the creation of literary works yielded fruits in imagist movement of literature. Imagist movement of poetry attempted to present ideas and feelings in the form of concrete images. They tried to represent reality as objectively as possible, just like a camera, via poetry.

Another important idea that Eliot put forward was the idea of “tradition.” He calls it a historical sense. This historical sense is what makes a writer traditional. But Eliot’s historical sense denies chronology and conceives of the past as both timeless and temporal at the same time. This contradictory view on literary representation makes Eliot very interesting for critics. In a way Eliot releases history from its historical context. Tradition involves, firstly, the historical sense, and this historical sense obliges a man to write not merely as an individual but also as an embodiment of

the whole nation and antiquity. This historical sense makes an author at once ancient and modern.

Then came the Formalists. They almost discarded the idea of literary mimesis. They defined literature as an art form. According to the Russian Formalists, literature uses literary language to defamiliarize reality. Formalists established the supremacy of form over content in literature.

Out of Formalism, a school called Structuralism emerged. For example, Roman Jakobson was a formalist before but a Structuralist later. In the Structuralist's vocabulary, what an artist creates is a sign, and these signs certainly come from a big cultural reservoir. Art reflects reality. Writing, as an art, aspires to reflect reality.

Jacques Derrida rationalized Plato's objection to art in the twentieth century. He said that human beings are incapable to endure the loss of an original reality against which they gauge themselves to fathom their place in the world. If the duplicate interchanges the reality, then it would result in bewilderment and dislodgment. Derrida writes:

The reflection, the image, the double, splits what it doubles. The origin of the speculation becomes a difference. What can look at itself is not one; and the law of the addition of the origin to its representation, of the thing to its image, is that one plus one makes at least three. (4)

What arises from this argument is that on the one hand we need to know that the world has a single definable source, which can be estimated. On the other hand, the artist with its images of the world reminds us that it is possible to add, supplement, and splinter that world.

After analyzing different views of different theorists from Plato to Derrida, it can be asserted that literature is a mode of representation and it attempts to represent various kinds of realities in various modes. Primarily there are two modes of representation in literature –poetic and historical. Both of these modes have their own strengths and limitations. Some forms of realities may be represented well through the poetic mode whereas some forms of realities may be represented well through the historical mode. And there are some writers and theorists who do not even agree with the idea that history is devoid of poetry and vice versa.

Salman Rushdie, a student of history, often uses history as a representational mode to depict our societies. As a novelist, he also injects poetic mode of representation in his texts. Because he is both a historian and a novelist, he tries to bring both of these modes of representation together.

Historiography as a Sub-Mode of Representation: Views on History

Traditionally history is regarded as a compendium of raw data or facts. These scholars are (un) popularly known as traditional historians and historiographers. They assert that history is just a record of past events, just an archive. Even Aristotle, who was a philosopher not a historian, tried to define history as something factual.

Aristotle wrote:

It will be clear from what I have said that it is not the poet's function to describe what has actually happened, but the kinds of thing that might happen, that is, that could happen because they are, in the circumstances, either probable or necessary. The difference between the historian and the poet is not that the one writes in prose and the other in verse . . . the difference is that the one tells of what has happened, the other of the kinds of things that might

happen. For this reason, poetry is something more philosophical and worthier of serious attention than history; for while poetry is concerned with universal truths, history treats of particular facts. (*Poetics* 43-44)

Aristotle has more faith in poetry than in history because poets depict events and also interpret them. However, there are some historians and historiographers that have understood history in an entirely different way. These scholars see history as a critical enterprise that deals with events of past for a purpose. All historians who record history might have their own perspectives and this subjective lens colors their historical narratives. For these groups of intellectuals, history is a systematic research into the past.

The first groups of scholars who talk about the invincibility of facts are known as traditional historians. Those historians ask for historical objectivity and the methodology that they use is often empiricism. J.B. Bury is a very prominent historian of this school who made a pronouncement in his lecture titled *The Science of History* in the following way:

I may remind you that history is not a branch of literature. The facts of history, like the facts of geology or astronomy, can supply material for literary art; for manifest reasons they lend themselves to artistic representation far more readily than those of the natural sciences; but to clothe the story of human society in a literary dress is no more the part of a historian as a historian, than it is the part of an astronomer as an astronomer to present in an artistic shape the story of the stars. (9)

He thus believed in the scientific aspect of history. He wrote that history is “science, no more and no less” (6). Still many historians faithfully follow the footsteps of J.B

Bury and his legacy has been still carried out by the Positivists and the Annales School of history.

The early traces of the dichotomy between history and literature can be found in the writings of Aristotle. He defined history as truth and literature as made up stories or imaginative pieces of writing. Different thinkers at different points in history, knowingly or unknowingly, have created this insurmountable wall between history and literature and the dichotomy between history and fiction now appears to us as a wall of segregation. Salman Rushdie, through his writings, tries to break down this wall permanently, bringing history and literature to the same level. His writings suggest that history has literary elements and literature contains historical elements. They are not enemies, but old acquaintances. They are not opposite to each other, for there exists many similarities between these two genres of representation.

In order to understand the relation between history and literature, one needs first to examine their evolution. It was Plato who initiated the discussion. Plato didn't distinctly talk about the dichotomy between history and fiction but as readers we can easily perceive that he gave more emphasis to non-poetic writing i.e., philosophy and history than to imaginative writing like literature. He pronounced all literary writings as imitation of imitation and exalted philosophy as a superior genre of knowledge. Plato somehow denigrated poetry. His reckoning of philosophy as a supreme art form brings history near to philosophy and establishes its supremacy as an authentic knowledge.

Plato did not just condescend poetry and poets but he also wanted to banish them from his imaginary republic. He was afraid that poets would manipulate common citizens with their emotional appeals. He writes that, "the tragic poet is an

imitator, and therefore, . . . he is thrice removed from the king and from the truth . . . Feeds and waters the passions instead of drying them up . . .”(7-8). Plato demands that reason should rule, not the heart.

Plato wanted his citizens to be guided by mind or reason, not by heart or emotion. He meant that poetry is all about emotion and philosophy and history are all about mind or reason. The subjects that appeal to our emotion than to our mind, as Plato understood, are less reliable. They are not just lowly but may also be very harmful to young minds.

The same issue had been picked up by Plato’s disciple Aristotle but in a different way. Aristotle dealt with the issue from a more scientific outlook. He gets the credit for initiating this age-long debate very formally, with scientific rigor. Unlike Plato, Aristotle brands the poet as superior to the historian. He believes that the poet is a creator who works by a plan or idea that parallels nature. Not only that he believes in the supremacy of imagination. He maintains that the function of the poet is not to “relate what has happened but what may happen, what is possible according to the law of profitability or necessity” (55). Poets create a self-sufficient world of their own using their imaginative power.

In *Poetics*, Aristotle powerfully posits, “Poetry therefore is a more philosophical and a higher thing than history for poetry tends to express the universal, history the particular” (55). What is particular is of small range. It may be useful in only a few cases but anything that has universal appeal or dimension can serve the purpose of the multitudes. This is why poetry may be, according to Aristotle, more important to us than history.

After a long visible silence, Philip Sidney, a noted 16th century thinker, added something very significant in this debate. His writings consolidated the dichotomy between history and literature by placing poetry on a higher plane than history. In *An Apology for Poetry*, Sir Philip Sidney writes,

The philosopher therefore and the historian are they which would win the goal, the one by precept, the other by example; but both, not having both, do both halt . . . Now doth the peerless poet perform both; for whatsoever the philosopher saith should be done, he giveth a perfect picture of it in some one by whom he presupposeth it was done, so as he couplet the general notion with the particular example. (13)

Sidney is in favor of poetic sensibilities because, he believed, historians stick to individual events whereas poets go for abstractions. Sidney wrote history is “a less fruitful doctrine” (14) for historians lack general reason of things. Sidney’s confidence in poetry also comes from the fact that poets never claim to be absolutely true yet what they say they say with honesty whereas historians claim to be true but the truth is that their writings are also colored by their likes and dislikes.

Another important dimension was added to this debate after about 250 years in the 19th century by a thinker named Hippolyte Taine. He is a very common name to students of history as he is considered the father of historical method. He defined literature as a good platform where history of its production era gets reflected. A student of literature, in Taine’s view, is a student of history automatically. Taine writes, “A great poem, a fine novel, the confessions of a superior man, is more instructive than a heap of historians with their histories” (619). Thus, Taine endorsed

the dichotomy between history and literature, placing literature at the top of the ladder.

Nietzsche's Contribution to Historiography

A German philosopher of the late 19th century, Friedrich Nietzsche, not only challenged the foundations of Christianity and traditional morality but also shook the foundations of traditional historiography. He did not believe in any set of beliefs that hinted at god and afterlife, rather, he celebrated life, inventiveness, power, and the actualities of the world we live in. His primary philosophy was “life-affirmation” and he also prescribed a new motto of living –“live dangerously”.

Nietzsche inspired people to practice sincere questioning of all principles that drain life's extensive energies. Many of our beliefs and practices, according to Nietzsche, are against ourselves and they are unscientific too. In his early writings Nietzsche views that non-rational forces, or in another word Dionysian energy, reside at the foundation of all creativity and of reality. This idea of Nietzsche broke the confidence of traditional historians over themselves because Nietzsche hinted at the fact that human beings are not completely rational creatures. In his essay titled “On Truth and Lies in a Non-moral Sense,” rejecting the idea of universal constants, Nietzsche posits that truth is:

A mobile army of metaphors, metonyms, and anthropomorphisms, in short, a sum of human relations which have been enhanced, transposed, and embellished poetically and rhetorically, and which after long use seem firm, canonical, and obligatory to a people: truths are illusions about which one has forgotten that this is what they are; metaphors which are worn out and without

sensuous power; coins which have lost their pictures and now matter only as metal, no longer as coins. (46-47)

Nietzsche thus questions the confidence of a positivist historian. His ideas give a twist to our worldview. After all arbitrariness prevails in all aspects of human life and “truth” is nothing more than the brainchild of stable agreements. In an essay titled “Untimely Meditation” Nietzsche proposes alternative ways to write read and history. He writes:

Is it true that only by imposing limits on this unhistorical element by thinking, reflecting, comparing, distinguishing, drawing conclusions, only through the appearance within that encompassing cloud of a vivid flash of light – thus only through the power of employing the past for the purposes of life and of again introducing into history that which has been done and is gone – did man become man: but with an excess of history man again ceases to exist, and without that envelope of the unhistorical he would never have begun or dared to begin. What deed would man be capable of if he had not first entered into that vaporous region of the unhistorical? (64)

Nietzsche’s claim here is that the standard of “life” is a more unrelenting and higher concern than that of knowledge. Our pursuit for knowledge should aid our life for we have only one life, not many as major world religions proclaim.

Nietzsche has provided many important insights for poststructuralism and postmodernism. His bold rejections of many of our conventions such as the rejection of facts, the rejection of essences, and the jamboree of the plurality of interpretations and of the fragmented self have provided a basis for many Poststructuralists and Post Modernists to develop their theories of representations and truths. The age-old

dichotomy of history and fiction crumbles as it collides with Nietzsche's assertion that the truth is but an ambulatory legion of metaphor. Nietzsche made many thinkers understand that our world is characterized by its relativity and everything has to be understood in relation to each other.

People often tend to take useful things uncritically. Nietzsche asks us to take everything critically, be it a history book or a novel. Yes, Nietzsche demands a critical reception of history. He asks people to use history for life. One should be tactful in uses of history for it may help us as well as damage us. There is no guarantee that knowledge will always help us.

According to Nietzsche, the historian as a judge should study history critically, picking out some relevant events of the past, and developing critical attitude to those events. Nietzsche proposes the concept of supra-historical being who does not just consume history but is also capable of using it to solve the problems of history. In this regard, Nietzsche writes:

When past is analyzed critically, then we grasp with a knife at its roots and go cruelly beyond all reverence. It is always a dangerous process that is a dangerous process for life itself. And people or ages serving life in this way, by judging and destroying a past, are always dangerous in danger. For since we are now the products of their aberrations, passions, mistakes and even crimes. (qtd. in Adams 31)

Nietzsche thus forwarded the idea of the relativity or subjectivity of truth.

History/Discourse determines the truth and that truth may help sustain the discourse.

He reiterates, "Everything has become: there are no eternal facts just as there is no absolute truth" (5). Historical facts are only perspectives, determined by power.

History and literature, in this sense, are not two extremes –as if one presents the truth and the other the lies.

Nietzsche's notion of historiography radically opposes the traditional understanding of time and history. Nietzsche asserts that historical development neither is nor can be completed since the completion of history is not just impossible but unwanted too because it would lead to an erosion of mankind and our history. Nietzsche believes that history is not a rational process but it is full of blindness and injustices. Here he contradicts Hegelian idealism and its implication towards history and historiography. In this regard, Nietzsche becomes one of the early thinkers who question traditional historiography.

Michel Foucault's Views on History

Similarly, another influential thinker who gave historiography a twist is Michel Foucault (1926-1984). He views that the discourses including the texts are the embodiments of power. Foucault defines text as something entangled into the social and political sphere of its production era. Foucault's attempt to link texts with history has given a new direction to history and literary writings.

Emphasizing the intricate relation between the text and an ideology, Foucault succeeds in historicizing the text and textualizing the history. A text, as Foucault believes, never represents or reflects pre-existing entities and orders of a historical situation. Texts rather speak of the power structures, which are after all the products and propagators of power. A text, in Foucault's view, speaks of "history" but not as it is described by traditional historicists and Marxists. It buries within itself the "situatedness" of institutions and social practices. Foucault in *Archaeology of Knowledge* writes:

History, in its traditional form, undertook to “memorize” the monuments of the past, transform them into documents, and lend speech to those traces, which, in themselves, are often not verbal, or which say in silence something other than what they actually say; in our time, history is that which transforms documents into monuments. (7-8)

So, a text becomes “a history of otherwise” in that it presents a historical situation, not a background but as something with which it can have constant interaction. Text is the product of power and at the same time it produces and maintains power. It is not just the documentation of monuments, but is rather a kind of monument in itself.

Foucault very well understood how historians are situated in a certain historical framework and he knew that historians couldn't escape that “situatedness”. Since historians are “embedded” in the social practices, it is, by this logic, clear that what they write entails their own perspectives. So, a historian's “situatedness” plays a very crucial role in the making of his/her book.

Foucault's ideas on history and reality contributed to the rise of a new historical method that we call an “alternative history.” Alternative history can be considered as a kind of counter history, that not only resists the official monolithic version of past but also offers a new way of understanding the same. Assessing Foucault's influence in the field of critical thinking, Hazard Adams in *Critical Theory since Plato* writes, “Foucault's influence in a literary theory has been strong among revisionist literary historians known as ‘new historicists’ who study the culmination of power through society and the literary texts that are part of it” (1133).

Foucault admits that history cannot escape human fabrication for it involves historians and their inadequate tools. Historians position, their likes or dislikes, and

shape the nature of history that they write. The way a historian records and interprets historical events reflects the historian's situatedness itself. If we understand history this way many questions may arise in our minds such as: How is history different from fiction, is history just a form of literary writing? Foucault's answer would be "yes" to a large extent. Foucault neither believes in absolute objectivity of history, nor does he believe in total subjectivity of literature.

Similarly, Foucault in *The Archeology of Knowledge* comments upon the nature of the anthropocentric notion of history. He sees history as not having a casual law or final goal but as having a network of power relations. Foucault developed a genealogical model of history. He describes genealogy as a diachronic method to study and understand history. Genealogy, for him, is an effort to undermine all absolute grounds and to demonstrate the origins of things only in relation to/in context with other things. Whereas archaeological model seeks to uncover the layers of civilization by positioning in them the stability of systems of thought that stay long for an era and come to a sudden end, genealogy, on the other hand, turns towards the problems of power and practice. In this regard, Foucault says, "the search for descent is not the erecting of foundation: on the contrary, it disturbs what was previously considered immobile; it fragments what was thought unified; it shows that heterogeneity of what was imagined consistent with itself" ("Nietzsche" 88). According to Foucault, Genealogical model of history has a big scope since it attempts to go after histories than with a single totalizing grand narrative.

A historian, for Foucault has three tasks. First, while confronting the "one" reality, a historian should be in favor of the use of history as a "parody". Second, he should be against a singular human identity. And thirdly, the "investigations" should

be directed against the so-called absolutism and objectivity (“Nietzsche” 87). This is how Foucault tries to redefine the role of the historian.

Foucault has a very radical stand regarding historiography. He defines history in three dimensions. First, he rejects the absolute truth or origin and argues for fictionalized history and historicized fiction. Second, he refutes the so-called linearity of history, and the third dimension is that history “divides our emotions, dramatizes our instincts, multiples our body and sets itself against itself” (qtd. in Shreedharan 285). Foucault casts doubt on the possibility of historical truths “because historical writings are always entangled in tropes” (Selden 102). Discourses are manufactured within an actual world of power struggle and they are used as a means to gain or, sometimes even to subvert power. Discourse is determinant in the formation of truth and maintenance of power relations. Objective knowledge of history is never possible.

Foucault’s notion of power has been often misunderstood and misinterpreted. They often tend to understand Foucauldian power as a negative term. But Foucault says:

In defining the effects of the power as repression, one adopts purely juridical conception of such power, one identifies power with a law which says no, power is taken above all as carrying the force of a prohibition . . . what makes power hold good, what makes it accepted is simply the fact that it doesn’t only weigh on us as a force that says no, but that it traverses and produces things, it induces pleasure, forms knowledge, produces discourse. (1139)

Thus, Foucault opens up a highway to go beyond the traditional definitions of history and literature, saying that historical writing is always entangled in tropes. Every

discourse is involved in power and discourses are rooted in social institutions. Hence, discourse is not only inseparable from power but also a means of achieving power.

Facts do not speak for themselves, be it in literature or in history. So, each society has its own versions of truth. Furthermore, power diffuses itself in the system of authority and the effects of truth are manufactured within discourses. But the discourses in themselves are neither accurate nor incorrect. Foucault sees truth as a product of power relations and it changes as systems change. In this sense, literature and history are narratives and they have many commonalities. These ideas of Foucault became watershed for the New Historicists to develop their theories of history and literature.

Historicity of Text and Textuality of History

New Historicism offers a distinctive approach, a rigorous method, to read and understand historical and literary narratives. It is highly political in nature for its open alignments with left wing politics. Indeed, at times New Historicism seems almost designed to provide a foundation for the leftist interpretations of literature.

The New Historicist movement is an important insight to examine the relationship between literature and history. A large number of scholars worldwide have been practicing its methods of interpretation. Jonathan Dollimore, Stephen Greenblatt, Don E. Wayne, Catherine Gallagher, Arthur F. Marotti, Jean E. Howard, Stephen Orgel, Peter Stallybrass are some of the prominent New Historicists. New Historicists have given historical research a new momentum. It is due to the new historicists' achievement that we have started treating public as well as personal documents with equal respect. New Historicists treat documents such as reports, religious tracts, and labor statistics as objects of historical inquiry.

Stephen Greenblatt's *Renaissance Self-Fashioning: From More to Shakespeare* talks about the main focus of the movement. New Historicists consider literature as a social force that contributes to the making of individuals. In the introduction of *Renaissance Self-Fashioning*, Greenblatt writes:

If literature is seen only as a detached reflection upon the prevailing behavioral codes, a view from a safe distance, we drastically diminish our grasp of art's concrete functions in relation to individual to institutions, both of which shrink into an obligatory "historical background" that adds little to our understanding. (VI)

Literature acts as a form of social regulator. In this regard, Marxist approach and the approach taken by new Historicists seem to be similar. Both of them interrogate the traditional view of literature as a sovereign entity and try to liquefy the literary text into the social and political context from which it arises. The truth may be that New Historicists try unambiguously to solve the theoretical strain in Marxist criticism, relating the artistic production to the material base. In this sense, one may reasonably argue that New Historicism has consolidated Marxist criticism by providing it a methodology.

Every text is to be analyzed in relation to its context i.e., history. Text and context cannot be separated, as they are complementary to each other. Because of this nature, it would be very unwise to try to put them in any sort of hierarchical ladder. Readers will find history in literature and literature in history.

The Positivist view of history bases its historical research on experience and these historians were confident to excavate and interpret the events of the past accurately. "Events as they occurred" was their watchword. On the contrary, the New

Historicists accept history only as a contemporaneous activity of recounting or signifying the past. New Historicists don't believe in any monolithic narration of past, they say histories, not History. Without some sense of time and place in which a text is composed, it is difficult to decipher it. Trying to decode a text without its context is probably just like trying to unlock a safe without its password. A text unlocks itself to its readers once the reader is able to acknowledge various environments that may have shaped the text such as social, cultural, economic, scientific, intellectual, and literary.

The difference between the new historicists and the old historicists is that both are interested in establishing a relationship between history and text but the new historicists give high emphasis to history and they also look at it from a broader perspective. New Historicists see a two-way relationship between history and literary text i.e., they influence each other. New Historicists argue that literature does not reflect history as a mirror; rather it shapes and constitutes history.

Traditionally, history and literature are viewed as stark opposites. Commonly it is believed that literature contains fiction and history contains facts. Historians of the Positivist School sided with one of the two poles, history or literature, as superior to the other. New Historicism reacted against such assumptions for they see literature in history and history in literature.

Literature and history are interdependent upon one another. All texts, be it literature or history, are embedded in specific historical contexts. Louis Montrose argues that the key concern of the New Historicist critic is the historicity of texts. By the phrase the textuality of histories, Montrose means to say, "access to a full authentic past is never possible" (410). Our knowledge is a product of narratives and

narratives are stories, written by authors employing the techniques of story writing. These narratives mediate our knowledge of the past. Past survives with the help of such narratives. Events don't have a long life. Once they happen, they may be over. If they are to survive, they will survive as stories. So, without narratives, we know nothing of the past.

Because all writings are a kind of narrative, literary writings are also equally important from the historical point of view. They also mediate history, representing the past in their own way. Sometimes, the historical traces that they have may give a truer picture of the society than history books do.

New Historicists give equal attention to all the inscribed documents. They make an appraisal of the available documents before selecting or rejecting them. They try to understand the textuality of history and historicity of text. Peter Barry observes, "New historicists believe that every strand of knowledge or information is available to us in a textualized form" (175). New Historicists do not discriminate between historical and non- historical text because both are the expressions of the same era. New Historicists are involved in "an intensified willingness to read all of the textual traces of the past with the attention traditionally conferred only on literary text," writes Stephen Greenblatt, one of the pioneers of New Historicism (qtd. in Hawthorne 197). The production of literary texts, as New Historicists believe, is a cultural practice, not just the creation of a writer's idiosyncratic creative frenzy. We cannot make an absolute distinction between literary text and other cultural practices.

According to Greenblatt all types of art, including literature, are "embedded within the social and economic circumstances in which they are produced and consumed" (*The New Historicism* 57). But these circumstances are not stable in

themselves. He believes that there can be no art without social energy. Greenblatt believes in the circulation of social energy in every kind of production. Written texts are not solely the creation of an individual author rather they are the products of social, cultural and political forces.

Texts embody the existing values and ideologies of their own production era. Regarding the impossibility of subverting the dominant culture, another New Historicist Louis Montrose says, “a text creates the culture by which it is created, saves the fantasies by which it is shaped, begets that by which it is begotten”(qtd. in Brannigan 169). Literary or non-literary texts speak the voices of the ruling class because elites often own the capacity to disseminate their concerns in the form of ideology. The new historicists examine different literary and non-literary texts in order to understand how those texts play a key role in mediating power relations of the society.

All texts are discourses that are involved in power relations. These representations are, therefore, used “to produce subversion only in order to contain that subversion”(Brannigan 172). Literary texts and non-literary texts shape the worldview of a particular period, by determining the power relations of the society. Greenblatt claims that texts of all kinds offer us indications of subversion, but only in order to enclose subversive elements meritoriously.

Texts mediate knowledge of the past. Historical documents are also a kind of texts. The primary question then would be how they are interpreted, than what they contain. This is why New Historicists assert that history is only knowable through interpretation, argument and speculation. For this reason, literature and history must be viewed subjectively.

The traditional historians assert that there exists unity, homogeneity and totality in history. On the contrary, New Historicists point out to the contradictions, heterogeneity and fragmentations in history. According to New historicists, there is no single history, rather a multiplicity of histories. Louis Montrose says there has been “a shift from history to histories”(“Professing” 411). This shift from history to histories has brought about many changes in the conception of history and literature.

All writers as well as readers are tied to their own historical situation. They cannot transcend these historical forces. We are the product of our own history. That is what has shaped us. In this regard Greenblatt writes:

The human subject itself began to seem remarkably unfree, the ideological product of the relations of power in a particular society . . . we can't escape history . . . our knowledge and understanding is the part of history itself. So our own voice is the voice of the dead. The voices of the dead are heard in the voices of living through the textual traces. (“Renaissance”496)

Thus, it is very safe to conclude that we can never have an unbiased and objective explanation, estimation or conception of a text, for we are all the time entangled with the discourses of our own history.

According to the New Historicists, there are no definite patterns of cause and effect in history. Such patterns are to be imposed by the readers. Knowingly or unknowingly readers impose their own patterns in the act of reading and interpret the texts. History, in this sense, is not a coherent body of objective knowledge. It follows not the cause-and-effect pattern. It is historians who, through their imaginative and critical mind, construct the causes and effects of history. History, in this regard, is a subjective interpretation of facts. The past is made intelligible using the schema of the

present. Hence, there can be as many versions of the same event of the past as many readers read them.

For the reason that history can never escape human manipulation and fabrication, we cannot view history as a set of fixed, objective facts. It is not only literature that is the product of subjective interpretation; history is also the product of subjective interpretation, to a large extent. Historians' presuppositions and prejudices color an act of writing history. History, in this sense, is very near to fiction. Different historians might interpret the same differently, therefore there might exist many versions of the same event. It is not the content that the history books contain but the existing power structure of the society that determines which version is true and which one is fabrication. This is why New Historicists assert that there is no discrete segregation line between fiction and history.

Literature is a social and cultural paradigm shaped by more than one cognizance. It is a matter of individual genius and at the time historical forces. Literature is historical, in the sense that it is not predominantly the record of one mind's endeavor to solve certain formal tribulations. Therefore, through the culture and society that produced literature, one should attempt to grasp a literary text. Thus, literature has to be understood, not as a discrete category of human activity, but as an essential part of it. It has to be understood in relation to society.

It is not just literature that is a social construct. Man is a social construct. He is the messy arrangement of social and political forces. Human nature can never transcend history rather we are a part and parcel of history. A medieval man belongs, inescapably and irretrievably, to the middle age. The voice of the era speaks through him/ her. A modern man is not in a linear fashion linked to that medieval man. There

are ruptures in history. History is a series of “rifts” between ages and men. As a consequence, historians or critics are imprisoned in their own “historicity”. This is what New Historicists believe. No individual can upsurge above his own social materializations and his own ideological nurturing. It is not possible to understand the past on its own terms. Past is interpreted in the light of the present. Viewed this way, the best a historicist can hope to accomplish is to use the text as a basis for the reconstruction of an ideology. Such an approach makes traditional historical scholarship stand on its head.

Traditional scholarship, with its generally agreed-upon point, aims at the retrieval of the original meaning of a literary text. However New Historicists sees this as a futile attempt, for they believe, such recovery of meaning is impossible. By contrast, New Historicists concentrate on the retrieval of the original ideology that gave birth to the text. Traditional scholars from a long time had neglected this dimension of critical interpretation. It was because the “enabling presumption” of ideology was unavailable to them.

Literary texts themselves subdue the processes by which they build ideology. A traditional formalistic approach that treats the text as a self-contained entity can never trace these ideological maneuvers. Only a New Historicist approach, treating the text as one element in the ideology of an age, can hope to lay them bare. New Historicists can do this because they are critical of the “enabling conjectures” of their forebears.

Similarly, Post Structuralists also endorse the New Historicists’ idea of textuality with an argument that the text is not aloof from the neighboring context, that there is contiguity between text and whatever might once have been seen as

“outside” it. To New Historicists, artistic fictions do not imitate human action but mediate it. It means the fiction is described as the lens through which a certain representation of the human experience is brought into focus. So literary texts shape rather than just reflect their era of production.

New Historicists not only succeed in shattering the old paradigms in the understanding history but also succeed in offering the new ones. Breaking loose from the extremely narrow precincts of literary study as it is now practiced within the academia, New Historicists like to image themselves as challenging the norms of writing and reading (non) literary texts.

A plethora of interpretations, seemingly coming from two diametrically opposing sides, invaded the academia in late seventies and early eighties. New Criticism of 1930s tried to explicate all texts as self-sufficient, and autonomous entity. On the other hand, the poststructuralists of 60s, led by Jacques Derrida, attempted to expose the fundamentally unstable and internally contradictory nature of literary texts. They initiated a debate whether anything was absolutely comprehensible or not. At such times of confusion, New Historicism stood up with a signal post for literary criticism. New Historicism was primarily a method for the political interpretation of literature. They confirm that the material or economic conditions play a crucial role in the production of literature. This idea takes them very near to Marxist critics.

New Historicists and the Marxists have similar assumptions. First of all, they call into question the traditional view of literature as an autonomous living entity. Second, they try to liquefy the literary text into the social and political milieu from which it issued. In fact, New Historicist’s newness ensues with the ideas laid down by

the Marxists. Both relate literature, a product of human consciousness and imagination, with the material conditions of the society.

Literature is shaped by history and in turn tries to create or guide history too. Though New Historicism considers history as an important contributor of literary texts, it does not consider history as the sole producer of the texts. Rather history and literature are complementary to each other and they have dialectical relationship. This reciprocal relationship brings them both to the same level. New Historicists would reject any extreme view about literature and history. Literature is not a pure propaganda and nor is history pure facts. Literature is free, to some extent, from external factors. Humans, with their creative brains produce literary texts. But at the same time our brains are a product of the society where we live in.

Hayden White's Contributions to Historiography

Hayden White is of the opinion that history and fiction are both a kind of narrative. He is fiercely against the notion that history gives us only facts. Since narratives are entangled with the linguistic system and social discourses, history lacks any absolute truths or facts in its narratives. He writes, "When you want to ask the question . . . "What is man?," all you've got is history!" (White ix). In his understanding, men are the products of their history.

Historians work on the pool of data and they do not or even cannot use every single data gathered. They will have to make choices, prioritizing certain facts over others. They establish a rationale behind such narrativizations and weave stories of the past. Behind this, the historians' own limits and sometimes prejudices may be at work. Historians give meaning or create sense out of the chaos of historical records. Historians use various interpretive tools for this purpose. Some of the prominent tools

that historians use are emplotment, argument building, and interpretations. Only after a rigorous application of the above procedure, the finished historical narrative comes to the readers.

Literary writers choose their stories, craft them beautifully, and present them to the readers. Similarly, historians are also involved in the process of selection and exclusion. It is not true that only litterateurs have infinite possibilities of story making, a historian also may also have limitless possibilities, which primarily arise due to the blending of fact and fiction. The blending of fact and fiction shapes the nature of their narratives. Some historians may add more imaginative detail, whereas some may try to keep them to the minimum.

In comparison with a historian, writers of fiction may have more liberty over their material but the former also may enjoy a certain degree of liberty, in the use and manipulation of their resources. Historians also present events with the help of plot and character. They will have to order events in a spatial and a temporal sequence. Historians also may use the techniques such as flashback and foreshadowing, while narrating events. Historians' presentation of facts may exert an influence over the readers and somehow control meaning. Good historians may somehow be able to make readers believe what they want them to believe. The silences and fissures in the text also play equally significant role in the establishment of truth. Historians may hide many facts in order to achieve their goals. Ricoeur quotes Danto, "for the whole point of history is not to know about actions as witness might, but as historians do, in connection with later events and as parts of temporal wholes" (147). Danto's views on historians are applicable to the process of fiction writing as well.

Hayden White does not just say that history is a kind of narrative, but also goes to the extent of saying that history is more an art than a science. He acknowledges the fact that historical data are important in history but at the same time he asks us to be aware of the distortions that may take place in the recording of historical events. To have an access into the past and bring the data as it actually took place is not possible. History is to be understood not as the past in itself but the interpretation and representation of the past. Such attempts of representations become a part of the narrative. The basic elements of both history and fiction, as White believes, are the narrative itself. Both genres are primarily narratives. Facts and figures are just components of history. They alone don't make history in its totality. So, the traditional definition of history as a collection and presentation of facts seems lopsided. Hayden White in *Metahistory* asserts:

In order to realize these aims, I will consider the historical work as what it must manifestly is –that is to say, a verbal structure in the form of a narrative prose discourse that purports to be a model, or icon, of past structures and processes in the interest of explaining what they were by representing them.

(2)

Elements of a narrative such as events, plot, characters, setting, etc. are found in history as well. Historians' reliance on various narratives, eyewitnesses, and their fictions bring historical writings near to literary writings. Eyewitnesses will report an event as they felt it, not as it took place. According to White, due to such complexities, historians' attempt to recapture the past as it took place is doomed to failure.

Historians' discretion or their biases play a very crucial role in their selection and exclusion of certain facts and figures of the past. When historians omit certain crucial information from their history book for their own interests, they are somehow lying to us. They may be propagandist historians. But as readers we cannot always be sure who is doing what and for what reason. There may be a purpose behind such omitting.

Some of the feminists have claimed that patriarchy systematically and thoughtfully erased a name of a woman rebel called Lilith from the pages of history in order to establish the male as the superior race. They claim that Lilith, a powerful woman, who is also known as Adam's first wife, did not submit to the desires of her husband easily. This is why her name has been deleted. Such omission of some crucial information may stir serious consequences in the long run. Questioning the reliability of historians as scientists, White writes:

What really happened in the past, therefore, the historian must first prefigure as a possible object of knowledge the whole set of events reported in the documents. This pre-figurative act is poetic as much as it is precognitive and pre-critical in the economy of historians' own consciousness. It is also poetic and so far as it is constitutive of the structure that will subsequently be imaged in the model offered by the historian as a representation and explanation of "what really happened in the past."(30-31)

Thus, Hayden White considers history to be a unique historical narrative. In recording historical events, historians as well as creative writers follow the rules of story writing.

Louis O. Mink's Notion of History

Louis O. Mink, a philosopher of history, challenges the traditional notion of history and historiography with his proposition that history is also a kind of narrative. He establishes a strong link between history and fiction. According to Mink, historians use narrative techniques while describing the past events. Human beings comprehend things and events with the help of narratives. Narrative is a kind of cognitive instrument to us. Mere data are not enough for history. Historians use narrative techniques to represent the past. Mink agrees that history and fiction do have differences. However, he strongly believes that they share more commonalities than differences. Mink writes:

Researches of historians, however arduous and technical, only increase the amount of precision of knowledge of facts that remains contingent and discontinuous. It is by being assigned to stories that they become intelligible and increase understanding by going beyond “what?” and “when?” to “how?” and “why?” (47)

Knowledge of the past is full of ruptures. These ruptures are to be filled up by historians and readers. In the course of filling up those gaps, historians weave stories out of the past events. Because of this reason, history is organized like a story. It has a beginning, middle and an end. Events are to be ordered in some fashion in order to make them intelligible. In the process of telling past events, historians rely on their memory, imagination and, of course, conceptualization.

Mink in his “law model” explains how history is written or recorded. Historians need to establish cause-and-effect relationship of all the events that they intend to present and for this they rely on their own rationality. With reason, they

establish the link. Place yourself in the shoes of the character and add details wherever necessary! In this regard, Mink expresses, “Rational model undertakes an account of explanations of intentional actions, which show that the action performed, was the reasonable thing to do for someone situated like the agent in those circumstances” (123). We all know that human beings do not act rationally all the time. Such rationalization by the historians may be wrong at many places. Law model fails to work if an agent works irrationally. When historians feel that rational theory may not be much applicable in certain situation, they may concentrate on an alternative model i.e., the narrative model.

In order to establish the relationship between cause and effect, the narrative model suggests us to use our imagination. Use your subjectivity where necessary because whether you like it or not your subjectivity colors your writings, be it fiction or history. In comparison to the law model narrative model is less restrictive. Mink admits, “The difference between narrative history and fiction lies not in the kind of intelligibility and understanding they respectively afford, but in the nature and kinds of evidence for the truth of their statement” (123). Thus, Mink provides historians methods for writing history and fiction and at the same time he provides readers insights to understand better the nexus between history and fiction.

Postmodern Challenge to Traditional Historiography

Postmodern historians believe in the presence of gaps and discontinuities in history. These scholars question the possibility of historical objectivity. By pointing out the shortcomings of conventional historiography, they propose a new method of historiography. Traditional historiography strongly believes that history reflects the past and the past can be represented as it took place. Up to the nineteenth

century, most of the historians cherished this notion of history. According to Onega, traditional historiography viewed history, “as an empirical search for external truths corresponding to what was considered to be absolute reality of the past events” (12). Onega is also very suspicious of the claims of absolute objectivity of traditional historians.

One of the most prominent historians who opposed this traditional notion of history is Hayden White. White himself has been counted as a postmodern historiographer and his views on history as a mixture of fact and fiction has given historiography a new turn. Hayden White opines that history cannot be represented without any mediation. Since historical representations need some sort of mediation, be it of language or of historian, such narratives do have some amount of distortions.

Thus, conceptualizing history as a narrative, White provides a basis for postmodern historiography. Due to the influence of thinkers like Jacques Derrida, Jacques Lacan, Roland Barthes and others, historical or other writings are entangled in the web of intertextuality. Similarly in Abrams words, history is, “a discourse which consists of representations, that is, verbal formations” (183). Following the footsteps of Roland Barthes, Derrida and others, Post Modern historiography proposes that historical accounts are also an ideological construction and absolute objectivity in them is a chimera. Since all texts are a matter of discourse formation, historical accounts also need a very critical reading.

Postmodern Historiography views history as a heterogeneous entity. Traditional historians see history in isolation, apart from the socio-cultural milieu out of which a historical text emerges. It is an error according to postmodern historians. History and literature are to be studied in alignment with the larger social contexts.

History is an “ongoing series of human constructions” (Cox and Reynolds 4). History is multi-vocal. Hayden White in *Metahistory* claims “narrative form is the only possible form of representation in the writing of history” (9). Since historical facts alone do not make any history, historians need to supply details where necessary.

Historians decide which facts are to be highlighted and which one to be suppressed. Traditional historians of the nineteenth century were optimistic about the scientific procedures. They had a faith in science and believed that scientific method will help them represent past as it was. On the contrary, postmodern historians took raw data as always incomplete. They are of no great value until someone gives them a flow and makes some sense out of them.

Traditional historians use different aides to record history. Some of the handy tools are archives, researches, and eyewitnesses, and so on. They use all these tools and techniques to meet the demand of authenticity. They use quotations, citations, footnotes, and bibliography to consolidate what they write. However, many historians these days don't believe on what traditional historians talk about history. These new historians may try their best to meet objectivity but they are at the same time aware of what happens when we write history. Himmelfarb beautifully puts his remarks against traditional historians when he says that they:

. . . conceal its ideological structure behind a scholarly façade of footnotes and facts . . . to “demythicize” or “demystify” this history, postmodernism has to expose not only its ideology – the hegemonic, privileged, patriarchal interests served by this history but also its methodology, the scholarly apparatus that gives it a specious credibility. (75)

Himmelfarb shares postmodern view of history so he believes in the narrative nature of history. Going against any official history, thinkers like Himmelfarb question the power structures and try to expose how official history suppresses minorities and their voices. Elisabeth Wesseling also has a similar view regarding state sponsored history. She writes, “the absence of ethnic minorities from . . . history does not result from some sort of natural, automatic process, but from deliberate exclusion” (166). Her proposition is that history is not an empirical science.

Postmodern historiography gives voice to those suppressed stories. It believes in the plurality of history. Because these historians attempt to unearth such suppressed voices, we can, with certainty, say that postmodern historiography aims at freeing itself from the fake tyranny of truth. Breaking history free from the shackles of such tyrannies of the dictators, postmodern historians dream to liberate history.

We still have not been able to find out a satisfactory answer to the question whether history is a science or art, yet many theories of history and historiography so far hint at the same answer –history is partly science and partly art. This hybridity is what makes history an important area of study. The positivists, the first of the modern day historical theorists, were of the opinion that history is a science. Annales School also believed in the supremacy of facts. Marxist school of history also focuses on the depiction of society as it is/was. These schools of thought believe that history contains objectivity and it is beyond any doubt a true reflection of the society. They all stand upon the merit of facts and they have a faith that historical truth is very firm and stable. Representation of the past is unproblematic because, as they believe, facts are immutable in nature.

Unlike these empiricists, postmodern historiography treats history as a narrative, more or less just like a work of fiction. There is no single true story, they say. History has to be understood as something written through the use of various narrative strategies, such as emplotment, tropes, argument building, and ideological implication. Historians gather historical data and then interpret them using certain techniques. The techniques that they choose would be their own decisions. The way they use these tools and techniques brings difference in the historical document that they produce. Readers often take history book as a product and mostly fail to acknowledge the rigorous process that historians go through in the creation of that text. If we pay a close attention to the process of history writing, we will also start questioning the certainty of what they write. Human hands, with so many shortcomings and biases, record historical accounts of the past, and they are obviously not absolutely true.

Postmodernist historians conceive history as a literary text. The way literary writers produce literature, a historian may produce history book. Literary writers collect data from the society or from history books themselves and work on those materials. They also involve themselves into the process of selection and exclusion. There exist infinite possibilities. It is the writers who decide which path to pursue and which to dismiss. They set priorities. Yes, it is true that historians will try to stick to the data but literary writers may be free to use the material in their own way. Unlike a fiction writer a historian may worry more about the truthful representation of the past but not all historians do that, nor any historian can do that. The way literary writers play with the chronology of events, with the use of narrative techniques such as flashback, foreshadowing, a historian will also rely on them to some extent. One of

the major differences between a historian and a creative writer may be that the former has a finite pool of facts from which to choose whereas the latter has no scarcity of data. They can imagine data using their imaginative capability.

To conclude, in O Mink's words, historians can never totally dissociate themselves from narrative; "for it is as narrative, or as essentially connected with narrative, that historical knowledge is transmitted, if at all, from professional historians to the common culture" (91).

Chapter III

Modes of Historical Representation

History as Fact: Chronicles

History is supposed to be the continuous record of past events. What we understand, as “the present” is, in fact a construct of “the past”. The “Present” also doesn’t stand in a vacuum. Though the presence of past may not be felt all the time explicitly, it plays a significant role in the formation of the present, and of the future. Those who are ignorant of their own past are not much better than animals since both would live only in the present, without being aware of the formative influences of the past. This is why the study of past is very important for human beings.

Nineteenth century contributed a new model to historiography. It was called positivism. It believed in the supremacy of facts and observable phenomena. Positivism believes that human societies all around the world function according to certain laws. Nothing happens without a reason. Nothing is unexplainable in terms of scientific procedures. If we can understand these governing laws, we can even predict our futures.

J.B. Bury as a positivist historian demanded that historians should try to explain the governing laws using the scientific methods. He strongly believed that history is a “science, no more and no less” (6). According to him, first, we need to understand the governing laws that run our societies. But in order to establish these laws, one must follow scientific procedures, very rigorously.

J. B Bury had a strong faith in scientific methodology and for this faith; he had a belief that past can be brought to the present objectively. The Historian’s task was to present the past as it had actually happened. Another historian Leopold von

Ranke (1795-1886) even laments for the fact that past historians before his time neglected or did not understand the real purpose of historical writings. Instead of representing the past as it was, they often imposed their own value judgments and interpretations. Bolted writes:

Ranke cautioned historians against allowing their own judgments in creating the past lest the degree of objectivity in their work would be compromised. He stressed that only when a historian removed all traces of his personal feelings and opinions could he ever produce an objective historical work. (12)

In Ranke's opinion, judgment or evaluation is not the task of a historian. Nor should historians try to recreate the past; rather they should just represent it. Ranke was not the first historian to demand for objectivity in historical writings. Even Herodotus wanted to achieve such objectivity in his writings very much. For this reason, he extensively traveled to almost all of the countries that were involved in the Persian War. He listened to the witnesses very critically, and then only wrote their information in his book.

Even Thucydides aspired to write history as objectively as possible. In his book titled *Peloponnesian War*, he wanted to document the social reality of that period as objectively as possible. He wrote the history of the contemporary times because he wanted to write the objective truths only. Brown indicates:

Thucydides chose to write the history of contemporary incidents because he felt historians can vouch for objectivity only for contemporary occurrences.

He took pain to seek not only as much facts as possible but also to ensure that the facts were true. (834)

Thucydides is known as the father of scientific historiography because of his passion for objective reality. He attempted to discard gods and other supernatural elements from his history books.

Another historian, Auguste Comte (1798- 1857), also known as father of sociology, contributed a lot to the development of the idea that history is a collection of facts only, nothing else. He is also considered as a leader of the positivist approach. Comte opines that history should be treated as an aspect of human knowledge. He opines that history has passed through various stages. The first stage was theocratic stage when it was believed that the gods controlled everything. Metaphysical phase, the second phase, was an era when mankind searched for a logical explanation for human life and natural phenomena. At this stage, human beings could not satisfy themselves with the explanation that gods control everything. In the third stage, a new approach to history was developed which we know as positivism (Brown 830-833). Positivists use two methods –First, historians should attempt to find out the governing laws of nature using scientific procedure. Second, historians must be committed to using the direct sources as far as possible to capture the past as it really took place.

John Stuart Mill (1806-1873) was another positivist thinker who attempted to establish history as science. In his famous book entitled *A system of Logic* (1843), the British philosopher claimed that the task of philosophy was to discover the laws which governed history. In order to discover these laws, a historian needs to study human nature.

Scientific method improved the knowledge of humankind in different aspects and gained immense popularity in the nineteenth century. English philosopher R.G. Collingwood (1889-1943) propounded the idealist school, which was considered a

branch of positivism. He viewed history from sociological perspective. Unlike the natural scientists, Collingwood believes, historians seek to study and understand historical events and their underlying causes.

The core idea of positivism was that the scientific method of recognizing only positive facts and observable phenomena to be applied to the study of nature and society. This school of philosophy suggested that any society in the world functioned according to certain laws, which could be examined to predict its future. In other words, to obtain a scientific basis for historical conclusions, one should employ only natural science procedures. By the end of the nineteenth century the scientific approach to history had become widely accepted. In addition, the positive contributions of science during that century had improved the knowledge of humankind.

History as Story: Narratives

Historians like Carl Becker, Charles Beard, around 1920s, started a different historical movement in America. They are also known as “the relativists.” They questioned the ability of historians to recreate the past objectively. In this regard, Anbalakan writes, “According to Becker, historian chooses what he prefers based on his experience and knowledge and the need of his time and presents that as history” (3). These relativists turned the direction of the discussion and led it to a different destination.

The word “History” refers to an academic discipline where the prime focus is on the events of the past. It also refers to a branch of knowledge what we call “narrative”. The relativists’ arguments paved a way for the development of this narrative school of history. There are various theories, principles, and methods that

historians follow in order to recapture the past events and present them to the readers as “narratives.”

One prominent school of historiography defines history as a narrative. It takes history not just as a collection and presentation of raw facts, but also as a sequencing of events in a certain space and time order, along with the establishment of causes and effects. Up to the modern age, history was, to a great extent, understood as a collection of mere data. But with the rise of postmodern philosophy, the concept of history also has changed a lot. Post modernists often describe history as a narrative, just like literature. History also tells us stories that we believe are true. Historians also use their imagination and rationality to explain events and establish cause and effect.

These postmodern thinkers who define history as a narrative often raise the question of representation and its authenticity. They point out at the problems that historians inevitably face in their attempts at recreating the past. According to post-modernist historians or historiographers, reality does not exist outside the system of representation. History is a mode of representation, just like literature. History and literature may have their different priorities, but both of them are narratives. Even in historical narratives, the question of true representation emerges out and troubles many readers as well as historians.

Representation has its own complexities. Narratives allow readers to perceive the events they represent in a certain way. We are given with an illusion that the order of narratives presented to us of the past events is real. But the truth is that they are the creation of the writers/historians. Postmodern philosophy of history is incredulous of such grand narratives. Any historical events that make a false claim of authenticity of representation are untrustworthy. How do we fragment time in human calendar? How

can we be sure that what we see, hear, experience are truths? These thinkers raise such complex issues and questions to deny any claim over authenticity and objectivity.

In order to highlight the falsities that historians often promise, postmodern historians/ writers use a special technique that is called self-reflexivity. Using this technique, they expose the doubts and uncertainties that cloud the writings of the historians/ narrators. Postmodern historians prefer mini-narratives to metanarratives for the reason that mini-narratives do not overgeneralize things. These mini-narratives have a better capacity to represent the fragmented realities of our lives than the grand narratives that tend to cover a large sweep of time, space, and people.

Traditional historians claimed that they would give facts objectively. Just like J. B. Bury and others, they developed various scientific methods and tools to maintain authenticity of their accounts. They presented history as something that moves in a linear order. But postmodern historians reject such claims as mere lies.

Roland Barthes, in his essay “The Discourse of History” writes, “historical discourse is in its essence a form of ideological elaboration” (qtd. in Jenkins 121). What Barthes means by this statement is obvious. He is trying to make a point that history works out the traces of past into a narrative form of representation. He affirms that ideology is nothing but an extension of the structure. His views have influenced postmodern view of history tremendously.

The historians who believe that history is a narrative often question the validity of the sources and documents that historians use in the process of recording and writing history. Which facts are to be used, which facts are to be discarded are in fact historians’ choices. They may have personal choices, and at times, unknown

reasons to manipulate facts. Their subjectivity affects their interpretation of the facts. The ideology of historian's era also speaks through the historians. They may have just become scripters of the social milieu they belong to.

This narrative interface of history brings historians very near to the fiction writers. Fictions tell stories and so do historical accounts. Many fictions explicitly deal with past events, just the way historical accounts dwell upon the past. The theories of narratives apply to the act of story writing as well as to the acts of history writing.

Historians neither can nor would be interested in including all of the raw data from the past in their writings. They also select some data and reject others. The relationship between events also must be established. In this sense, a historian writes history very much like a storywriter. History inevitably contains the elements of narratives/ story for it is also a kind of story. Michel de Certeau rightly points out, "the past is the fiction of the present" (10). Certeau talks about the possible fictionalization of past events in the act of recording and writing history. He uses the term "entombment" which reflects the interaction between past and present. In this sense, history represents certain events of the past in a certain representational mode.

Postmodern philosophers and critics such as Paul Ricoeur, Louis Mink, Michel de Certeau, Dominick La Capra, Arthur Marwick often foreground this narrative aspect of history. They problematize history by pointing to its inherent weaknesses. Due to the theorization of these postmodern critics, the term "new history" is being used these days in contrast to old historical methods. This "new history" is often the history from the margins. Subaltern groups, women, Blacks, and

so on often use this new approach. This is how postmodernists have redefined history as a narrative, a mixture of fact and fiction.

Historians need to survive on fragments of the past. Imagination becomes their main aide. Linda Hutcheon in *The Politics of Postmodernism* writes: “Historians are readers of fragmentary documents and, like readers of fiction, they fill in the gaps and create ordering structures which may be further disrupted by new textual inconsistencies that will force the formation of new totalizing patterns” (87). Hutcheon’s view about historians describes the writers of fiction as well. Both rely on imaginative or the creative faculties of the mind in order to prepare plausible narratives.

Viewing history as a narrative, postmodern historians attempt to create their own alternative version of the past. They often contradict mainstream historical narratives. This act of defying the established histories has brought postmodern historians into controversy. In an attempt to create an alternative version or versions of the past, postmodern historians often incorporate in their historical narratives, anachronism, fantasy, gossip. Such elements also become a part of postmodern historiography. These historians weave beautiful stories of the past events that at times explicitly, and at times, symbolically represent the bygone era and events.

Broadly speaking, there are two types of narrative history. The first one is the traditional school that takes history as a narrative but in a limited sense. The modern school that takes history as a narrative takes the idea a bit further. It incorporates the postmodern views of history. This modern school of narrative breaks away from rigid chronology. It encourages historians to form the narrative more freely.

One of the fundamental differences between these two schools of narrative is that the first one focuses on “what” whereas the second school focuses more on “how” and “why.” These interpretations are also very much important in historical narrative for historians also may lie or manipulate events. Linda Hutcheon in this regard writes, “All past events are potential historical facts but the ones that become facts are those that are chosen to be narrated” (73). Hutcheon’s arguments make readers aware of the common pitfalls of historical accounts. This is why some New Historicists claim that we sometimes understand history much better from fictions than from history books.

Facts alone are meaningless. For example, one encounters some roses in the battleground. What does it signify? It may be meaningless unless we connect it to a context, to a larger picture. Historians interpret the facts and produce meanings. In this regard, Hutcheon writes: “Given the narrative has become problematic in historiography as well as fiction, what is interesting is that the same issues arise: narrative representation as a mode of knowledge and explanation, as unavoidably ideological, as a localizable code” (54). Hutcheon views narrative as a mode of representation. Similarly, she views ideology as a code or formula of representation. It applies to both fiction and history. In “The Canadian Postmodern: A Study of Contemporary English-Canadian Fiction, Hutcheon writes:

. . . to write history (or historical fiction) is (equally) to narrate, to represent by means of selection and interpretation. History (like realist fiction) is made by its writer, even if events are made to seem to speak for themselves . . . What historians call “narrativization,” – making experience into story – is a central mode of human comprehension. (66)

Thus, Hutcheon connects fiction and history to each other for both undergo the same process of making. The similarities between history and fiction have given birth to a new type of historical account that we call “historical fiction”.

Hayden White also views history as a story. He considers historical representation of reality as poetic in nature. He calls history poetic in the sense that history casts events in beautiful stories, using figure of speech, at times. History has a beginning, middle, and an end. It answers what happened, how it happened, and why it happened. Chronicles don't do that. But we rarely read chronicles. By history, we understand historical narratives. This is why he calls history a poetic mode of representation. It is a matter of historian's choice and interpretation. Thus, Hayden White connects history and story, giving history a new identity, a narrative mode of representation. In order to explicate how historian's choices affect their narratives, Hayden White writes:

The production of meaning in this case can be regarded as a performance, because any given set of real events can be “emplotted” in a number of ways, can bear the weight of being told as any number of different kinds of stories. Since no given set or sequence of events is intrinsically tragic, comic, farcical, and so on, but can be constructed as such only by the imposition of the structure of a given story type on the events, it is the choice of the story type on the events, it is the choice of the story type and its imposition upon the events that endow them with meaning. (44)

White suggests that facts in themselves are meaningless. How historians clad them into beautiful form decides the nature of the narrative. Historians can turn the same event into tragic or comic. Because of this reason, White asks us to read history as a

narrative. Viewed from this perspective, history appears as a type of novel. The Annalists' claim of objectivity appears a remote thing here. Narrative school of history thus asks us to reject, revise, or augment the older mimetic theories of historical discourse.

Marwick thinks in the same line. It becomes evident as he writes, "history is simply a branch of literature, in which the narratives of historians do not significantly differ from the novels of novelists" (12). Marwick believes that historians have some other objectives than the novelists, so these two genres have two different functions. This reveals us how they can be related and at the same time how they are two different modes of representation.

However, Hayden White has a different view about the nature of history and fiction. In this regard he writes: "there are many histories that could pass for novels, and many novels that could pass for histories, considered in purely formal terms. Viewed simply as verbal artifacts, histories and novels are indistinguishable from one another" (122). In Hayden White's understanding of history, all written documents may have simultaneously fictional and historical significance.

White sees the difference in the way they present their ideas and visions. Historians have different visions than fiction writers. In this essay titled "postmodernism and History," Willie Thompson opines that history contains narrative in the sense of "a coherent and ordered representation of events or developments in sequential time" (132). In any writings, be it historical or fictional, facts and fictions merge seamlessly. With the help of narratives, historians create patterns, form, and structure in history.

It is the historians who read the past and interpret them to the readers. They are not just readers, but also creators and artists. In the process of what happened and how did it happen, the historians exercise control over the readers. This is the act of storytelling that gives historians their distinguishing power.

History as Myth/Magic

Myths and history have one strong commonality. Both attempt to explain how things got to be the way they are now. Both genres attempt to reveal the knowledge of the past, through stories. Many myths are created with a purpose in mind. They are often created to fulfill our longings for identity.

Some of the historians like J. B. Bury, Auguste Comte, John Stuart Mill and others, especially those who believe strongly in scientific history, often degrade myths as a collection of lies and gossip. Using the methodology of science, they believe, we can revoke the past as it really was. These historians demand that we need to arrange the facts into a readable narrative only. They want to limit the contribution of narratives to the minimum. These historians firmly believe that readers read history for facts, not for stories. They have the faith over scientific historical knowledge. These historians are also known as the Annalists, the positivists etc.

Against this school of thought, the New Historicists posited the similarities between history and fiction. New Historicists believe that the process of writing history also involves subjective judgments and individual choices. For example, if historians want to go back to the prehistoric times, they mostly need to rely on myths and legends. They become the source for historian's information. This is why probably in India, even today, the Ramayana, the Mahabharata, and the Vedas are taken as religious as well as historical documents. Such old scriptures are known as

Itihasa or even chronicles. Such stories of gods and goddesses, demons and seductresses not just enliven the spirits of Indians but also provide people all over the world with some sense of history. Historian Romila Thapar is among such scholars who try to connect Indian Vedic scriptures with the mainstream history of Indian subcontinent. Though scientific historiography does not consider these legends as history books, they certainly do contain much information about life in the past.

The word “mythology” comes from Greek language. It means “the story of the people”. These myths tell us the stories of our ancestors. They acquaint us with the stories of human origin, the origin of our cultures, our religions, and so on. Myths have a religious outlook. They also serve historical functions. They are taken as the earliest forms of history. Legends are considered as the history of people and places, for example, the Ramayana tells us the story of the expansion of the Aryans in the subcontinent.

If we trace the history of historical writings, we need to go back to Herodotus, the father of history. He wrote the accounts of war between Europe and Asia. In order to write the events, he primarily relied on informers. But what is the guarantee that his informers gave him correct information? What is the guarantee that they didn't distort the past? Thus, history or myth, both may contain fact as well as fiction.

Traditional historians often claim that they can separate myth from truth. Later on, it is understood that separating myth and history is not so easy. It may even be impossible at times. This is why historical narratives may often contain myths, legends as integral constituents of history. This type of history is also known as the myth-history. Myths and history have a strong link. Both may contain elements of

each other. History uses myths to access what happened in the past. Myths use history to create an impression of authenticity.

Such mythical narratives contain many “uncanny” elements. Still many people easily accept it in the name of religion, or nationality. For example, in India, many people strongly believe in the texts such as the Ramayana and the Mahabharata. In the Western world also, a lot people, even the most educated of them, believe in the creation stories and stories of the Bible. Muslim world also has its own prehistoric elements that have been accepted as a part of history. This is how history comes us in the form of myths and legends.

Magic is another aspect of history. In all types of historical narratives, it may not come explicitly but in many we can see its strong presence. The above-discussed mythical elements in history are also a kind of magic. If religion is removed from the Ramayana, it will have a magic realist text left. Historians have a compulsion to hug myth as the real traits of human societies and psyche. In the process of uniting its people, the nation may create several myths. For example, America created various myths of George Washington in order to use him as a symbol of national integrity. America almost deified him, but the stories are largely myths and they are also samples of magic. These mythical stories are later on incorporated into the mainstream history as well. This is how myths and magic become a part of history.

Every storyteller understands the importance of creating someone as a hero. Once we create a hero and weave stories around him/her, we engage the listeners/readers. This is how heroes are created in history. At times such myths are created and propagated intentionally also. To conclude, myths are also an ingredient

of history. Historians consciously or unconsciously may use myths in their historical documents. So myth and magic is also a vehicle to represent historical reality.

Magical History as a Postcolonial Weapon

Postcolonial writers often use myths and magic in their writings also as a tool to fight against the imperialist historiography. These writers deliberately use magic in their historical narrative in order to resist colonial ideology. During the era of colonization, colonizers systematically tried to erase the histories of the colonies. They did so in order to establish the superiority of the white masters over the natives, and in this process the people of colonies almost lost their connection with their land and history. Once they became independent, they had to revive their lost culture, lost glory, and lost history. For this purpose, some of the postcolonial writers devised a smart technique to recover the lost past. They tried to recover the history, using fantasy and magic. Thus, we can say that magic realism was intended to designate a new form of realism. It is also taken as an “intuitive realism.” This mode of representation represents, in an intuitive way, the fact of the exterior world. It may distort the reality but this distortion may have an objective of achieving a greater clarity. Thus, magic realism represents reality, relying upon imagination and creativity.

James Irish claims that magic realism “must be evaluated in the context of the general attempt by nineteenth and twentieth century Latin American thinkers to discover, analyze, and define the truly characteristic features of Latin American reality” (127). In this sense, this mode of representation was the necessity of history. The social reality of these colonized nations was so bitter or pungent that these postcolonial writers had to use not just real but also magical mode at the same time.

In these colonized parts of the world, a different reality existed. For example, in India, it is said that most of the people are deeply spiritual and the superstitious values have almost dominated this continent. Their stories and history books, for example the Ramayana and the Mahabharata, are often filled with “impossible stories”. In this context, the magical mode of social representation becomes very appropriate. A Cuban novelist named Alejo Carpentier writes:

After sensing the unmistakable witchery of Haiti, and having found sign of magic along the red roads of the central Plateau, and after hearing the drums of the Petro, and the Rada, I found myself comparing this recently experienced, marvelous reality with the exhausting presumption of evoking the marvelous which characterized certain European literature of the last thirty years. (84)

Through this marvelous reality, Latin America expressed its unique characteristics. Carpentier seeks to seize the mystery that surrounds Latin America and calls it a new model of history. Homi K. Bhabha writes, “magic realism after the Latin American boom, becomes the literary language of the emergent post-colonial world” (7). Using “indigenous magic,” Rushdie gives a voice to the Indian subcontinent. He vocalizes the stories of the oppressed.

History as Gossip and Lies

Gossip is something that societies often condemn. But it is true that people are surrounded by gossip, and yet at the same time they are very snobbish about it. All wittings, be it a fiction or a history, use gossip. Some may use it a lot while some may try to keep it to a minimum. Gossips are often portrayed as something womanish and

silly. This patriarchal assumption about gossip is very problematic because it is not only women who indulge themselves into gossips but men also gossip a lot.

Novelists often use gossip as a framing device. In epistolary novels, through characters gossip, readers come to know about the happenings in the story. These novels are often full of gossips. Once a novelist uses conversations as a basis of the development of the story, most probably gossips automatically enter into the narrative. While using witnesses or informants, historians also knowingly or unknowingly use gossips in historical narratives.

When gossips enter into historical accounts, they may spice up the story. Gossip may be true or false. They may assert or distort the reality. Sometimes historians may deliberately use them to manipulate readers. It is not true that historians are all selfless. Such faith on historians will be very naive. So, through such manipulations, historians may be promoting a specific ideology or their particular agendas.

Those who are in power often use this tool to distort history or the reality. Distorting reality may help rulers to subjugate people. Such distortions may be used to glorify an individual, a race, or a nation. It may be also used to vilify “others”. Even nations use this trick. Governments may ask historians to do such things. For example, James Mill wrote a book titled *A History of British India* where he tries to show how British government tried to civilize a primitive nation like India. Colonizers not just tried to distort the history of the colonized nations but also attempted to erase many of them. Sometimes nations use such lies and gossips in history books in order to promote nationalism, at times even jingoism. Hitler was also doing such things in Germany in order to use people for his personal gains.

In America, even up to the 19th century, history textbooks of school and colleges incorporated blatant lies. They claimed that the whites had made most of the great achievements in human history. They were distorting history in order to bolster their image as a great nation.

There are various ways that history books may lie to the readers. Some of the examples are –cultural imperialism, ultra-nationalism, xenophobia, semantic manipulations, and so on. Due to these complexities that surround historical narratives, scholars and critics like E.H Carr and others even assert that history is not just what really happened in the past, but a tricky area of study. History is in fact a complex intersection of fact, imagination, myth, and lies.

In order to write history, historians need to remember the past. For that, they rely on their own memory and the memory of the eyewitnesses. But our memories are fallible. In order to explain the facts, historians interpret them using their own subjectivity. At times historians may write purported histories as well in order to achieve their own vested goals. As a reader, one must be very careful of such possibilities. If we naively believe history to be a collection of facts, we may be easily misled or manipulated. But even the most extravagant gossip may have some grains of truth in it that may lie hidden beneath a mountain of lies.

In this sense, history appears as a messy business. It is for very smart readers only. Even the same event narrated by various journalists differs significantly. This is why it is said that history is susceptible to bias, self-righteousness, pride, vanity, and so on. When we study the record of the past events, we must be able to examine the propaganda of various sorts. We should be aware of the possible lies and

manipulations, though we won't always be able to detect them. We should probably read history books very much like fiction.

Since all history is, in a way or other, remembered history, memory intervenes all historical narratives. Most of our ancient history comes to us in an oral form. These informers of the past give us a picture of what they saw, experienced, or felt. But what is the guarantee that what they saw, felt or lived was the truth? What is the guarantee that they were not lying or manipulating? As far as memory is concerned, human beings have selective memory. We tend to remember only what we like. This sort of memory's role in the act of history writing secures the possibility of gossip and lies in historical narratives.

When historians find out a cultural, or a historical artifact of the past, they must connect it to the larger picture. They must interpret the significance of what they find out. This is where historians may insert lies into their narratives. Sometimes some of the historians even invent history. It may be the demand of the era or the demand of human weaknesses. Myths are the examples of such histories. There are not just old myths in our societies. We also do have modern myths. Many postcolonial writers have created modern myths. Such historical accounts subtly foreground the idea of history as gossip and lies. To conclude with Kathleen A. Feeley and Jennifer Frost:

Gossip is usually viewed as suspect historical evidence because it cannot be verified as true or false. Yet, historical information and knowledge can be teased out from gossip, and for some groups and topics gossip may be the best or only available source of evidence. So, gossip and history are integrally related. Whether we understand gossip as "counter history" or history as an

“elevated form” of gossip, they both offer narratives and interpretations of the past. (Why Historians Can't Afford to Ignore Gossip 87)

Thus, history may manifest itself, at times, as lies and gossip. Salman Rushdie, in most of his novels, deliberately highlights all these aspects of history and fiction in order to make readers aware of how history and fictions have to be dealt with.

Syncretic Approach to History

History is not only facts. If we take history just as stories, we will be wrong. Taking history as myths or magic only would also be insufficient. If we go to the extent of taking history as just a collection of lies and gossip, again we will be misled. Some scholars, such as Marxists, go the extent of saying that history is a horse of the winner, only the winners! In fact history is a bit of all ingredients mentioned above.

History manifests itself primarily in four different forms, and they are –history as facts, history as narratives, history as myth/magic, and history as gossip/ lies. In any historical documents, we may find little bit of all these four components. If we agree to view history in this syncretic way, our understanding of history would be holistic. Otherwise we would define history only in its fragments, not in its totality. Rushdie forwards this comprehensive notion of history, through most of his fictions and non-fictions. He does it deliberately because he, as a novelist and a student of history, wants his readers to understand what history and fiction really are.

All historical documents are not alike. Just as there are various kinds of novels, there are various kinds of histories. Positivists may use fact as a dominant mode of representation, where as historians like Louis Mink and others may use narrative as their primary mode. Historians like Franz Roh may prefer myths and magic as the primary mode of the representation of reality, where as some may

choose lies and gossip as the mode of representation of reality. Benjamin Franklin, Thomas Paine, and Goebbels are often tagged as propagandist historians. These are the variations in the spectrum of history and Rushdie also subscribes to this philosophy of history.

Chapter IV

Representation of History in *Midnight's Children*

A Very Brief Documented History of India's Independence

In 1757 the British Army fought and won the Battle of Plassey, and the British East India Company was established. This victory formally inaugurated the British rule over India. Later on, India supported British regime wholeheartedly during the First World War. This act of loyalty won India some liberty, a certain degree of self-governance. However, in 1919, the Rowlett Act provided the British government with extraordinary powers to suppress Gandhi's Satyagraha. This act silenced the press, curbed political activists without trial, and arrested any individuals suspected of treason against the British Empire without a warrant.

British rulers' suppression triggered a widespread discontent and fury among the Indians. On April 13, 1919 about 10,000 people assembled to celebrate Baisakhi, a Sikh festival at Jallianwala Bagh, Amritsar. The British soldiers killed about 1200 civilians, opening fire to the crowd. This act of atrocity really defamed British government in India, and fueled rebellion.

The Indian National Congress took initiative to fight against the cruel foreign rule in India. Gandhi led the non-violent movement and the Civil Disobedience slowly gained momentum. Leaders such as Mahatma Gandhi, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel, Jawaharlal Nehru gave the movement a direction. After successfully fighting against the whites in South Africa for Indian indentured servants, Gandhi returned back to India in 1915 with a determination to fight against the British rule in India. He traveled around India, collected information, and made plans to fight against

British injustice. Initially Gandhi was saying that he was not fighting against British rule, but just against the injustices. But later, the movement swept the entire British regime when Gandhi appealed to the Indian people to boycott the courts, British products, taxes, and so on.

The Indian National Congress gathered in Lahore in 1929 and passed a new resolution that India needed complete Independence from the British rule. Jawaharlal Nehru's voice got endorsed in this resolution and it was planned that on January 26, 1930 India would get Independence. But British rulers got this information somehow and arrested approximately 100,000 Indians to suppress the agitation. The British government called the National Congress leaders for a round table conference in 1931. The negotiation failed and Gandhi continued his civil disobedience movement.

During the same period, Hindu and Muslim leaders got involved in some sort of conflict. The Muslim League questioned the Congress for its claim to represent the whole of India. The Muslim League passed a resolution in Lahore to divide India into Hindu and Muslim states. Gandhi, on August 8, 1942, issued an order for the Britishers to leave India. Gandhi was arrested but it sparked a nationwide protest. British government arrested over 100,000 people and imposed curfew on the streets. Gandhi started fasting as a protest against the British rule in India. On August 15, 1947, India finally got Independence and a new independent nation was born. Along with India, a new nation Pakistan was also formed in 1947. On January 26, 1950, the Republic of India was declared, the first president of India was elected, and India thus officially severed ties with Britain.

India got Independence but Hindu-Muslim conflict soared high in the streets. Pakistan and India became separate nations. Gandhi was assassinated on 30, 1948 by

a Hindu fanatic. Then India went into an election where Jawaharlal Nehru led the Congress Party got victory. India also had to go a losing war with China during 1962-63. Indira Gandhi came in power and was elected Prime Minister of India in 1966. Her rule disappointed many Indians, especially the minority. In the 1967 election, the Congress Party shrunk a little bit. India was beset by innumerable problems. The Indian National Congress Party was split in 1969 but Indira Gandhi still continued to govern with a slim majority. India got involved in a Pakistani civil war in 1971. This gave birth to an independent Bangladesh.

Indira Gandhi was becoming less and less popular but at the same time she was being more and more power hungry. In 1974, the High Court declared her guilty of abusing government funds for election purpose. People asked for her resignation but she instead declared an emergency in 1975. The government suspended many civil liberties with an explanation that a serious national security threat has hit the nation. Indira Gandhi took into custody the leaders of the opposition. Her son Sanjay Gandhi in 1975 even ran a program of castrating the poor Indians forcefully in order to control population. It was named as sterilization drive. Her government destroyed many slums in Delhi, killing thousands of innocent Indians. In 1977 election Indira Gandhi and her party was defeated badly and her active political era was over.

Documented History of India in *Midnight's Children*

Rushdie begins his novel with a prologue where the protagonist Saleem Sinai speaks out his intention that he wants to start his narrative with an accurate fixing of time and place. He wants to sound like a historian, not a storyteller. He says:

I was born in the city of Bombay . . . once upon a time. No, that won't do, there's no getting away from the date: I was born in Doctor Narlikar's

Nursing Home on August 15th, 1947. And the time? The time matters, too. Well then, at night. No, it's important to be more . . . On the stroke of midnight, as a matter of fact. (9)

Almost like a speaker of a dramatic monologue, Saleem tells us how he wants to narrate his story and how he wants to sound like. He does not want to sound like storytellers who often start their stories with the phrases like once upon a time, in a remote village, and so on. It seems that he hates made up stories. He calls himself a historian. He is a fact teller, as he thinks of himself. He sounds like a positivist historian.

Midnight's Children is Saleem's autobiography, so what he tells us are supposed to be the true events. Saleem's life events unfold in such a way that it resembles the Indian oral way of story telling. Saleem makes predictions and prophecies, as well as tells us about his dreams and memories. He does not let the story flow on. He himself interrupts the story.

Saleem, a narcissistic narrator, speaks to Padma, his loyal listener. The historian sometimes starts to talk about himself, his mental and physical state, disorienting us from the true stories. He expresses his doubts frankly so that readers might not easily believe in his life events. It seems that Rushdie's interest in the story of *The Arabian Nights* has influenced the story of *Midnight's Children*. In *The Arabian Nights*, Scheherazade has to tell stories in order not to get executed. Saleem is telling his stories so that he will survive! He hopes that he will be immortal with the history book that he longs to record.

Saleem weaves stories within stories, for he wants his readers to go on reading and reading, as if hypnotized. Rushdie is trying to set up a tension in the text by

creating a paradoxical conflict between the form and the content of the story.

Saleem's life makes him miserable, but the narrative is told in a way that readers are captivated into the fabric of his stories. Saleem's personal tragedy is pitted against the tragedy of the nation. Personal here becomes the national and vice versa! At last Saleem's body breaks down into six hundred million pieces to resurrect six hundred million inhabitants of India. Then there exists the possibility of at least six hundred million stories!

Many critics have said that the novel contains multitudes. It can be interpreted from multiple perspectives. Some say it is a novel; some even say it is a history. Some have even said that it is like the Mahabharata, the grandest history of the Indian subcontinent. Since it is allegorical, it can be read in different ways. In this regard, Peterson posits:

The allegory is most evident in the description of the main character. Saleem is a changeling, which underlines his and India's multicultural heritage. Religions, races, and social classes are mingled in his identity. He says himself that he has the ability to give birth to new parents. His biological father is the Englishman Methwold. The British heritage is therefore central. It is in his genes and therefore a part of India forever. (qtd. in Karlsson 2)

Peterson thus sees that hybridity at the core of this text. Rushdie has used a technique in the novel to connect two diverse things together, that is, the development of India and the development of Saleem are paralleled. This parallelism beautifully connects Saleem's personal story with the national history. What appears to be just a story is at the same time the history of the nation too.

Saleem is writing the story to create meaning in his life. At the age of thirty-one, he is trying to preserve his life stories just the way he, in a pickle factory, preserves pickles. Michael Gorra writes, “Saleem sees himself as suffering from a peculiarly Indian disease . . . an urge to encapsulate the whole of reality” (38). This disease drives him to attempt an impossible task. How can an individual historian represent the whole truth? How can an individual historian know everything of the past? Saleem’s positivist attitude to history will ultimately deceive his readers and himself, since he is trying a herculean task, an almost impossible task.

Saleem loses his body part one after another, just the way India loses a part of her that we call now Pakistan, and another part that is called Bangladesh. Since Saleem is a son of an Englishman and an Indian woman, his self is divided. He is handcuffed to history so his story symbolizes the story of his own nation. As the prime minister of India Jawaharlal Nehru writes to him, he is the “the newest bearer of that ancient face of India” (122).

Saleem’s disintegrated body symbolizes national fate as a whole due to the fact that India had also begun to crumble. In the map it may look like a solid undivided nation but deep down there are gaps and fissures. Moreover, in school, Saleem’s teacher mocks at his facial geography, comparing that with the geography of India. Even Saleem’s face resembles India. The teacher says, “These stains, he cries, are Pakistan! This birthmark on the right ear is the East Wing; and this horrible stained left cheek, the West! Remember, stupid boys: Pakistan is a stain on the face of India” (231-32)! So Saleem’s history is very much the real history of India.

Once, at school, Saleem meets a small accident by the door and cuts off his middle finger. He is rushed to the hospital where doctors are surprised to know that

his blood group does not match with either his parents. Saleem himself is greatly puzzled and he says:

Because a human being, inside himself, is anything but a whole, anything but homogeneous; all kinds of every hitching are jumbled up inside him, and he is one person one minute and another the next. The body, on the other hand, is homogeneous as anything. Indivisible, a one-piece suit, a sacred temple, if you will! It is important to preserve this wholeness. But the loss of my finger (which was conceivably foretold by the pointing digit of Raleigh's fisherman), not to mention the removal of certain hairs from my head, has undone all that.
(236-37)

Saleem's identity is multifaceted. It has been splintered into many layers. He was born of a Hindu woman and an English father. The father he grew up with was not his true father. Who is he: history or fiction? He was living history or a fiction? A Christian babysitter nursed him. He had come to wrong parents. A son of a poor man came to a rich man's family, a doctor's house as their son! This is the complexity that truth is made of. So-called factual history also falls into such quagmires. Saleem, a symbol of positivist history, contains this multitude and hybridity.

Historians attempt to understand past as truly as possible. Saleem is also obsessed with that. But they ultimately fail somehow. That is why Greenblatt in his *Renaissance Self-Fashioning* writes:

In all my texts and documents, there were, so far as I could tell, no moments of pure, unfettered subjectivity; indeed, the human subject itself began to seem remarkably unfree, the ideological product of the relations of power in a particular society. Whenever I focused sharply upon a moment of apparently

autonomous self-fashioning, I found not an epiphany of identity freely chosen but a cultural artifact. If there remained traces of free choice, the choice was among possibilities whose range was strictly delineated by the social and ideological system in force (1980: 256).

In *Midnight's Children*, Saleem explains this with an example. He says when we go to a movie and if we watch the film from the back of the room, we may have a full view over what happens on the screen. But if we start coming closer and closer to the screen, images also grow. If we come too close to the screen, we may feel dizzy. Things become unclear and very vast. Even the dots may appear like mountains. Exactly the same thing may happen with historians. If they get very close to the incidents, they may find them increasingly complex. You need to stand at a certain distance to see things clearly but this distance also affects our knowledge of the past. Thus Rushdie, though he seeks facts and figures, maintains a distance and narrates them in a unique manner.

This autobiographical mode of telling the history of the nation connects Saleem's body to the geography of the nation. The violent birth of Independent India parallels Saleem's violent birth. Saleem's biological mother dies after giving him birth. Saleem writes:

I shall not describe the mass blood-letting in progress in the frontiers of the divided Punjab (where the partitioned nations are washing themselves in one another's blood, and a certain Punchinello-faced Major Zulfikar is buying refugee property at absurdly low prices, laying the foundations of a fortune that will rival the Nizam of Hyderabad's) . . . (112)

At school, when his teacher pulls his hair, India loses its territory. Riots sweep East Pakistan. Even Kashmir demands for independence. These incidences have no apparent connections but who knows? Like the butterfly effect who knows how far they may affect! When there is a clash among the members of the Midnight's Conference, the nation goes into war with China! India's defeat with China takes away Saleem's special gift of smelling and hearing voices. His telepathic powers disappear. Saleem loses many of his family members in the war and he also loses memory as a silver spittoon hits him. He loses his memory as well as hopes and at the same time the nation loses hopes too. In such instances of interconnections, it is very likely that the novel *Midnight's Children* does not reflect the official history of India.

India's role in the formation of independent Bangladesh is not an enigma. Many history books have clearly outlined it. Rushdie also very cleverly alludes to the same in *Midnight's Children*. Saleem goes to the war with some of his friends. There he sees with his own eyes many atrocities committed upon East Pakistani people and soldiers with his own eyes. But as he later on checked government records, he found a lot of distortions there. Here Rushdie is trying to prove himself a fact finder, contradicting the official records. His love for evidences seems obvious here. Saleem describes the Pakistani soldiers' behavior in Dhaka as something that is not true because it conflicts with the image of the Pakistani soldier:

Shaheed and I saw many things that were not true, which were not possible, because our boys would not could not have behaved so badly; we saw men in spectacles with heads like eggs being shot in side-streets, we saw the intelligentsia of the city being massacred by the hundred, but it was not true because it could not have been true. (375)

Here the official historiography of the country is questioned with another version but according to Rushdie, it is not also false. It is the history from below and it may be truer. In the very beginning of the novel, Saleem's grandfather, Aadam Aziz, a west educated intellectual, meets his future wife, Naseem. Aadam sees her when he was asked to give her some medical treatment. In the course of the treatment, he falls in love with her. He is allowed to see her body only in fragments. He comes to know the whole truth i.e., her whole body, only after a long time. When Aziz asks for permission to examine her closely for the treatment, her father Mr. Ghani says, "You Europe-returned chappies forget certain things. Doctor Sahib, my daughter is a decent girl, it goes without saying. She does not flaunt her body under the noses of strange men" (23). It shows the differences between two different kinds of upbringings. When historians write history, these differences, of course, penetrate their writing. Just because of this, we cannot call those colorings unfair or untrue.

Naseem stands for eastern values. She falls in love with the doctor and marries him. But when the doctor asks her to move a little during an act of love making, she gets very angry. She interprets it as something unfair, which makes her feel like a prostitute. Such frequent changes in position, looks like western perversion to Naseem. Thus, she represents the traditional Eastern values. If she writes a history book, her approach to facts may be different and interpretations of the same facts may be different too. This is the nature of history which Rushdie, in *Midnight's Children*, foregrounds. In this regard Goonetilleke writes,

She is a typical Indian (female) figure in this respect – dishing out or not dishing out food, fasting as a protest (like Gandhi). Aadam tries to change her character. He asks her to move during the sex act and come out of purdah. He

fails in regard to the first but, though he succeeds in regard to the second,
Naseem resents it and the concession is on the surface . . . (62-63)

The way India is torn between Hindu and Muslim values, these midnight's children are also torn between personal and public spheres. What is personal to them becomes automatically public as well. These one thousand and one children born during the hour of Independence have been gifted with special talents and these talents control their fate. Rushdie in *Midnight's Children* writes, "history, arriving at a point of the highest significance and promise, had chosen to sow, in that instant, the seeds of a future which would genuinely differ from anything the world had seen up to that time" (195). It was in fact a great moment in Indian history and in Saleem's view it had the power to alter the future.

The transition stage of India from a colonized nation to an Independent one was costly too. India lost many of its citizens, lost some of its territory, and also lost some of its fundamental values and beliefs. It is very well symbolized by an incident that takes place in the novel itself. About four hundred and twenty midnight's children died. Those who survived were from various class and creed and they represent the whole of India. Midnight childrens' conference is not just a routine conference; it is in fact Indian Lok Sabha itself in disguise, a total of five hundred and eighty-one members.

Rushdie presents Indira Gandhi as a villain as she imposes curfew over the nation and also tries to crush the midnight's children. She declares the Emergency of 1975-77. She is not ready to give power and authority to the federal states under India. She wants to enjoy absolute power. She promotes a slogan –Indira is India and India is Indira. Rushdie writes:

For Mother India cannot endure the threat embodied in the pluralism of the MCC. History books may argue that Mrs. Gandhi declared the Emergency of 1975-77 because the economy had gone bad, because she feared a conspiracy against her, because she'd been caught in a bit of election fraud . . . her declaration of that "continuous midnight which would not end for two long years" had but one purpose: "the destruction of the midnight's children" . . . (404-406)

Midnight's children were the true representatives of India but Indira Gandhi didn't like them. Because they were heterogeneous, and there was an intense disagreement among midnight's children as well. They quarreled and fought. Their conference turned into chaos. The hope they were supposed to project crumbled. Different groups and sub groups were formed and India became a nation of diversity, even more than before. This incident does not just tell us a fictional story but it signifies something larger. It refers to India's documented history as well.

In short, Rushdie uses facts and figures from Indian history to write this novel. It comes in a beautiful form, an art form, but it is a history of India. There may be another version of the same event but this version is also not false. It has been written from the perspective of the common people but it is not less accurate than the history that the nation records. Rushdie verbalizes, through his novel, that India is a country of multiplicity. It has pluralism and hybridity at its core. The novel suggests India is at once tremendously plentiful, heterogeneous and united. So, India should not be understood as one whole, but a country with multiple faces and its history also will come in many forms.

Our historian here is Saleem and he has made some errors in his book. But the truth is that his errors are his limitations. Every historian will have to grapple with such things while writing history. They use archives that may contain errors. They use eyewitnesses who may mislead them. They use their own memory that is also fallible. Historians interpret the data they collect according to their capacity and intelligence. So, history, despite being fact seeking, is full of holes. Positivist historiography attempts to minimize such distortions but they cannot do away with such errors. The question is how many errors or distortions historians make, not whether there are errors and distortions in history.

History as Narrative in *Midnight's Children*

Midnight's Children, a defining book for post-colonial literature, is a novel about history, nation, and politics. By bringing different aspects of fairy tale, autobiography and history together, it boldly questions the traditional methods of historiography. This new method of history writing is also known as an alternative history. This alternative history that Rushdie depicts in *Midnight's Children* deploys the techniques of postmodern historiography. The novel captures the history of the Indian subcontinent between 1915 and 1977. It is replete with Indian historical facts. It is of course a novel that highlights different aspects of historiography.

Midnight's Children tells the story of ordinary people and reveals the ordinary and sometimes extraordinary experiences of common people. Rushdie does not use the traditional mode of representation in order to tell these multiple stories about the postcolonial realities. In Saleem Sinai's narration, we find many manipulations. The fusion of fact and fantasy becomes apparent in the very beginning of the novel when the narrator says:

Clock-hands joined palms in respectful greeting as I came. Oh, spell it out, spell it out: at the precise instant of India's arrival at independence, I tumbled forth into the world . . . because thanks to the occult tyrannies of those blandly saluting clocks I had been mysteriously handcuffed to history, my destinies indissolubly chained to those of my country. (3)

The narrator tries to show a link between his birth and the birth of modern India. He thinks that he is very special and has extraordinary power. Readers become aware about his exaggeration in the very beginning of the novel. It suggests that the novel does not follow the ordinary convention of traditional historiography.

Saleem Sinai is the self-proclaimed historian who, in the novel, tries to write the history of his family as well as the history of India after Independence. He does not tell the history like a traditional historian. Other characters in the novel also question traditional historiographical conventions. They also retell history, exaggerate history and eliminate many facts and figures present in official documents. Several aspects of Indian history including its false consciousness of nationalism, events from the Amritsar massacre to the period of Emergency are closely examined and connected to the Sinai family. Certainly, the novel challenges traditional notion of objectivity since the narrator of the novel attempts to tell the history of his nation on the basis of his own memory. Saleem Sinai explains the relationship between history writing and memory like this:

I told you the truth; I say yet again, Memory's truth because memory has its own special kind. It selects, eliminates, alters, exaggerates, minimizes, glorifies, and vilifies also; but in the end it creates its own reality, it's

heterogeneous but usually coherent version of events; and no sane human being ever trusts someone else's version more than his own. (292)

Thus, Rushdie links history writing and memory. Traditional historians proclaim that history writing is always objective and there is no role of memory in such writings. But Rushdie radically differs from such historians and their notion of history. In Rushdian notion, history lacks chronological order. History is fragmentary. It fuses legends and chronicles. Thus, Rushdie forwards a new notion of history by refuting traditional historiography. This new notion of history helps us see the flaws in officially sanctioned historical documents.

Saleem Sinai has a strong and peculiar sense of history. He is determined to challenge the so-called objectivity of traditional historians because he doesn't believe in absolute facts, nor does he believe in absolute fiction. In this regard, Saleem says, "Reality is a question of perspective; the further you get from the past, the more concrete and plausible it seems but as you approach the present, it inevitably seems more and more incredible" (229). In this sense, every historical record is a matter of historian's perspective. Truth depends upon our ways of viewing things. It is because all history writings are human products they undoubtedly suffer human limitations and inefficiency. That is why Rushdie in *Midnight's Children* claims that there can be as many versions of India as there are Indians.

Midnight's Children questions the hard facts of the traditional historian. In order to question such facts, Rushdie inter-connects the Sinai family and India in a fictionalized way. Saleem Sinai makes it obvious when he says, ". . . my very presence is having an effect on history; already baby Saleem is working changes on the people around him: and, in the case of my father, I am convinced that I was who

pushed him into the excess which led, perhaps inevitably, to the terrifying time of the freeze”(178-179). It becomes apparent that national and personal events may have resemblances. They are not contradictory; rather at many times they may go parallel. History and people are connected and they affect each other. This view is forwarded in *Midnight's Children*, especially through the fantastic coincidence between the Sinai family and the national history of India.

Saleem Sinai opens the novel by explaining the exact date and time of his birth i.e., August 15, 1947, at midnight. Saleem's birth coincides precisely with the moment India officially gains its independence from Britain. Thus, as Saleem notes, his miraculously timed birth ties him to the fate of the country. He is thirty-one years old now and feels that time is running out for him. Saleem believes his life is ending and he must tell all of the stories trapped inside of him before he dies. Saleem, as a historian, tells us what happened just before and after the Independence in various places of India like Srinagar, Amritsar, Agra, Bombay and Karachi.

Saleem Sinai, the member of the third generation, works at a pickle factory by day and records his experience by night. The novel's structure founded upon the history of the subcontinent is revealed before the reader as Saleem tells it to Padma. The first part of the narrative is set before the Indian independence in 1947. It begins in the valley of Kashmir with the first man, Aadam Aziz and his wife. The second part of the narrative deals with independent India and this comes to an end with the war between India and Pakistan. And, the third part describes the events leading to the formation of Bangladesh and various political situations in India. Indian history is there in the novel but what is more interesting is the way Rushdie mixes up the

various personal and national events. Because Saleem's birth coincides with the birth of decolonized India, Jawaharlal Nehru personally writes a letter to the baby Saleem:

Dear Baby Saleem, my belated congratulations on the happy accident of your moment of birth! You are the newest bearer of that ancient face of India, which is also externally young. We shall be watching over your life with the closest attention; it will be, in a sense, the mirror of our own! (167)

Saleem's mother gives birth to Saleem in doctor Narlikar's nursing home on August 15, 1947. Half an hour before her, a poor street singer's wife gives birth to another child. It is at this moment Jinnah proclaims the birth of Pakistan. After some time, the nurse, Mary Pereira, swaps Amina's son for the street singer's. The reason is that she is in love with a political revolutionary and thinks that she is doing a benevolent act by transforming a poor boy into a rich one.

Thus, the actual Sinai boy grows as Shiva, and the poor boy as Saleem Sinai. The swapping of children sounds real but there are other aspects of the story that cannot be accepted as real because they contain magical elements. The presence of fantastic elements in the novel problematizes our sense of the real and unreal. The basic historical data the novel talks about is the history of India, especially after independence. The swapping of children by Marie symbolizes the possible changes in the established official historical documents. For an instance when president Nixon claimed, "no one in the White House staff . . . was involved" in the Watergate break-in August 29, 1972, he was out rightly lying but it became a fact in official records.

When Saleem grows, there are quarrels at the midnight children's conference. This incident mirrors the quarrels in the Indian parliament. Similarly, the Sinai family members also witness crucial historical events. For example, Saleem's grandfather

Aadam Aziz is an eyewitness to the Jalian Wallah Bagh massacre. Again, Saleem is seen participating in the planning of a coup in Pakistan. “Not only did I overthrow a government, I also consigned a president to exile” (405). Thus, events that are connected to Saleem and his family are interpreted in such a way that they seem to affect the nation.

Rushdie shows gaps and fissures in official history and he has added imaginative details in these gaps with the help of fantasy. All these details hint at the fact that Rushdie advocates a new method of historiography through the blending of fact and fiction. For example, Saleem’s and Shiva’s parents are swapped. This incident has a great significance to the readers of history because it undermines the objectivist’s claim over historical authenticity.

Rushdie invades the personal history of the Sinai family into the national history. This overlapping gives a complex structure to the novel. At the heart of *Midnight’s Children* lies the official Indian history, beginning from the Amritsar massacre and ending with the clamping of emergency. But Rushdie, through an unreliable narrator like Saleem, parodies the official documents and creates an alternative version.

Not only Rushdie, Foucault also in “Nietzsche, Genealogy, History,” questions the finiteness of traditional history. He argues that effective history is without constants and it is full of discontinuities. The validity of the continuity of the traditional history is often questioned. The very purpose of history, according to Foucault, is “to seize the various perspectives, to disclose dispersions and differences, to leave things undisturbed in their own dimension and intensity” (125). Rushdie also tries to fill the gaps, which traditional historians left untreated.

Rushdie also seems to have been very much influenced by the New Historicist's notion of history. That is why he does not claim that his historical data are absolute. His approach hints towards a lack of confidence in the ability to find the absolute truth. His notion is very much like the notion of relativists who believe that everything is relative. The notion of relativity questions traditional historicist's confidence in finding "the Truth" about the past. Foucault talks about this aspect of history in his essay entitled "Nietzsche, Genealogy, History" as "the final trait of effective history is its affirmation of knowledge as perspective" (126). Rushdie also forwards the similar notion of perspectival history in *Midnight's Children*.

At one instance in the novel, our historian, Saleem Sinai, tries to alter the date of Mahatma Gandhi's assassination. He does it consciously and he does it for a purpose. It is not that Rushdie does not know when Gandhi was shot at. Not only this, Saleem Sinai's version about India-Pakistan war is full of contradiction because he has drawn data from different sources which contradict each other. It is very true that Pakistan's version of India-Pak war would be different than India's version of it. Our self-proclaimed historian gives such contradictory history to us as he says, "Shaheed and I saw many things which were not true, which were not possible" (432). This is why it is said that history is just a matter of perspective. For example, Adam Aziz in *Midnight's Children* questions the validity of elitists' version of Indian history as he asserts, "These Nehrus will not be happy until they have made themselves hereditary kings" (267)! Nehrus would certainly write the history of the nation differently than what Saleem has written. Historians' biases will inevitably color their writings. Similarly, in an instance Saleem claims that Valmiki made Ganesh write the Ramayana. We all have been taught for ages that Vyasa made Ganesh write the

Mahabharata and that Valmiki the Ramayana. Rushdie also knows the fact very well yet he tries to challenge it. He fictionalizes many events to undermine the traditional understanding of right and wrong. Rushdie's rationale behind such fictionalizations may be that it is impossible to know about anything with absolute certainty.

Saleem tells us the history of India but he is not totally reliable since he himself confesses that he is confused. History that he tells us is memory-based history. Human memory has limitations and when historians try to interpret any events of the past, they will interpret them with their biases and prejudices. Rushdie emphasizes such nature of history in *Midnight's Children*. Thus, we can say that *Midnight's Children* denounces the claim often made by traditional historians that history can be and should be completely objective.

Saleem Sinai calls himself a historian but he is a self-aggrandizer. That's why he says, "Already my very presence is having an effect on history; already Baby Saleem is working changes on the people around him" (178-179). Making such an unbelievable statement, which is of course a parody, Saleem tries to undermine traditional historian's self-proclaimed role and any promise of objective history. The same idea is further reinforced when Saleem says:

It is possible even probable, that I am only the first historian to write the story of my undeniably exceptional life-and-times. Those who follow in my footsteps will, however, inevitably come to this present work, this source book, this Hadith or Purana or Grundrisse, for guidance and inspiration. (410)

The above-mentioned statement made by Saleem strengthens the fact that history is just an interpretation of the historian. In this sense, it is like literature. Since it is a matter of perspective, many versions of the same event are possible. Nietzsche also

believed that history is a matter of perspective. Another incident in the novel further elaborates the idea that history is a matter of perspective. At first Dr. Aadam Aziz sees only the fragments of his would be wife and when he sees her in entirety, he is surprised to know that she has a different appearance. This is a metaphor for the nature of truth. How we look at things make us see things differently. Rushdie's use of this metaphor in *Midnight's Children* proves that we have a fragmented view of things and our attempts to write history also suffers from this lack.

Similar event is seen when Saleem narrates about the war between two parts of Pakistan. Eastern side of Pakistan fought against the western side in order to get independence. In this war, Saleem is on the side of Pakistan. After returning back from war, he goes to India and starts working in a pickle factory. This is the place where he starts writing his autobiography. He prepares chutney in the factory and writes history very much the way he makes chutney, a blend of many things. This kind of blending of official historical accounts and fictionalized accounts are found a lot in *Midnight's Children*.

For example, Dr. Aadam Aziz's involvement in Amritsar massacre in 1919 is mysterious. Official history has never talked about the incident this way. When it is said – “We were in the middle of the crowd but because of his sneezing, he miraculously escapes from the bullets of the British army” (585) – readers find it difficult to believe. Rushdie here takes help of fantasy in order to poke fun at official historical documents. It is a purposeful poking.

Similarly, in another incident Saleem finds himself in a language demonstration procession. It symbolically hints towards the fragmentation of India on the basis of language. But how is it possible for Saleem to be there? It is an element

of fiction. It is equally doubtful when Saleem says that he took part in the conspiracy of a coup in Pakistan. His involvement is nothing more than a fiction. The character of Mian Abdulla, who closely corresponds to Sheikh Abdulla in Kashmir, is also a part of a fictionalized story.

In one particular scene in the novel, Saleem loses his finger as his teacher punishes him. This incident coincides with the violence in the country. He loses a finger and India loses a certain part of her territory. Saleem claims that these two incidents are related. Such instances of fictionalizing history are rampant in *Midnight's Children*. In another incident, Saleem turns into a dog. He acquires dog-like qualities such as a strong sense of smell. A human being's transformation into a human dog is really a curious phenomenon. It is an element of pure imagination. We are being told that Saleem turns into a human dog because of his desire to assist Pakistan in finding East Pakistani leader, Mujibur Rahman. These exaggerated instances may be considered as some of the fictionalized elements in the novel that attempt to blur the demarcation line between fact and fiction or in another word between history and fiction.

Saleem gives us a fragmented history, which can be well understood in the light of postmodern historiography. Jean-Francois Lyotard defines the term, postmodern "as incredulity toward metanarratives" (36). Metanarrative or grand narratives make a false claim that they can give a comprehensive story. Grand narratives try to make a totalized view of things or events. They aspire to write world history where there are no contradicting voices. Postmodern theories reject such totalizing tendencies. Postmodernism believes in multiplicity. It believes in heterogeneity. Rather than History, it believes in histories. Postmodernists don't see

any hierarchy between history and fiction. They believe that fiction, sometimes, can give better historical understanding than history. Postmodern historiography can be very useful for our understanding Rushdian model of history as well. For example, in *Midnight's Children*, Saleem believes in multiplicities. He lives among confusions.

He says:

A thousand and one children were born; there were a thousand and one possibilities which had never been present in one place at one time before; and there were a thousand and one dead ends. *Midnight's Children* can be made to represent many things, according to your point of view: they can be seen as the last throw of everything antiquated and retrogressive in our myth-ridden nation. (278)

A single historical event is capable of generating multiple interpretations. If one version of a certain historical event exists, other versions of the same event are equally viable. *Midnight's Children* forwards such fictionalized alternative versions as alternative truths. The fictional quality of history is revealed throughout the novel both through its structure and content. Its structure is mingled with the known history of India and the Sinai family saga. The latter one is a distinct example of fiction. So far as the content of the novel is concerned, the way Saleem connects personal history with national history suggests the fictional quality of *Midnight's Children*. Saleem plainly says that his account is not at all realistic whether it is of the nation or of his family. Though he says that his account is not true, readers often find his account much more reliable than the account provided by official authorities. Saleem asks us not to believe in his accounts because he knows that all historical accounts are colored. He says:

My special blends: I've been saving them up. Symbolic value of the pickling process . . . Every pickle-jar (you will forgive me if I become florid for a moment) contains, therefore, the most exalted of possibilities: the feasibility of the chutnification of history; the grand hope of the pickling of time! (642)

Thus, it becomes apparent that Saleem has a different understanding of history. He knows the problems of history writing. He knows how the personal sometimes become the national and how the national sometimes becomes too personal. He understands the intricacies between the individual and history. He is well aware of the fact that history writing as well as other kinds of writings can never be final. That's why he says: "The process of revision should be constant and endless; don't think I'm satisfied with what I've done" (643).

Rushdie's novels are full of ambiguities. Reading Rushdie would never be an easy job. At many places in his writings, he challenges reader's long cherished beliefs too. Saleem and his family members influence and intervene most of the national events: the Jallianwalla Bagh tragedy, Quit India Movement, Cabinet Mission, Freedom Movement, Muslim League Movement, and bloodshed subsequent to the Independence, Five Year Plans, reorganization of Indian States, language riots, Chinese Aggression, the theft of the sacred relic from the Hazratbal Shrine, Pakistan War, Liberation of Bangladesh, the Emergency, chaos, communal tensions, religious fanaticism, and many more. The events may be true but his family involvement?

Saleem is well aware of the fact and that he knows very little. This is why he attempts to write history by collecting bits and fragments. In this regard, Saleem says, "A climax should surge towards its Himalayan peak; but I am left with shreds . . . Well then: I must content myself with shreds and scraps" (596). Saleem says that he,

as a historian, must work with whatever is available to him. Where Saleem feels like adding the imaginative details, he freely supplies them. By making Saleem do this, Rushdie wants his readers to know about the chimeric nature of history. Not just Rushdie but we have New Historicists and post Modernists who also believe that history is a cocktail of facts and fictions.

Saleem has all human weaknesses such as egotism, narcissism, confusion etc. He says, “Already, at the age of nearly nine, I knew this much: everybody was waiting for me” (210). Why does Rushdie create such a narrator who calls himself the first historian? Why does he proclaim his greatness? Why does he appear unreliable? Rushdie makes Saleem an ordinary human being in order to expose his new concept of history. Through the character/ narrator like Saleem, Rushdie parodies conventional historiography.

Sometimes Saleem sees himself as a master of the entire national history and sometimes he feels that he has no power over any historical event. He feels that he doesn't even know how to write history. Saleem expresses his confusion as: “I am left with shreds” (596). This instance foregrounds the fact that no history is foolproof. All versions are equally doubtful.

Thus, it seems that Rushdie strategically attempts to highlight the notion of a new history in *Midnight's Children*. In *Imaginary Homelands*, Rushdie makes it very clear that the India he portrays in *Midnight's Children* is *his* version of India (10). It is the India that exists in his mind. Therefore, Rushdie's version of India is highly subjective and he believes that any historian's version would be equally subjective. Pure history or objective history is impossible to write. Thus, Rushdie

historiography creates an alternative order that is not less interesting than any self-proclaimed objective historical account. In this regard, Saleem says:

All my life, consciously or unconsciously, I have sought out fathers. Ahmed Sinai, Hanif Aziz, Sharpsticker Sahib, General Zulfikar have all been pressed into service in the absence of William Methwold; Picture Singh was the last of this noble line. And perhaps, in my dual lust for fathers and saving-the-country, I exaggerated Picture Singh. (595)

Thus, Rushdie gives historiography a new method. He shows his conviction in imagination and the role of the artist in historiography. He tells history as a story, throwing doubt over the notions of pure objectivity.

A Note on Magical Realism

History has always been one of the most favorite topics for Salman Rushdie. The connection of history with literature is also well known. Rushdie's interest in post colonialist historiography also becomes evident in many of his novels, especially in *Midnight's Children*. Saleem Sinai, the narrator does not just rewrite Indian history but also parodies and distorts many facts and figures that Indian official historical documents had sanctioned as absolute truth. Rushdie's attempt to rewrite Indian history through the narrator like Saleem is undoubtedly a challenge to Eurocentric historiography.

Writing history as an autobiography is also an attempt to question the most cherished values and norms of colonialist historiography. Colonizers saw no variety among natives because to them natives were just like animals who do not have any distinctive features. That is why colonizers tried to make totalizing views about the nations that they ruled. This Eurocentric historical tradition comes under heavy

scrutiny in Rushdie's *Midnight's Children*. In *Midnight's Children*, Rushdie attempts to subvert the so-called Western scientific historiography and their linear thought by offering a non-linear and personal his/story.

Colonizers systematically silenced the natives for their own interest. In order to rule over natives, they had to prove their superiority over natives in all aspects. By suppressing the voice of natives, they succeeded in establishing the western notion of history. In this regard, the whole of the Indian nation can be regarded as a victim of history whose voice is silenced in the process of history writing. Postcolonial writers such as Rushdie feel that it is their responsibility to challenge the western/ the colonizer's discourse in order to restore the victim's pride. Alternative truths must be pointed at so that the so-called absolute truths that the colonizers tried to establish for such a long time could be questioned. The stories and myths of natives must be rewritten so that they survive. This is exactly what Salman Rushdie tries to do in his writings and *Midnight's Children* is an emblematic text in this direction. What Rushdie tries to do is to create alternatives not only to events but also to the discourses of history.

He achieves his target by blurring the boundary between fact and fiction. Saleem wants to write an autobiography before he dies. As he struggles to write, many things trouble him. Sometimes his memory betrays him and sometimes he does not have historical data. Wherever he lacks historical data, he fills the gaps with his imaginative power or in another word fictionalizes certain historical events. In this sense, his writing is a blend of fact and fantasy. He has two different responsibilities to fulfill at the same time. He is the narrator in the novel but at the same time a writer of his history. Sometimes he appears like a historian and sometimes like a novelist.

Thus Rushdie, in *Midnight's Children*, tries to subvert colonialist historiography by blending documented history and fiction. In this task, he uses a number of strategies, among which one is the use of magic realism.

Magic realism is a literary technique that commingles everyday reality with supernatural events. The two terms “magic” and “realism” come together in order to explore or depict new realities. Here strange and unearthly happenings become almost accepted, a part of our everyday reality. Franz Roh used the term Magical Realism for the first time in 1925 in his famous article entitled “Magical Realism: Post Expressionism.” This new art seeks to explain the objects associated with this world and give them new meanings. Magical Realism is situated firmly between two extremes –between imagination and highly structured day-to-day reality. Magical Realism attempts to bridge the gap between worldly and otherworldly things and concepts and offer glorification of the mundane world. Roh elaborates the mysterious world of magical realism as “the mystery does not descend to the represented world, but rather hides and palpitates behind it” (16). By amalgamating the elements of realism and fantasy, it rejects the mere copy art of photographs and illustrations that do not include a tinge of intellectualism and thought.

Luis Leal forwards a very practical definition of magic Realism by saying, “In Magical Realism, the writer confronts reality and tries to untangle it, to discover what is mysterious in things, in life, in human acts” (121). Though there is a disagreement among theorists and critics about the definition of magical realism most agree that magical realism is a blending of the unreal with the real. They all agree that magical realism is a glorification of the mundane. It is a desire to breathe new life into our day-to-day realities.

Magic realist novels and stories have typically a strong narrative drive in which the recognizably realistic merges with the unexpected and the inexplicable and in which elements of dreams, fairy story, or mythology combine with the everyday reality, often in mosaic or kaleidoscopic pattern of refraction and recurrence. In magic realism, we find the transformation of the common and the everyday into the awesome and the unreal. It is predominantly an art of surprises. Time exists in a kind of timeless fluidity and the unreal happens as part of reality. Once the reader accepts the *fait accompli*, the rest follows with logical precision. Magic realism is what happens when a highly detailed, realistic setting is invaded by something too strange to believe.

A literary mode rather than a distinguishable genre, magic realism aims to seize the paradox of the union of opposites. For instance, it challenges polar opposites like life and death and the pre-colonial past versus the post-industrial present. Magic realism differs from pure fantasy primarily because it is set in a normal, modern world with authentic descriptions of humans and society.

In magic realism, the magical elements are blended into a realistic atmosphere in order to access a deeper understanding of reality. These magical elements are explained like normal occurrences that are presented in a straightforward manner that allows the “real” and the “fantastic” to be accepted in the same stream of thought.

During the 1950s, magic realism became a major literary technique of Latin American writers, especially Jorge Luis Borges and the Colombian novelist Gabriel Garcia Marquez. It is often described as a literary genre or style associated especially with Latin America that integrates fantastic or mythical elements into otherwise realistic fiction. In the 1970s and 1980s, the term gained a new application and usage

with the American and Latin American literary scholars employing it to define and describe this genre using the marvelous in the real.

Authors of Magic Realism feel free to bring in the elements of dream, mythology, fairy tale and day-to-day living, creating a kind of hallucinogenic pattern of deflection and repetition. Magic realists incorporate many techniques that have been linked to post-colonialism, with hybridity being a primary feature. Specifically, magic realism is illustrated in the inharmonious arenas of such opposites as urban and rural and Western and indigenous. The plots of magic realist works involve issues of borders, mixing, and change. Authors establish these plots to reveal a crucial purpose of magic realism: a more deep and true reality than conventional realist techniques would illustrate.

In magic realism, the supernatural is not displayed as questionable. While the reader realizes that the rational and irrational are opposite and conflicting polarities, they are not disconcerted because the supernatural is integrated within the norms of perception of the narrator and characters in the fictional world.

Magic realists' alternative world works to correct the reality of established viewpoints, like realism, naturalism, and modernism. Magic realist texts, under this logic, are subversive texts, revolutionary against socially dominant forces.

Alternatively, the socially dominant may implement magic realism to dissociate themselves from their "power discourse." With magical realism, postcolonial writers are able to challenge realistic narratives and present an alternative reality.

History as Myth/ Magic in *Midnight's Children*

The events in Rushdie's *Midnight's Children* are very similar to the events recounted in the *Arabian Nights*. In this novel, the mingling of the fantastic and

ordinary, which is an aspect of magical realism, seems Indian as the characters involved in contemporary political and social upheavals also possess the power of mythic heroes. In the beginning of the novel, there is a fine passage as an example for this mingling of the real and fantastic. Such incidents in the novel give a kind of dream like quality due to the mixing up of the real life with the fantastic elements.

Such fantastic elements are often found in postcolonial writings in abundance. Rushdie wants his *Midnight's Children* to question the colonial paradigms so that the constructed "Other" may give India and such colonized countries a decolonized identity. *Midnight's Children* can be considered as one such attempt of Rushdie to recapture India. From this perspective, it can be concluded that Salman Rushdie's *Midnight's Children* links magical realism with postcolonialism.

Rushdie's ambitious novel rejects the British colonial versions of India and constructs a "new" world and a new depiction of Indian citizens and history in an attempt to provide greater truth to Indian images and history. The ability of the narrator, Saleem Sinai, to wordlessly communicate with the other Indian children born on the same day demonstrates how magic realism gives Indians the opportunity to communicate the thoughts, desires, and dreams of a nation. Hence, these midnight children literally give voice to an entire subcontinent. The formal technique of magic realism becomes the framework of the novel, through which the characters become able to communicate their individual perspectives and provide their own versions of history.

In order to effectively illustrate a new and emerging Indian postcoloniality, it becomes necessary to write in a new method to properly communicate to the colonial and post-colonial citizens. Rushdie's use of magic realism in *Midnight's*

Children becomes not only a new literary technique, but also a necessary one, vital to communicate the new problems and struggles associated with Indian postcoloniality.

Midnight's Children's usage of magical realism becomes not only a mere formal innovation, but also the most adequate expression of the history of Indian colonialism and the modern moment of Indian postcoloniality. The novel connects historical events, mythological stories, and fictional narratives and combines them to form a true picture of Indian postcoloniality.

The novel, through Saleem's personal narration, understands the need to explore the history and identity of one's nation in order to adequately express one's own personal history. Thus, the ways in which the novel's characters interact and overlap allows for the combination of fiction with myth and history. This mixing and melding of history, identity, and storytelling occurs through the social interactions within the novel, mostly occurring relationally to Saleem. The social and cultural hybridization occurring within the text directly influences Saleem's narrative, and allows new postcolonial narratives to become prominent, while marginalizing colonial narratives.

Midnight's Children is a loose allegory of events in India both before and, primarily, after the independence and partition of India, which took place at midnight on 15 August 1947. In the temporal sense, *Midnight's Children* is a post-colonial text, as the main body of the narrative occurs after India becomes independent. The narrator of *Midnight's Children* admits that his history or a major part of it "ends in fantasy" because, in a situation where reality ceases to exist, or is subverted or made invisible, fantasy is the only means of uncovering what is being hidden. So, through his novel, Rushdie tries to uncover the hidden identity of India.

The language of fantasy is not representational in the traditional sense. Like any other postmodern fiction, the language of *Midnight's Children* is not representational. It may not represent facts or what is real; instead, it may present facts in disguised form. To depict this nature of reality, at times the language becomes metaphorical. Saleem writes, "Nobody could remember when Tai had been young. He had been plying this same boat, standing in the same hunched position, across the Dal and Nageen Lakes . . . forever" (10). But as the narrator observes even if the reality has been presented metaphorically, it nevertheless is real. Certain other features of the novel also exploit the fantasy genre. For example, there is a violation of chronology in the act of storytelling. Rushdie's tale weaves past and present, jumping to and fro. It begins with the mention of Saleem's birth in 1947, and then it looks back to the twentieth century, and then briefly Saleem recalls his childhood experiences, and then it goes back to Jallianwala Bagh incident.

Another element of fantasy found in Rushdie's novel is the overt violation of what is accepted as possible or probable, true or fact. For example, like the Puranic characters, Tai the eternal boatman is ageless – "Nobody could remember when Tai had been young. He had been plying this same boat, standing in the same hunched position, across the Dal and Nageen Lakes . . . forever" (10). Rushdie brings up this sort of information in the novel to remind us that historians, at times, need to stay amid uncertainties and unsolved mysteries. For example, Saleem writes that Tai "took to drifting slowly past the Aziz household, releasing the dreadful fumes of his body across the small garden and into the house. Flowers died; birds fled from the ledge outside old Father Aziz's window" (29). Such incredulous elements when pitted against the realistic setting help us understand the reality better.

Rushdie resorts to this method in his novel very often. The midnight's children had mysterious magical powers. A boy could jump into mirrors and appear wherever he wanted. Similarly, another midnight's child could eat metal. Not only that there is a girl who can inflict physical wounds with words. Saleem himself had a highly developed sense of smell. He had the ability to get inside people's mind. There is a deliberate attempt to subvert the conventions of realistic representation in the novel. It becomes apparent as the narrator says:

It seems that the late summer of that year my grandfather, Doctor Aadam Aziz, contracted a highly dangerous form of optimism. He was by no means alone, because despite strenuous efforts by the authorities to stamp it out, this virulent disease had been breaking out all over India that year. (39)

This is obviously a reference to a real historical event, the Quit India movement in 1942. Saleem says, Mian Abdullah's humming "could fall low enough to give you toothache and when it rose to the highest, more feverish pitch, it had the ability of inducing erections in anyone within its vicinity" (46). Through all these unbelievable remarks, Rushdie signals towards the fact that facts come in history, but not always unadorned!

History as Lies and Gossip in *Midnight's Children*

Thucydides, in his introduction to *The History of the Peloponnesian War* wrote, "My conclusions have cost me some labor from the want of coincidence between accounts of the same occurrences by different eyewitnesses, arising sometimes from imperfect memory, sometimes from undue partiality for one side or the other" (40). If so, how do the historians know that the informants' memories are

accurate? How do they know that they are appropriate representations of the events they aim to portray?

Salman Rushdie, in *Midnight's Children*, explores similar issues with a great subtlety. The novel, *Midnight's Children*, written from the perspective of the main character Saleem Sinai is as much about Indian Post Independence history as it is about Saleem's personal history. In this sense, it is also a confessional autobiography.

Saleem, a self-proclaimed historian, tries to record everything, but at the same time he is aware that he cannot record everything, neither does he know everything. He is the one who decides what to include and what to preclude. His choices and rejections result into an abandonment of so-called objectivity in the act of writing history. His narrative rests largely upon his memory and his priorities. In *Midnight's Children*, our historian says that Ganesha sat at the feet of the poet Valmiki and took down the Ramayana. Saleem writes:

When Valmiki, the author of the Ramayana, dictated his masterpiece to elephant-headed Ganesh, did the god walk out on him halfway? He certainly did not. (Note that, despite my Muslim background, I'm enough of a Bombayite to be well up in Hindu stories, and actually I'm very fond of the image of trunk-nosed, flap-eared Ganesh solemnly taking dictation!).(76)

Saleem not just gives us wrong information but also boasts over his profound knowledge in Hinduism. Similarly, during his account of the evolution of Bombay, Saleem tells us that the city's chief goddess Mumbadevi has fallen out of favor with contemporary Bombayites. Saleem rather adds that the calendar of festivals reveals her decline and there is no Mumbadevi's day now. Saleem writes:

. . . but where is Mumbadevi's day? It is not on the calendar. Where the prayers of pomfret folk, the devotions of crab-catchers? . . . Of all the first inhabitants, the Koli fishermen have come off worst of all. Squashed now into a tiny village in the thumb of the handlike peninsula, they have admittedly given their name to a district-Colaba. But follow Colaba Causeway to its tip-past cheap clothes shops and Irani restaurants and the second-rate flats of teachers journalists and clerks –and you'll find them, trapped between the naval base and the sea. (45)

Though our historian tells us a lie, the truth is that the calendar of festivals clearly includes Mumbadevi Day even now. Mumbadevi has not fallen out of favor among modern Bobbayites. Rushdie thus tells history of India in *Midnight's Children* but his version of Indian history largely rests upon the memory or at times whims of the protagonist historian.

The reality Saleem witnesses in the present do not match his expectations of the past. Because the past is not a place that can be revisited in a real sense, Saleem reconstructs past in his own way. His reconstructions are his personal truths only. As a reader we should be very careful because he may be lying. Saleem writes:

. . . yes, it was my Bombay, but also not-mine, because we reached Kemp's Corner to find the hoardings of Air-India's little rajah and of the Kolynos Kid gone, gone for good, and Thomas Kemp and Co. itself had vanished into thin air . . . flyovers crisscrossed where, once upon a time, medicines were dispensed and a pixie in a chlorophyll cap beamed down upon the traffic. Elegiacally, I murmured under my breath: 'Keep Teeth Kleen and Keep Teeth Brite! Keep Teeth Kolynos Super White!' But despite my incantation, the past

failed to reappear; we rattled on down Gibbs Road and dismounted near Chowpatty Beach. (522)

In *Imaginary Homelands*, Rushdie talks about such reconstructions when he writes that he writes to “create fictions, not actual cities or villages, but invisible ones, imaginary homelands, Indias of the mind” (10). Saleem’s India is also an India of his own mind, which resides in his own memory.

In *Midnight’s Children* Rushdie thus depends on memory and uses it without hesitation in order to explore the possibilities of multiple versions of the same story. He legitimizes the claim that history also has to pass through the subjective lenses. This is why Rushdie tells lies to go beyond well-established historical data. He explains such distortions in his essay *Imaginary Homelands*:

This is why I made my narrator, Saleem, suspect in his narration, his mistakes are the mistakes of a fallible memory compounded by quirks of character and of circumstance, and his vision is fragmentary. It may be that when the Indian writer who writes from outside India tries to reflect that world, he is obliged to deal in broken mirrors, some of whose fragments have been irretrievably lost (10-11).

It is true that memory is selective and it can be edited for improvisation. When we tell stories, there also we need lots of improvisations. We add our own flavor to the stories we hear and retell them to others. A lot of history is gossip.

The conflict between past and present, history and memory ultimately creates a ground for a compromise. This compromising point is neither truly the past nor the present. It becomes a new reality. This is exactly what happens when historians write history. And this is what may happen when creative writers write fictions. Saleem

says, “Shaheed and I saw many things which were not true, which were not possible, because our boys would not could not have behaved so badly” (432). Here, Saleem does not believe his eyes! It is because he saw with his own eyes Pakistani army behaving so brutally. His heart could not accept that fact though his mind was willing to see the reality.

Saleem wanted the help of notary public to confirm it but they were also absent there. He was giving at least two accounts there –one was what was taking place there in front of his eyes, and another was what he wanted to believe. Therefore, the credibility of the historians as well as history is irretrievably linked to the nature and capacity of the narrator and his/her memory. Gaps and fissures in history are symbolically signified in the novel through Saleem’s disintegrating body. Saleem says:

Please believe that I am falling apart . . . I mean quite simply that I have begun to crack all over like an old jug –that my poor body . . . buffeted by too much history . . . has started coming apart at the seams . . . This is why I have resolved to confide in paper, before I forget. (We are a nation of forgetters).

(36)

Even though the narrative is primarily about Saleem’s trail through history, his life is linked to the hardships and atrocities that India went through after the independence. Rushdie, through Saleem, reminds the reader that there are histories and memories that are forgotten. Such stories may be the stories from the margin. Historical truth can be a mirage, a false narrative laced with gossips, lies, myths, and magic.

Thus Rushdie, in *Midnight’s Children* exposes the true nature of history and historians, closely linking history with memory. Whether his stories about India and

its struggle after Independence are correct or not, Rushdie validates that history and memory walk hand in hand and history indisputably contains lies and gossip.

Chapter V

Representation of History in *The Enchantress of Florence*

Documented History in *The Enchantress of Florence*

The Enchantress of Florence again proves that Rushdie is handcuffed to history. In this novel, he heavily draws historical data from the archives of documented (official) history. The story moves back and forth in time and space, attempting to recreate the past. In Rushdie's own words, *The Enchantress of Florence* is his most researched book that required years and years of reading ("Imagining the Self"). Rushdie tells us that he, in order to write this novel visited Fatehpur Sikri, which is a hidden treasure of art and literature. In the end of the novel, Rushdie provides us with an eight-page bibliography not only for booklovers, but also for the outside world.

The Enchantress of Florence is a preternatural novel. Since it took years and years of reading Indian historical and mythological books to compose this masterpiece, it is also like a research document. Each and every word, sentences, paragraphs, characters and characterizations of this novel are thoughtfully crafted. They are highly intertextual as well. For example, the word "enchantress" comes from an American comic book, published by D.C. Comics, and D.C. Entertainment organized by Warner Brothers. Warner Brothers are considered as an icon of Hollywood. In the original text, the enchantress is a fictional antihero character who dominates other roles with her powerful voice and fearful looks. She dominates the scenes with her mystical powers.

The second word “Florence” is derived from the Italian province of Florence. This beautiful city is famous for its history, business, and arts. It is well known throughout the world as the region that gave birth to literary Renaissance, the place where classical wisdom was reborn. Not only that, Florence is a beautiful city where every year thousands of tourists visit to enjoy its beautiful scenery. Rushdie chooses these two charming words as a title of his novel, *The Enchantress of Florence*.

It is Rushdie’s tenth novel published in 2008, based upon Indian history, mysticism, aesthetics, and wisdom. The story of the novel is set against the backdrop of the Europe and the East in around the 16th Century. The novel seems to be historically accurate to some extent but it is conceived fictionally. It appears to us as a fiction, a fabrication, but it subtly exposes a lot of aspects of India and Italy at a certain moment in history. The book is rich in presenting minute details of the countries in the particular era.

The novel concentrates upon the history of the Mughal Empire and the Renaissance. It deals with the relationship between the East and the West. In Neuman’s words “the novel seeks a refuge in the mirror of history –in this case, it is a mirror veiled in delicate multiculturalism” (675). Rushdie, like Garcia Marquez, intertwines actual historical characters and events within a story full of history, fantasy and fables.

Because Salman Rushdie knows the importance of history, in *The Enchantress of Florence* he states, “The past was a light that if properly directed could illuminate the present more brightly than any contemporary lamp” (315). A. S. Rao authenticates this point as he writes: “Meanings and truths are influenced by their

historical position and cannot in principle be set apart from history” (2). Readers contextualize the texts in order to understand them and in this process, they also appropriate the text according to their interests and needs.

The novel begins with a traveller; a Florentine gentleman called Mogor dell’ Amore, who wishes to relish the splendid beauty of Fatehpur Sikri, located at Agra district in Uttar Pradesh, India, developed and ruled by the great King Akbar. He was the third powerful king of the Mughal dynasty. His father was Humayun and his grandfather was Babur, the founder of the Mughal Dynasty in India. Akbar was an artist and he showed much interest in art and culture. He got the throne from his father Humayun who was in fact a noble man with passion in arts, literature, and paintings. Once Akbar became the ruler, gradually, he expanded his kingdom from the North to the South of India. He implemented the centralized administration system in his country. His political, economic reforms made him a successful leader. Very soon Non-Muslim communities also started believing and respecting him as their true leader.

Akbar was a great lover of books. He had volumes of classical books written in Sanskrit, Persian, Arabic, Latin and Greek languages. He invited literary scholars from the East as well the West to translate the classics into Indian languages. Akbar’s palace Fatehpur Sikri became the center of art and literature. Thus, Sanskrit literature was also translated into Greek and Latin and Persian languages. Not only that even Greek and Latin literature were translated into Indian languages. The period of King Akbar is still known as the Renaissance of Indian Literature.

Mogor dell’ Amore wanted to tell the king a story, which, as he says, nobody

had heard before. Mogor called his information “a great secret.” He was able to speak Italian, Spanish, Arabic, Persian, Russian, Portuguese and English. He was a quick learner of languages.

The stranger said that he was the son of a princess named Qara Koz, a lady with a beautiful face, glittering eyes, and a charming personality. She had some kind of special magical powers like witchcrafts. Just the way the traveller picked up languages, he also started acquiring new names. His name later on was changed to Uccello. He was a great painter of Florence and an initiator for the Renaissance of Italian Art and Paintings. Later on he tells the authorities his original name as Niccolò Vespucci instead of Mogor dell Amore.

The story also brings references of a powerful Italian Politian, historian and an artist named Machiavelli who has significantly contributed to the Western society as well as to the World. For several years Machiavelli worked as diplomat in Florentine Italy.

India has an ancient historical, cultural, religious roots so Indian historians, and writers need to go into the deep study of classics that were composed in Sanskrit Language. Rushdie’s *The Enchantress of Florence* attempts to dig out these roots. Though it comes to us as a fiction, it is replete with historical information, of the past and the present.

As Rushdie tries to trace out the hidden stories of the Mughal India, he comes up with the new realities. In the novel there is a character called “the hidden Princess.” Just like that, in the history of a nation, there may be many hidden pages or princesses. In Rushdie’s understanding, the history of India is not as plain as the British Colonizers thought. It was full of hard facts as well as of myths and magic.

Salman Rushdie, for his novels, chooses places and people very carefully. The locations that he chooses are not just physical entities, but also an idea or a form of mental construction. His Fatehpur, Sikri is not just a geographical marker, it represents something larger.

In this book, Rushdie questions many of the facts that are recorded in Indian history books, but his version of India also holds some truth. He has researched a lot and he is trying to create a counter history as well. Rushdie's characters of *The Enchantress of Florence* represent various strata of the Indian society and they automatically link us to the larger history. Rushdie's representation of the Mughal India of 16th century has poetic and aesthetic significance also. The text has many narrators and they have multiple stories. Using the technique of telling stories within stories, Rushdie succeeds in incorporating several stories of the nation.

Rushdie's characters give enough space to the readers to understand and imagine with the full length of the historical incidents. The traveler came from the West to tell a secret to the king is the main element in this novel. It gives us enough scope to compare India to the Western countries. The traveler told that had some information, which, he got from the queen. It shows that there was a good relationship between India and Italy then. The novel has different stories of the East and West. The first few chapters keep us in to the world of fantasies and historical identities. The other chapters show us the West and its history and culture.

Rushdie brings two different locations and time together in the novel with a view that they are also human constructs. What exactly is the location of India? Is India just a geographical boundary or is it something more? Obviously, any nation is more than its location. This is why Rushdie brings two different places and times

together in the novel. It does not make his novel less historical, rather it propagates a new notion of history as well.

Even if seemingly impossible events and descriptions appear in the text, they might have metaphorical significance. For instance, in *The Enchantress of Florence* Rushdie writes, “everything contained god, trees contained spirits, and so did rivers, and heaven alone knew what else” (410). Though we may not be able to prove that in every nooks and corner of India, god and spirits dwell, many people in India firmly believe in this idea even now. If people believe, it must have some significance and relevance. Such notions also become a part of the history.

By presenting history in such a strange way, Rushdie wants to highlight the strangeness of history itself. History is not as simple as many people tend to think. Rushdie, as a historian, also wants to give the common readers a message that there are various kinds of realities that exist in our societies. Rushdie clearly knows that Machiavelli was born in 1469 and he died in 1527. Similarly, Akbar was born in 1542 and he died in 1605. How is it possible that these two people meet? It is impossible but Rushdie makes it possible in his book. He has done it with a purpose. He wants to make his readers understand that time is a fluid concept. History is also something fluid. It also changes, and keeps on changing. We impose our sense of time and place upon nature and try to understand them. By creating this strange reality such as Akbar and Machiavelli coming together, Rushdie forwards his own philosophy of history. In this regard, the narrator of *The Enchantress of Florence* writes, “the past was a light that if properly directed could illuminate the present more brightly than any contemporary lamp” (315). Rushdie wants to use this light of history, the present text, to illuminate our present and future. *The Enchantress of Florence* may appear to

many readers as distorted facts, but in fact, it contains much information that we find in officially recorded history of India and Italy. It also refutes some of the data from official records. Regarding the nature of truth, Rushdie, in *The Enchantress of Florence* writes,

It comes out of the old Pygmalion idea of men who invent women to fall in love with who then escape them. In the case of the Emperor Akbar, who is the character in the novel, who invents the queen for himself, it came out to the fact that in India today, if you ask people who was the queen of the great Emperor Akbar, they all say Jodha. If you look at the historical records, she didn't exist. It is a curious legend of a Hindu queen. It's a happy legend for India because it's a myth of inclusion and tolerance. (qtd. in Shivaram Bharati 40)

Thus, it becomes clear that Rushdie's *The Enchantress of Florence* brings to us history, though it appears to us in a very sumptuous way. The book has a very strong backing from history. To conclude, Rushdie believes that history comes to us in many forms and one of them is "fact and figures".

History as Story in *The Enchantress of Florence*

Salman Rushdie's *The Enchantress of Florence* is undoubtedly a fascinating tale that brings two different worlds, the East and the West together. Rushdie in this novel, just like in *Midnight's Children* and *Grimus*, attacks any form of absolutism, be it political or personal. It seems Rushdie is waging a war against notions such as absolute truth, authority, despotism, and so on.

In order to question totalitarian views on anything, Rushdie uses historical facts and renders them into beautiful and alluring stories, using narrative as a

technique. This version of history or reality should be considered as an alternative version of reality. In Indian literature and history, Akbar and his Mughal Empire is not a new topic but Rushdie gives the same story a very powerful twist. Here, by blurring the boundary between fact and fiction, Rushdie succeeds in giving birth to a new definition of history. The creation of Rushdian character called Jodha forces readers to revisit their notion of any written account, be it fiction or history. The novel invites readers to rethink and reformulate their views about history and fiction and Rushdie achieves this end in the novel, primarily by narrativizing history.

The novel is very rich in terms of historical allusions, some of them are direct and some of them are only suggestive. The text resembles the texts like Ludovico Aristo's *Orlando Furioso* and Matteo Boiardo's *Orlando Innamorato*. These texts are 16th century Italian romantic epics that display a lot of magic and fairy tale elements. In these books readers find a world of fantasy where characters like enchanted jungles, supermen, sorceresses, and strange beasts inhabit. Rushdie also creates a similar kind of world in *The Enchantress of Florence* where we find sorceresses, princes, queens, enchanting pools, and magical landscapes.

In this world full of magic, readers also find very much down to earth realities of human existence. There is history and there are historical characters. It is a book of history but a fictionalized one. Rushdie in this novel illustrates how history and fiction walk hand in hand.

In *The Enchantress of Florence*, Rushdie presents Akbar as the history maker who dreams of many things and tries to establish them as reality. Rushdie draws a bold parallel between Allah and Allah Akbar and this suggests is how rulers create and establish truth to justify their actions. Akbar considers himself Allah. His version

of the Islamic creed comes in the novel as a counter argument. Here Akbar's story of his own greatness gives us a hint at how rulers may distort history. The narrator of *Enchantress of Florence* admits:

. . . 'The Almighty is not a tyrant. In the house of god, all voices are free to speak as they chose, and that is the form of their devotion' . . . We will build that house of adoration here on earth. . . . Then with a cry –Allaha Akbar, 'God is great', or just possibly 'Akbar is God' he –chopped off the pompous little twerp's cheeky, didactic and therefore suddenly unnecessary, head. (44)

The narrator, thus, gives us a picture of how king Akbar tries to equate himself with the supreme god. His statement however makes readers realize how the truths that historians or storytellers create are after all a human construction. It is a matter of narrative since our truths are embedded in narratives. Rushdie thus questions the validity of any so-called mainstream historical writings. Rushdie asks us to defy any claim of absolutism, be it history or literature. It is our duty to think beyond such given restrictions. Defiance is probably in our blood, as Christians believe man defied God by eating the forbidden apple. In this regard, Rushdie's *Imaginary Homelands* asserts, "Human beings understand themselves and shape their futures by arguing and challenging and questioning and saying the unsayable; not by bowing the knee, whether to god or men" (394).

Rushdie in *The Enchantress of Florence* recreates a new version of the past, using his imagination where he felt necessary. The narrator tells us the story as if it is the authentic history of Fatehpur Sikri and Italian Florence but readers are, indirectly, also provoked to question the authenticity of this narrative as well as other official

history books. In his article “New Historicism,” Louis Montrose writes about such reconstructions of the past as:

By the historicity of texts, I mean to suggest the historical specificity, the social and material embedding, of all modes of writing including not only the texts that critics study but also the texts in which we study them; thus, I also mean to suggest the historical, social and material embedding of all modes of reading. By the textuality of histories, I mean to suggest, in the first place, that we can have no access to a full and authentic past to a material existence that is unmediated by the textual traces of the society in question. (410)

Thus, it becomes quite evident that we can have no access to a full and authentic past. Historians’ claim regarding the authenticity of their historical writings does not hold water since they all are after all narratives, just like any other fictional writings. The mainstream historians often write from the vantage point of those who hold power, modifying the history according to the interest of the elites. This reality alters the reality that they try to represent and what they write often undergoes subjective colorings. New Historicism is against such fake authenticity. It tries to blur the hierarchy between literary and non-literary texts because it sees history in fiction and fiction in history. Rushdie seems to be influenced by the idea of New Historicist that both history and fiction are subjective in nature. History may try to run after fact however the prejudices of the historians and his/ her personal limitations would certainly affect the history. Once we accept this view of history, we swiftly move to what Louis Montrose said, “a shift from history to histories” (441). Rushdie’s *The Enchantress of Florence* illustrates this notion of history and historicity.

History is after all a narrative composition that embroils a dialectical affiliation of past and present apprehension. An author's subjectivity gets an outlet through the characters or the stories that they tell. Their biases may become the basis of their story telling. This unique point of view unfailingly turns historical accounts into narratives. Throughout the novel, Rushdie tries to undermine our general notion of Akbar and his Empire by bringing together historical data and fictionalized accounts. For instance, Akbar has many reasons not to believe the stranger who has come to the king's court. The foreigner looks much younger than the king yet he claims himself to be the uncle of the king. Here it becomes very difficult for Akbar as well as the readers to know who is speaking the truth and who the lies. This is the nature of reality and this is the reality of historical narratives as well. Akbar does not tend to believe what the Florentine gentleman says. Yet the story the foreigner is saying is so compelling that he cannot deny it. Akbar gets into a great dilemma for he does not know how to react to the stories that the foreigner tells. Mogor dell Amore says, "My mother was Qara Koz, your grandfather's sister the great Enchantress, and she learned how to stop time. "No, said the emperor Akbar. No, she did not" (430). King Akbar does not so easily believe on what the Mogor says but he also does not have the power to drive the foreigner away. It is because he wants to listen to the story as well.

The stories that Mogor tells are crafted in beautiful language. Since history writing is also embedded in language itself, it can encompass this literariness. Hayden white in this regard writes:

All historical narratives presuppose figurative characterization of the events they purport to represent and explain. And this meant that historical

narratives, considered purely as verbal artifacts, can be characterized by the figurative discourse . . . language itself provided in the four principal modes of figurative representation: metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche and irony. (404)

White describes historical writings from a new perspective. This literariness embedded in the language of men of literature as well as of historians denies the idea that history can be completely objective and it communicates just one meaning.

Rushdie also seems to be sharing the notion of history and literature that Hayden White carries. By fusing fantasy and realism, Rushdie redraws the boundary of historical writings. An intruder's attempt to tell the history of Mughal Empire and Renaissance France itself questions the traditional way of history writing. The *Enchantress*, which is a fusion of fact and fantasy, resists the notion of objective history because if we believe in the existence of the enchantress, we must believe in fictionalized history.

Rushdie in this novel bridges two realities –the subjective and objectivist ways of looking at things and the subjectivist way of looking at things. It becomes apparent when the narrator says –“The world is a bridge. Pass over it but build no house upon it” (72). It means all types of writings, be it literary or historical are a kind of bridge. They are just tools to interpret what we encounter or think about. So, all kinds of writings are a blend of fact and fiction. In this sense, they all are narratives, and history too is a kind of narrative.

Any literary text that comes into existence can never escape the social and cultural context of the time. Readers' attempt to interpret it also gets affected by their own historical positioning. So, interpretations vary. In this regard, Lois Tyson, in her book *Critical Theory Today* writes, “Traditional historicism tended to ignore or

marginalize private life as subjective and irrelevant, new historicism tries to compensate for this omission by bringing issues concerned with private life into the foreground of historical inquiry” (289). Tyson here tries to assert New Historical notion that history is a matter of interpretation, not facts, and interpretations always occur within the framework of social and political conventions.

Akbar was a historical figure. But Rushdie’s Akbar may be a product of history as well as Rushdie’s imagination. Likewise, the young Florentine Niccolo Machiavelli is a fictional reality but he is also treated as a historical figure. Some characters of the novel are the inventions of other characters. For example, Jodha, and Qara Koz or the Enchantress, are creatures of Akbar’s imaginations. They are his fantasies for love and fulfillment. Here, Rushdie aims to mock at the reality about Akbar’s history and teases us also to segregate fact and fiction in historical documents. Of course, it is not so easy to differentiate facts from fictionalized narratives. In this regard, the narrator narrates:

Greater than the king of kings who ruled Persia before the Muslims came, superior to the ancient Hindu notion of the Chakravartin –the king whose chariot wheels could roll everywhere, whose movements could not be obstructed –he was the universal Ruler, king of a world without frontiers or ideological limitations. What followed from this was that human nature, not divine will, was the great force that moved history. He, Akbar, the perfect man, was the engine of time. (387)

Following the insights of New Historicists, Rushdie, tries to mock at these grand narratives of historical records that pretend to be damn serious about objectivity. Presenting Akbar as a historian, Rushdie highlights to the possibility of

distortions in official historical documents. It is because rulers would certainly like to magnify themselves. As Rushdie recreates him, Akbar is an absolute monarch but with tremendous faith in democracy and liberalism. At times, Rushdie's Akbar appears very impulsive. Rushdie's Akbar and the real king Akbar are certainly different. In *The Enchantress of Florence*, Rushdie writes:

Discord could be quelled, and it was his fist that could quell it. But what then, of the voice within that whispered . . . that discord, difference, disobedience, disagreement, irreverence, iconoclasm, impudence, even insolence, might be wellspring of the good. These thoughts were not fit for a king. (391)

Was Akbar really like that? Did he really feel like that? We don't have any absolute answers to these questions. But in Rushdie's recreation of the King, he appears to be a noble ruler. Using facts from history and fusing them with splendid imaginative details, Rushdie gives us a version of the Mughal Empire and this version comes to us in the form of a beautiful history. Not just Akbar, Rushdie also creates an entirely new character who we cannot find in the historical achieves. The narrator describes this character as:

Qara Koz unveiled –as angelica –had come into the fullness of her womanly powers and was exerting the full force of those capacities upon the city, misting the air with a benevolent haze which filled the thoughts of Florentines with images of parental filial, carnal and divine love. Anonymous pamphleteers declared her to be the reincarnation of the goddess Venus. Subtle perfumes of reconciliation and harmony filled the air, people worked harder and more productively, the quality of family life improved, the birth rate rose and all the churches were full. (351)

This lady becomes a new reality to readers just the way Akbar's queen Jodha has become a character of history. He describes the golden enchantress as, "The distance between Enchantress and witch was still not so great. There were still voices that suggested that this new incarnation of the woman-wizard through whom the occult powers of all women were unleashed" (352). This character, a creation of Rushdie himself, is a kind of added page to Indian history. People may believe her or disbelieve but she reminds us of a possibility that historians may ignore or deliberately omit some of the actors from history and sometimes they may add, if they wish. Regarding such connections between history and literature D.G. Myers writes:

The New Historicist effort to assimilate the literary text to history is guaranteed by the post structuralist doctrine of textuality, which states that the text is not aloof from the surrounding context, that there is contiguity, an ebb and flow, between text and whatever might once have been seen as "Outside" it. Yet those ideas are obtained second hand. (31)

New historicists' notion of textuality and historicity very much applies to *The Enchantress of Florence*. How much are these characters author's imagination and how much are they real is a very complex question to answer. This is the reason why New Historicists see history in fiction and fiction in history. Thus, *The Enchantress of Florence* can be regarded as a kind of new historical text where the writer appears highly concerned with the recreation of history by blurring the boundaries between history and imagination.

History as Myth and Magicin *The Enchantress of Florence*

Magic has been an integral part of Indian culture since times immemorial. One can easily find the traces of magic in almost every Hindu scripture, including the Vedas and the Puranas. Texts like the Mahabharata and the Ramayana are considered as very authentic documents of the past in India. These texts are not just stories of gods and goddesses but also books of history. They are thereby categorized as *Itihasa* or history. History also gets manifested to Indians in such magical modes. Though many Indians may like to take these magical stories as divine interventions, this magical or the fantastic mode of history writing has permeated Indian culture very significantly.

Rushdie attempts to rewrite the history of Renaissance Florence and Mughal India in *The Enchantress of Florence* using myth and magic as a mode of historical representation. He uses fantasy and magic as a tool to revisit the past. In the novel, he creates a character called Mogor who fantastically connects the East with the West. This character doesn't just bring two different worlds together but also brings together two different historical eras. Mogor is a European traveler who comes to Akbar's court with a message from his queen, as he claims. He claims himself to be a distant relative of King Akbar. This unique setting of the story helps Rushdie to weave stories around these two different eras and continents.

The protagonist, Mogor claims himself to be a child of an exiled Mughal princess Qara Koz, also named as Lady Black Eyes. Rushdie has drawn this story of the exiled princess from some historical accounts but he has appropriated this story in his own way, with some purposes in his mind. According to some of the available historical narratives, Lady Black Eyes was a Mughal princess who had been held

captive by the enemy during the war. But even after the victory of her country, she refused to return back to India. It was because she had already fallen in love with a Florentine gentleman. In fact, she was the Emperor Babur's half-sister. Though Rushdie does not use this historical information as it is, he retells the story in a different fashion.

To retell this story, Rushdie chooses a magical mode. He endows Qara Koz with magical powers. Once she becomes an enchantress, it justifies Rushdie's narration where this lady practices sorcery and witchcraft. As she gradually comes in contact with many other men, she enriches the story of *The Enchantress of Florence* with her magical powers.

According to Mogor, Akbar's grandaunt Qara Koz fell in love with Argalia, an Italian gentleman, during the battle between the Ottomans and Persians. This is why she refused to return back to India, even after the victory of her brother. She then comes in contact with various historical characters, even Machiavelli. She becomes very popular among Florentine gentlemen because of her beauty and magic. She goes in the hand of one man after another and creates a lot of stories or histories.

As Mogor goes on telling one story after another, the king also starts believing in them. Though Mogor's stories are too implausible at times, Akbar becomes helpless to ignore them because the stories that Mogor tells are very spellbinding. Slowly the king gets trapped into these stories. In this process, he also imagines a wife for him whose name the world knows as Jodha. He believes not just in his own fantasy world but also makes his people believe in this. King Akbar and his subjects reach a point from where they can't differentiate between magic and reality.

Rushdie uses this sort of magical mode in *The Enchantress of Florence* in order to reconstruct the past. This novel can be taken as Rushdie's attempt to reconstruct history in the magical mode. Using this reconstructive strategy, artists and historians try to get an access to the past. Past is something that is already dead. If we are to bring the dead back, we must use some sorcery! Rushdie exactly does the same. Such reconstructed version of the past may counter the already established truths. They may often counter the so-called claims over objectivity in the act of writing or recording the past. Such reconstructions of the past may lead to the creation of new myths and stories. In fact, they are the new histories. These new accounts help readers to look at the past from new perspectives. Rushdie is an advocate of such new versions of history. In this regard, G.R. Elton writes:

The discovery of truth requires not only acquaintance with the available evidence and scholarly assessment of it, but also imaginative reconstruction and interpretation. Evidence is the surviving deposit of an historical event, in order to rediscover the event, the historian must read not only with the analytical eye of the investigator but also with the comprehensive eye of the story-teller. (76-77)

Elton considers historians artists who do not just record the past but also recreate it, if required. In this view historians should be able to analyze the past as well as add something to it if necessary. Hegerfeldt in *Lies That Tell the Truth* writes, "history never consists of purely factual and impartial accounts, but serves the interests of those who write it" (63). Of course, the *Enchantress of Florence* also serves some interests of Salman Rushdie. He, as a historian and as a novelist, has some messages to his readers, regarding the nature of history and fiction.

The Enchantress of Florence questions the monolithic understanding of history and historiography. It foregrounds the idea that history can be written in many ways. Mogor's method of telling history problematizes the so-called objectivist historiography. In Mogor's version, readers find a very strong presence of myth and magic. Rushdie has rewritten some of the important historical details in a fairy tale like manner. He has been referring to the motifs such as the fountain of eternal youth in the novel. Not only that he also brings references of mythical characters such as mermaids. The city where Rushdie locates the novel is itself a fairytale like city. How can we assume that in Fatehpur, Sikri, there used to flow a river of gold? Rushdie deliberately turns this historical place to a fairy tale like place with a purpose. He is trying his readers to understand that any place or person in the hands of historians or artists may become something new. It is because writers or historians appropriate the people and the places in their own way and for their own purpose. Trying to recapture the city of Fatehpur of Mughal era is itself a herculean task. Writers may have to use the available facts and their own fantasies in order to recreate these dead things. Rushdie exactly does the same thing in the novel. He creates his own version of the Mughal India. Rushdie writes:

In the day's last light the glowing lake below the palace-city looked like a sea of molten gold . . . perhaps (the traveler surmised) the fountain of eternal youth lay within the city walls –perhaps even the legendary doorway to paradise on earth was somewhere close at hand? But then the sun fell below the horizon; the gold sank beneath the water's surface, and was lost. Mermaids and serpents would guard it until the return of daylight. (5-6)

This is the city of Fatehpur Sikri that Rushdie recreates. He does this with the help of myth and fantasy. So historical representation or recreation may use such mode in order to revive what has been already dead, the past. Traditional historiography supposedly deals with facts and figures. These historians opt for empirical data but Rushdie devises a different mode of historical representation. He does not believe that any historian can recreate the past, using the available data, as it were. In Rushdie's view, historians must manipulate the available data in a certain way, with a certain purpose in mind.

Rushdie's magical or mythical mode of historical representation presents the established historical truths in an entirely new way. The well-acquainted stories of the past all of a sudden appear to us as if they are totally new. Rushdie makes it very clear in an interview with Mustich, as he says,

I knew that people would assume that some of the most amazing things in it were things I made up. For me, writing this novel revealed once again the old truism about truth being stranger than fiction; I think actually almost all the stuff that people will think is outrageous magic realism is actually in the history books, and the stuff people think "oh, that's probably true", is the stuff that I've made up. (2)

Rushdie's view of history writing may remind a Nepalese reader of his/her own history books that tell them magical stories of the creation of Kathmandu valley. According to one most repeated event in Nepalese history, a demigod named Manjushree made Kathmandu suitable for human settlement and he did that with a big sword! Such fabulous stories are found in any nation's history books. If so, why can't one say that history may come to us, at times, as myth and magic?

In this sense we can understand why Rushdie writes history using myth and magic. He blurs the boundary between fact and fiction in order to highlight the hidden principle of magic realism as our everyday life itself is infused with myths and magic. In our everyday life also, it is not easy to draw the boundary between the real and the imaginary. We all have different sorts of fantasies and dreams. Our versions of ourselves, our family, our nation, our religion, and so on may be after all our delusions and megalomaniac ideas.

Thus, we can safely assert that *The Enchantress of Florence* takes its readers into a magical world that Rushdie creates but this world is also a kind of reality that had been hiding somewhere in the pages of official history. Rushdie just dug it out and presented it to the readers.

Rushdie has drawn many characters of this novel from official history books such as king Akbar, Uzbek Khan, Machiavelli, and so on. His descriptions of renaissance Italy as well as of Mughal India are not totally imaginative. He has done a lot of research, as he himself has made it clear. He has drawn a lot of ideas from official records and of course he has teased them out very cleverly. He has artistically played with the gaps and fissures that he found in official versions of history.

Rushdie in his interview with Mustich says that most of the information for *The Enchantress of Florence* comes from an autobiography written around 16th century titled *Baburname* where there is the mention of a royal princess named Qara Koz. This lady with the black eye is not totally fictitious. She is also found in history books but her stories are not well developed. Rushdie does this in *The Enchantress of Florence*. Historians must use surrealistic devices such as fantasy and dream to recreate or revive such blank pages of history. Rushdie, as a student of history, knows

what is there in historical archives and he knows what is lacking in them. So, he deliberately weaves this tale of history and magic around Qara Koz and Jodha in order to expose the fictional nature of a historical narrative.

If we equate Jodha with history, Rushdie's intention becomes clear. Any student of history would understand that Rushdie is trying to exemplify how myths and magic may creep into any historical narrative, with the author's intention or at times without the author knowing it. Rushdie writes, "In reality, while it is true that she does not exist, it is also true to say that she is the one who lives" (56). This is the nature of history as well. In history also, there may be many components like Jodha who common readers may regard as fantasy or magic. Just the way Jodha's fame will last for years and years as truth, such fantastic elements will also continue spicing up any historical narratives. Jodha thus represents this fantastic mode of representing historical reality. This element may exist in any historical narrative; some may have more portions of it whereas some others may have it in a lesser amount. How Akbar made his imaginative queen Jodha real gives readers some idea on how historians may establish truths. When historians attempt to write history, they often rely on others' documents. But Rushdie in his interview with Mustich says:

The Enchantress is the key to his (Mogor's) story, of course, but I very deliberately wrote the book in such a way that you don't really meet her for the first half of the novel. Up until then, you are aware of her as a person that other people talk about, as a tale told, rather than a reality. You don't meet her except the other people's versions. She is a quasi-legendary figure, mythical and imbued with occult powers, etc., but you only know this because other people say so. (7)

This is exactly the nature of history. Historians come to know about most of the events of the past through others. How reliable are these records? This is a very vexing question to all historians. The existence of Jodha and Kora Koz forces readers to rethink about their blind faith in historical narratives. History is not just facts, and it is also not just a plain narrative. It is also myth and magic. Myth and magic inevitable creep into any historical narrative, though in a subtle form. When king Akbar imagines his most beautiful and endlessly satisfying wife Jodha, his entire subjects automatically believe in her existence. Even if the king is aware of her fictional self, his subjects do not know anything about it. They believe in what the king believes. It is the king's fantasy turned into historical reality. This is how historians also often turn fantasy into reality.

The process of Jodha getting a real existence and identity mirrors the process of history writing. Historians also make it possible for certain people and events to exist in a certain manner. With the arrival of Jodha in Mughal Empire, the notion of reality and fantasy gets blurred, in Akbar's mind as well in his people's minds.

Rushdie writes:

They genuinely couldn't see the woman to whom they were speaking, yet they were willing to arrange themselves on her carpets, lounge against her bolsters, drink the wines her servants offered, and tell the sexual secrets of women throughout history to the empty air. After a while they stopped feeling that they had lost their minds, and acted as if they were alone, just the two of them talking to each other, speaking openly about what had always been closed, laughing helplessly at the shocking comedy of desire . . . (407)

This is the power of storytelling. Historians also, just like storytellers, may use such fantastic modes of history writing in order to recapture the past. Once they create some myths and stories, these stories become the basis of people's everyday lives. By shattering the oppressive power of time, space, and history, Kora Koz serves the above-mentioned purpose in the novel.

Just because Rushdie incorporates myth and magic in *The Enchantress of Florence* many people have questioned the historical significance of this text. But Rushdie in his interview with Mustich says:

What was very liberating imaginatively is that one of the real things about the world at this time, both in the East and the West, was a passionate belief in magic. People believed in magic in the way that we believe in doctors and scientists. And they believed on it not as something separate from their daily life, but as very much part of it. People were using magic in an everyday way –it was an enormous part of the way in which they understood the world. They saw the world as a place permeated by magic, and therefore, they believed that magic could give them power they might not have otherwise. (3)

Thus, Rushdie exemplifies how myths and magic also dwell in historical narratives. *The Enchantress of Florence* vividly displays how history may come to readers in the form of myth and magic.

History as Lies and Gossip in *The Enchantress of Florence*

The Enchantress of Florence mixes history and legend together in order to recreate or reinvent new myths and histories. This mixing of the real with the fictional and the incorporation of the mythical with the historic enriches the literariness of the text and opens the scope for the free play of readers' imagination. The story moves

back and forth in time and space, blending fact and fiction, using myth and memories for the redefinition of truth itself.

The novel is set in the era of 16th century and the story revolves around a young Italian called Mogor dell Amore and his visit to the Mughal emperor Akbar's court. Nicolle Vespucci, as the Florentine gentleman calls himself, claims to be a long lost relative, the uncle of Akbar. He says he was born of an exiled Mughal princess Qara Koz and a Florentine warrior Antonio Argalia. Basically, a mix of imagination and reality, the book is populated with a large number of historical figures and incidents, all steeped in a fine fictional fabric.

Employing all the typical postmodern literary devices like irony, magic realism, parody, coupled with the theme of the East and the West and the search for a new world, the novel opens itself up for an alternative historical reality. Rushdie's principal aim in this mixing of myth and history is the renewal of the concept of history itself. He demands for the removal of the prejudices of historical objectivity.

It seems that Rushdie is asking us to be very alert while reading history for historians also may tell us lies, just like other human beings. Though many people tend to dislike this idea that history may contain lies and distortions, the truth is that history is also a storehouse of lies, not just facts. There are innumerable propagandist historians around us and many historians have been knowingly or unknowingly creating and reinforcing historical lies. Any reader of history should be ready to accept this fact. That's why there are various kinds of history like official history, people's history, alternative history, marginalized history and the like.

Myths have two meanings: the first one is that myths are ancient stores that justify our worldview, and the second meaning is that myths are unfounded stories or

lies. Myth strengthens the fictionality of the text, whereas the historical accuracy justifies the claims of the objectivity of the text. In the words of A. S. Rao, “meanings and truths are influenced by their historical position and cannot in principle be set apart from history. The reality of a literary text lies with the reader’s imagination” (64). *The Enchantress of Florence* gives emphasis to such imaginative world order.

Adopting a historiographical meta-fictional mode, knowingly disrupting chronology, introducing supernatural occurrences and historically inaccurate data, the novel reminds the reader that history is a relative construct, riddled with subjectivity. Sundararaghavan hints at the possibility that history may contain gossip and lies as she says:

The myths crafted by empire, as also political myths of any era, have the ability to partially or wholly falsify, or shall we say fictionalize history as the facts themselves often suffer mutilation or erasure. Facts are obscured by propaganda, media manipulation and image building experts who project a picture far removed from reality. (2)

The blurred boundary between truth and lies is intensified in the novel through the presence of a character called Qara Koz. Who is Qara Koz and how she came to be the mistress of Argalia forms the central narrative that Niccolo Vespucci tells. Akbar, who has been completely ignorant of this hidden princess in the history of Mughals, is completely taken aback when he listens this story from Mogor. The story of Qara Koz/Angelica/ the lady black eyes, is an account that the foreigner Mogor del Amore narrates to Emperor Akbar to fill in the gaps in the history of the Mughals.

The introduction of the myth of Qara Koz is a clear deviation from the traditional historical narratives. The narrator, who claims to be the son of this lost

princess of the Mughal household, puts it as, “She was a princess of the true Chaghatrai blood, a direct descendent of Genghis Khan, a member of the house of Timur, and the sister of the first Mughal Emperor of India, whom she called the Beaver” (166). The narrator Niccolo Vespucci goes on to narrate the story of his mother and claims that “her name was Angelica and she was, a Mughal princess, and the most beautiful woman anyone had ever seen, and an enchantress without compare, a mistress of potions and spells of whose powers all were afraid” (167).

Thus, this wondrous beauty’s adventure in the Middle East and Florence, as she conquers the heart of one bloody conqueror after another, becomes the core of the novel. She is every man’s lubricious dream, at once princess, slave and witch, and willing to do whatever is required to please her current lord and to survive. Rushdie draws the character of Qara Koz on the magic realist lines by juxtaposing the sharply rendered and detailed elements, in the foreground and background, to develop an atmosphere of mystery and ambiguity. Her extraordinary beauty that makes men fall in love with her, and the magical powers that she uses to enchant others, render the ordinary unfamiliar and magical, thus blurring the line between fact and illusion. With these dreams of Akbar and the subsequent clarifications provided by Qara Koz, the mystery around the foreigner and his ancestry is solved to some extent and all the strands of the story are united. The narrator, who is endowed with a fractured and faulty vision of his ancestry and identity, reshapes his history through the imaginative reconstruction of the past. Thus, through the imagination of the narrator, the history of the Mugal emperors becomes clearer.

In the novel, the characters from the East are chronologically intertwined with characters from the Western world, along with their culture and religion that they

signify. The encounter between Akbar and the Mogor is a literal manifestation of the connection between the East and the West, one of the novel's thematic strands.

Rushdie, like Garcia Marquez, intertwines actual historical characters and events within a story full of magical realism and fantasy.

History and myth coexist when the hidden Mughal princess and the Enchantress Qara Koz meets Niccolo Machiavelli, and when Argalia battles Vlad the Impaler, Dracula. One constantly questions –which are the true details and which are the products of Rushdie's extraordinary imagination? Akbar's favorite wife Jodha is a product of his imagination, an imaginary wife dreamed up by Akbar. That imagination is so strong that she becomes real, at least until Akbar's intense love for her diminishes. This is a sheer portrayal of the ultimate male fantasy, as well as an expression of the way in which imagination becomes real.

Rushdie mixes reality and fantasy in such a way that one no longer knows where the dream world ends and the real world begins. The episode of the painter Dashwant painting Qara Koz to life and himself vanishing as an imaginary being “in the margins of history” (190) is a typical example of the disruption of border lines between real and unreal, life and art. In many ways, *The Enchantress of Florence* is a story about the story, a meta-fiction that looks at the line between history and gossip and crosses it.

Gossip is often derided as something negative in almost all cultures. It is one of the mostly relished and at the same time mostly denounced form of discourse. Some cultures are too intolerant about gossip, at least in public, and some cultures are a bit flexible. Gossips are very involving and interesting. Many people enjoy gossips as guilty pleasure also. Not all gossips are trivial and idle and similarly not all gossips

are demeaning and destructive. Gossips have played a significant role in the creation of knowledge, be it historical or scientific. Though women are often blamed for indulging into gossips, men also equally enjoy such spiced up stories.

One may find gossips of the past in diaries, memoirs, legal writings, government records, newspapers, magazines, literary texts, and even in history books. Yes, gossips are an integral part of history books also! So, gossips may come to us in the form of history and sometimes history may come to us in the form of gossips.

For example, in Rushdie's *Enchantress of Florence*, King Akbar fantasizes Jodha, probably the most seductive and the most beautiful woman on earth so far. People of his kingdom helped spread this story in the form of gossip throughout the nation and abroad. In the long run, some of the history books also incorporated this story as a real historical happening. So far, the story of king Akbar and his queen Jodha has already become an integral part of Indian psyche. But Satish Chandra writes:

The identity of Jodha Bai has for long been a matter of some discussion among historians. The recent debate in the media whether Jodha Bai was the wife or the daughter-in-law of Akbar has created fresh public controversy.

The discussion has arisen because the name of Jodha Bai does not occur anywhere in the Persian chronicles of the period. (237)

King Akbar had three-reputed historians in his palace but they have nowhere mentioned the name Jodha. Satish Chandra's claim over Jodha's existence throws some light on an important aspect of history and historiography. Everywhere in Indian texts we find the stories of Jodha and Akbar but is it a real story or just a story? Whether Jodha existed or not is not so important question here but what is

important for students of history is that gossips are not only an integral part of historical inquiry but also a legitimate branch of historical evidence.

Thus Rushdie, in *The Enchantress of Florence*, reimagines and reinvents history weaving it with fantasy, memory, tradition and other cultural artifacts, proving once again that history may contain lies and gossips and at times history may come to us as lies and gossip. Sometimes historians deliberately mask their truths with the fabrics of lies. Rushdie has accepted in an interview that it was fiction that saved his life. He has confessed if he had claimed to be a historian after the publication of his novels such as *Midnight's Children* and *Satanic Verses*, he would have been probably killed.

Chapter VI

Representation of History in *Grimus*

History as Fact in *Grimus*

Grimus, Rushdie's first novel, belongs to the genre of fantasy, and is not directly linked to historical events. *Grimus*^[1] deals with the issues like history, time, change, and immortality. It is a tale of fantasy, of magic potions, of alien creatures, and of travel through space and time to other dimensions. *Grimus* provides Rushdie with an opportunity to discuss some of his basic ideas of history and historiography.

The basic premise of the story of *Grimus* is fairly simple –three men, Virgil, Deggle and Grimus discover a Stone Rose of incredible powers. These powers include enabling these men to travel to other dimensions of time and space, conceptualizing other worlds, and granting immortality to themselves and to others. The three characters then choose certain mortals they deem worthy of everlasting life, and provide them with a world, Calf Island, where they would be among their own kind. Flapping Eagle, the hero, is one of these chosen men.

Power often corrupts and changes men. Deggle proves it again by stealing a branch of the Stone Rose. Deggle's mistake later on invites a series of consequences. Dimension Fever incapacitates Virgil. *Grimus* sets himself up on a mountaintop as a kind of deity. The inhabitants of Calf Island, rather than being inspired by their immortality, commit suicide or become so obsessive that they are no longer sane. It becomes apparent that Deggle's damaging of the Rose has caused a weakness in the very foundations of the island that is manifested in blinks of time and space. It is

Flapping Eagle's duty, as the Grimus look-alike, to overcome *Grimus* and become his son and successor.

Despite the complex ideas such as immortality, travel in time and through dimensions, the structure of the book is quite simple and follows a basic chronological order. The first section of the novel entitled "Times Present" moves in space from Calf Island to Amerindia and back to the island, and travels in near time from Flapping Eagle's twenty-first birthday to his arrival on the island some seven hundred year later.

The second section, "Times Past," outlines the background and endless present of the denizens of K. In order to protect themselves from the destructive nature of the Grimus effect that is causing the gradual disintegration of Calf Island, the town people have thrown into obsessive behavior that denies change. If a crack appears in that behavior, if they begin to doubt, then they will succumb to Dimension Fever. Flapping Eagle's initial acceptance of the way of life in K grants him a certain sense of calm:

Time is passing more slowly now, thought Flapping Eagle, and felt^[SEP]nearly happy. To be in K was to return to a consciousness of history, of good times, even of nationhood: O'Toole, Cherkassov . . . Like them or not, the names conjured a past world back to life. Here in the womb of the Gribb drawing room he felt and found comfort. (162)

Because life is indefinite and nothing is allowed to change, there is no sense of anticipation in K, and there seems to be no future. One of the characters explains, "My husband lives too much in the past; we all do I suppose. You must not think him mad. He is quite sane" (180). And so, she believes are all the others who continue in

their assigned roles, remaining forever the same. It is only those like Virgil who break free of self-imposed limitations. Virgil realizes that Flapping Eagle too is different from the others on the Calf Island. At first, he tries to convince him to alter his ways to fit those of the island:

Mr. Eagle, you do seem to have led a rather epic life. I'm afraid we can offer you no stories to match yours. We live wholly in the microcosm, you see; the state of my corns and the state of nations are to me of equal concern. I don't want at all to preach but I would recommend that you adapt yourself to minutiae; they are so much less confusing. (51)

In the third section of *Grimus*, there is the scene of the succession of Flapping Eagle and the reconceptualization of Calf Island. Before this can be accomplished, both Flapping Eagle and the reader must be supplied with additional information about Grimus, the Stone Rose and its powers. This is done in the form of a diary, written by Virgil, and read aloud to Flapping Eagle by Virgil's wife Liv. This is an interesting narrative device, for it allows the reader and certain characters to access details they would otherwise not have had.

More than one narrative voice exists in this text. The first to appear is a third person omniscient voice that is viewing the activities of Dolores and Virgil in Calf Island. This narrator is not a character in the novel. The next narrative voice is an uncertain voice that begins in the third person, describing "the young man," and develops into the first person, "I was the boy. I was Joe-Sue" (15). Statements, such as "It was Joe-Sue's birthday, I got up and went outside" demonstrate this distance. Part of the space could be due to the fact that there are seven hundred years and

several rebirths between the characters Joe-Sue and Flapping Eagle. Still, this narrator says he is Joe-Sue, not Flapping Eagle, yet chooses to allow the gap to continue.

There seems to be another third person narrator, separate from Flapping Eagle, who is probably the same narrator that opened the story. In the hierarchy of narrators, it is the third person omniscient that exists at the top, occupying the greatest amount of time and space of the text.

One of the major concepts introduced here, and pursued throughout his later works, is the idea that participating in history signifies influencing history. It means recording, telling or even just living, for all acts have the potential to be historical events. When Mr. Jones is first introduced to Flapping Eagle, he does not know that he is:

. . . about to make his rendezvous with a small historical event . . . for if he had known, he would have philosophized at length about the parade of history, about the historian's inability to stand apart and watch; it was erroneous, he would have said, to look upon oneself as an Olympian chronicler; one was a member of the parade. An historian is affected by the present events that eternally recreate the past. (11-12)

It can be easily understood that Rushdie writes here, and demonstrates throughout his fiction, that the historian does and must participate in the creation of history. The entire novel *Midnight's Children* is built on this premise. The importance of the historian, be s/he a character or the narrator, cannot be underestimated. If the historian participates in history, then surely s/he will influence it too.

This novel, unlike the others, is not set in a specific time period but there are some clues that help readers to situate the story. Bird-Dog, Flapping Eagle's sister,

takes her name from a “singing machine” that “sang about a creature called bird-dog, clever, and fiendish” (*Grimus* 18). This is a reference to a 1950s song by the Everly Brothers. Flapping Eagle tells us he has been alive for over seven hundred and seventy-seven years, and that, “All the people on the island . . . seem to come from a time roughly contemporaneous with the time I took the Elixir” (*Grimus* 101). Flann Napoleon O’Toole, a resident of the island, says to another who is avoiding a fight, “T’would be an act of true pacifism. For which I believe the Sanskrit word is Ahimsa. Mr. Gandy himself would be proud of you” (*Grimus* 138). “Mr. Gandy” mentioned here is of course Mahatma Gandhi; thus, the story takes place at least some seven hundred years past the mid-1900s and moves through centuries apart.

Calf Island is the refuge of those immortals that can no longer tolerate existence amongst mortals. The object of their obsession can be almost anything: love, hate, good deeds, revolution, or each other. *Grimus* considers life in Calf Island a kind of laboratory experiment:

This is the nature of Kaf, it is an attempt to understand human nature by freeing it from its greatest instinctual drive, to preserve the species through reproduction. The Elixir of Life is a beautifully two-edged weapon, removing at a stroke the possibility of reproduction by sterilizing recipients, and also nullifying the need to reproduce by conferring immortality. The island, furthermore, is plentiful and fertile. (292)

One citizen of Calf Island cushions himself with a protective layer of study. In normal life, one never has enough time to follow one’s theories through to the end but here in Calf Island that is no longer a problem. Another character Ignatius Quasimodo Gribb elucidates his obsession as:

Many years ago, he said, I became engrossed in the notion of race-memory: the sediment of highly concentrated knowledge that passes down the ages, constantly being added to and subtracted from. It struck me that the source-material of this body of knowledge must be the stuff itself of philosophy.

(*Grimus* 160)

Flapping Eagle, the hero of the story, has to develop his own obsession in order to survive immortality and the Grimus Effect. Gribb describes Flapping Eagle's obsession as, "this preoccupation with simplistic explanations of origin which is all creation myths are" (185).

Mythology and rebirth are two vital themes in *Grimus*. Mythological as well as historical names used in this novel include Jocasta (of the Oedipus story), Sisyphus (who here counts rather than pushes stones), and Grimus himself, who takes his name from, "a respect for the philosophy contained in the myth of the Simurg, which contains all other birds and in turn is contained by them" (292). The Simurg is a bird from the Persian book of kings, the *Shahnamah* by Firdausi (Warner and Warner 33). According to the story, the great bird discovers and nurtures into adulthood a child that had been abandoned by his father due to his unnaturally white hair. The father and son are eventually reunited, with the son coming into his rightful inheritance.

Historical names occur in abundance in this book, from a variety of time periods and cultures. Mr. O'Toole's middle name is Napoleon and he runs a tavern called the Elbaroom. A madam called Jocasta has managed the local "house of the rising sun." Mr. Jones has three initials, V. B. C., that stands for Virgil (Biblical), Beauvoir (Simone?), and Chanakya (ancient philosopher king). The narrator says about Virgil's name, "These were historical names, names to conjure with, and Mr.

Jones, though no conjurer, considered himself something of an historian” (*Grimus* 11).

Gribb, who like Flapping Eagle was a late arrival to Calf Island, tells about his experience:

When I arrived I found a certain number of unfortunate myths, which I have made it my business to expunge from the minds of the townspeople. It is incidentally an interesting corollary study to my work on race- memory: the growth of a mythology in a single, long-lived generation (163).

Rebirth lies at the very core of the concept of Calf Island. It is through their rebirth into immortality that the islanders live, through Grimus’s conceptualization or birth of imagination that Calf Island exists. It is through Flapping Eagle’s reconceptualization or mental rebirth that they ultimately cease to be. In many ways Flapping Eagle personifies rebirth. His formal Axona (Indian) name was Born-from-Dead because his mother had died moments before giving birth, and his common name Joe-Sue, describes his hermaphroditic state until sometime after his birth. He is reborn when he takes his name, Flapping Eagle, and again when he drinks the yellow elixir of eternal life. Grimus, his alter ego, seeks him out to become his son and heir to his kingdom. Grimus has devised a master plan similar to the Phoenix myth:

Through death the annihilation of self, the Phoenix passes its selfhood on to its successor. That is what I hope to do with you. Flapping Eagle. Named for the king of earthly birds. You are to be the next stage of the cycle, the next bearer of the flag, Hercules succeeding Atlas. In the midst of death we are in life. (293)

Much earlier in the text there is a hint of this idea “The town was called Phoenix because it had risen from the ashes of a great fire which had completely destroyed the

earlier and much larger city also called Phoenix” (10). Like the legendary bird and the town, Flapping Eagle is to rise from the flames and be reborn.

As mentioned before, *Grimus* allows Rushdie to introduce ideas that he pursues in his later books. The critic Parameswaran points out that “*Grimus* has several other characteristics in common with *Midnight's Children*, some of which are more fully developed and some vaguely present. Most important is the concept of a novel as propounded by Elfrida, one of the characters in *Grimus*” (37):

It's too pretty, too neat. I do not care for stories that are so, so tight. Stories should be like life, slightly frayed at the edges, full of loose ends and lives juxtaposed by accident rather than some grand design. Most of life has no meaning, so it must surely be a distortion of life to tell tales in which every single element is how terrible to have to see a meaning or a great import in everything around one, everything one does, everything that happens to one!
(*Grimus* 149)

Parameswaran points out that the narrator Saleem discusses the same idea in *Midnight's Children*. Saleem says “And there are as many stories to tell, too many, such an excess of intertwined lives events miracles places rumors, so dense a commingling of the improbable and mundane” (9)! He describes “this amoeba-like fission and fusion” as being “the distinguishing trait of the narrative voice or persona in both novels” (37). The metamorphoses of Flapping Eagle throughout the stages of male child, hermaphroditic Joe-Sue to a merged yet distinct being *Grimus* represents this fission/fusion aspect. In *Midnight's Children* two characters demonstrate this quality. Tai the storyteller represents the synthetic fusion of time-events; he is the repository of “racial memory.” Parameswaran writes, “Saleem represents this

compression of history as a less harmonious process. Under alternating fission-fusion, his individual identity is by turn fragmented and enlarged by the intertwined lives around him; he becomes the repository of a national memory” (Parameswaran 38).

There are many different spaces and times within *Grimus*. In the past, before journeying to Calf Island, there are two places for Flapping Eagle to live: on the tableau of the Axona, or on the outside. Calf Island, which exists in the past and perpetual present, is divided into three areas: the beach, K, and Grimus’s home. Other dimensions include the Gorf’s dimension of Thera, and also the distant past and locations described in Virgil’s diary.

Much of *Grimus* rests on the idea that another dimension exists, “Is it not a conceptual possibility that here, in our midst, permeating all of us, is a completely other world . . . with different perceptual tools which make us as non-existent to its inhabitants as they are to ours (*Grimus* 55). Time, too, exists simultaneously in different dimensions. Parameswaran writes:

Since there is always a Space-Time continuum in each world; the past, present and future coexist, and though ordinary human beings can move only in the present, there might be some, like inhabitants of Calf Island, who can move from one dimension to the other. (36)

Flapping Eagle’s background outside *Grimus* of Calf Island, and Virgil’s journal are the only true instances of the past in the novel. While the reader knows that the town of K has a past, all that is seen is a fixed state of the present, embodied in Cherkassov’s eternal pregnancy, “frozen within her as the lovers on the Grecian urn” (182). Virgil advises Flapping Eagle, “. . . Don’t worry about the past or the future” (*Grimus* 100). When Flapping Eagle arrives on the island, he causes something to

happen that never should have changed. Dolores fights the change by an insistence on her beliefs; “It is yesterday, she whispered. Every day is yesterday, so every day is fixed” (*Grimus* 60).

Rushdie’s exploration of time and space are connected to his views of history, for “an interpretation of history presupposes an approach to time and temporal sequences” (Pathak 216). Pathak quotes an article from T.S. Eliot’s selected prose in order to address the idea of historical sense:

The historical sense, T.S. Eliot remarks, “involves a perception, not only of the past, but of its presence”. This consciousness of history, he adds, is “a sense of the timeless as well as of the temporal and of the timeless and of the temporal together”, making a person genuinely “conscious of his place in time, of his own contemporaneity” (qtd. in Pathak 216).

Life on Calf Island, Saleem’s sojourn in the jungle, Sufiya’s trances and Gibreel’s dreams all involve a type of timelessness, and much of Rushdie’s literature seeks to distort chronology or any other kind of logical time. In *Grimus* Rushdie writes about “an infinity of continual, of possibilities both present and future, the free-play of time itself, bent and shaped into a zoo for your personal enjoyment” (252). History, narrative, obsession, and experimentation with time –these are just some of the ideas introduced in *Grimus*, Rushdie’s first novel, and developed in greater detail in his subsequent novels.

History as a Story in *Grimus*

Grimus is a historical fantasy and it presents an idea that historical narratives are not devoid of fictionality, rather they reciprocate each other, often dwelling together. History books don’t just reveal facts, rather, they often hide as much as they

reveal. As a reader it is our duty to expose such distortions and omissions. In this sense, Rushdie's *Grimus* attempts to expose this true nature of historical writings. *Grimus* propels an idea that individuals and human societies always seek new possible worlds to dwell upon and in this pursuit, we migrate from one place to another and we also create different worlds, if at least in imagination. We look for newness and work for newness. Rushdie's *Grimus* also explores this reality in depth.

Regarding the historicity of text and textuality of the history, Hans Bertens writes, "Literature is not simply a product of history, it also actively makes history" (177). Not only that, Bertens goes to the extent of saying that "historical texts are viewed as literary texts" (177). It becomes obvious that Rushdie also thinks in a similar fashion when he places his novels in historical events of the nation and creates alternative versions of them. This new treatment to history suggests that history is not just the recording of facts and figures but is also embedded with dynamic sociopolitical processes. History may have a purpose. Sometimes it may aspire to change societies, and at times it may aim to change people. It questions the idea that history is for the sake of history. It may have wider social implications. As readers, we need to understand this reality of history.

Rushdie has brought new concepts in novel writing tradition and in historiography. In this sense we may say that he has redefined the art of writing novels as well as the art of writing history. His works differ from others in the sense that they incorporate myth, religion, science, philosophy, historiography, and many more. The traditional understanding of linear narrative, unity of time, place and action all are questioned in Rushdie's novels in one way or the other. Realities are subverted and redefined. *Grimus* also does the same.

Art and history were taken as separate genre in the past. Aristotle was of the opinion that a historian could speak only about what has happened, whereas the poet could speak of what might happen. He had a notion that these two genres of writing are totally different. Contrary to what Aristotle believed, Linda Hutcheon writes:

The Postmodern novel has done the same, and the reverse. It is part of postmodernist stand to confront the paradoxes of fictive/historical representation, the particular/the general, and the present/ the past. And this confrontation is itself contradictory, for it refuses to recuperate or dissolve either side of dichotomy, yet it is more than willing to exploit both. (106)

With Hutcheon's above words, it becomes clear that Historiographic Metafiction first blurs the boundaries between the genres, history and fiction, and then uses them simultaneously but in a unique way. Rushdie's novels also follow the same ideals.

Narrative technique is a prominent element that plays a vital role in self-reflexivity in postmodern fiction. Circularity of narrative makes the story of a fiction clear and accessible to the readers. A number of theorists have defined different ways of narrating stories in fiction. In this connection, Mieke Bal explores the theory of narrative and defines a narrative text as "a story that is told in a medium, that is, it is converted into signs" (*Narratology* 8) and further posits narratology as the "theory of narratives, narrative texts, images, spectacles, events, cultural artifacts that tells a story" (1). It implies that the narrative system or principle employs certain elements of narrative such as actors, time, and location and so on to achieve the goal.

Rushdie draws heavily from Hutcheon's idea of historical metafiction. This Post-Modern technique supports the idea that the author battles against two tendencies –to draw fictional reality and to re-create a new world. Thus, the concept

of an alternative reality becomes more alluring since man is always in the attempt of creating and recreating realities. After all man is the maker of his reality, to a large extent.

Rushdie draws ideas for this novel from *The Conference of the Birds* by the Persian Poet Fariduddin al-Attar. Fariduddin is a twelfth century poet. In the poem, twenty-nine birds are persuaded by a hoopoe, a messenger of a bird god to make a pilgrimage to the god. The birds begin their pilgrimage. They all go through the valleys, rivers, and mountains. Finally, they arrive where god is supposed to live. To their dismay, they find no god there. More astonishing is the fact that they themselves have become gods instead. In this poem, we are forced to rethink about what we have been thinking for so long. We are asked to ask questions about our own faith and hopes.

Grimus supplies reader with a very crucial information in the beginning that Flapping Eagle, the central character, is exiled from Axona. It is his native place and it is the place where gods reside. He has been exiled because he broke the law of the land, by questioning the authority. He is thrown into an island called Calf Island.

Then after, Flapping Eagle goes in search of his lost sister as well as in search of a place where he will live for the rest of his life. Since he has already drunk an elixir, he is immortal. Not just immortal, Flapping Eagle would also remain young always. Being guided by Virgil Jones, a philosopher of history, he finally reaches to a magical place, a world devised by Grimus. In this magical land, no one dies. Flapping Eagle soon gets frustrated with this new magic land. He attempts to agitate the inhabitants of this place against the despotic leader Grimus.

He is bored by the same repetitive structures of this society as this society is

dictated completely by mind and rationality. Finally, he decides to resurrect the island without Stone Rose and to regain his human nature. He decides to return to his original place Axona but now he has become a different man with new learning and experiences. Now he has to question his own philosophy of life, like the birds in the Persian poet's book. This is also an instance of historical metafiction. History is therefore not unified but fragmented.

Rushdie's fictions, be it *Grimus* or *Midnight's Children*, displays a history of fragmentation. He depicts the reality in fragments, as if reflected in broken pieces of mirror. He argues:

The one thing you learn as an historian is just how fragmented and ambiguous and peculiar the historical record is. So, I thought, well, let's not try and pretend to be writing a history. Let's take the themes I am interested in and fantasize them and fabulate them . . . so that we don't have to get into the issue; . . . History does not have an absolute shape. No one can claim that history records complete knowledge. There are many histories within the general body of histories. From this general history there are several views that emerge and also many multiple selves. (qtd. in Smale 29)

Aron's argument strengthens the fact that no claim to absolutism in history is valid. All perspectives are open ended in nature. They are all parts of an unending discussion.

Rushdie uses myth and fantasy in *Grimus* in order to deconstruct monolithic worldview. He tries to open up avenues of incorporating imagination in the act of writing, be it fiction or history. The search is for truth but what the nature of truth is a puzzle.

Not just philosophers but also literary theorists, historians, and novelists are equally troubled by the question of truth. Some of them talk about truth with a capital “T” whereas some of them talk about truth with small “t.” In this context, these questions become prominent –What is truth? What does it mean by being credible? What distinguishes historical truth from the fictional truth? Rushdie also is equally troubled by these questions. For him it seems truth is an interpretation of the surroundings. He believes in the multitudinous aspects of truth.

Novelists deal with facts and figures with a certain liberty but historians play with them differently. The purpose that novelists have behind such maneuvering of facts may be different from the purpose historians may have under their sleeves. But both represent facts in their own ways. Rushdie as a historian and fiction writer is an ardent supporter of this philosophy of history and novel. For example, in *Grimus*, the protagonist at last realizes that what we think as true may not be true and vice versa. Virgil Jones, in *Grimus*, summarizes the basic tenets of a historian in this way:

If he had known, he would have philosophized at length about the parade of history, about the historian’s inability to stand apart and watch; it was erroneous, he would have said, to look upon oneself as an Olympian chronicler; one was a member of the parade. An historian is affected by the present events that eternally create the past. He would have thought this earnestly, although for some time now the parade had been progressing without his help. (*Grimus* 13)

Rushdie’s character Virgil clearly mentions that a historian is not just a recording machine. Mere facts do not make a book of history. Historians interpret facts and figures and make the events of history intelligible to readers. They can be compared

with teachers who explain the significance of raw data to their pupils. Comparing historians with poets Eric L. Berlatsky writes:

Historians, no less than poets, can be said to gain an explanatory affect over and above whatever formal explanations they may offer of specific historical events by building into their narrative patterns of meaning similar to those more explicitly provided by the literary art of the culture to which they belong. (314)

History moves forward linearly or it moves in spirals. Some say it moves in cycles. Whatever movement it has, historians need to make an attempt to capture it or at times recreate it. They capture it or recreate it through their imaginative powers as well. Historians interpret data and fill details where necessary. *Grimus* captures this very dimension of history and historicity. The characters here are on move. They are in search of a new history. This is why *Grimus* can be interpreted as an instance of alternative history.

Grimus does not negate past events rather it interrogates them. This very interrogation of past illuminates the true nature of history. It also becomes clear how novelists write novels and how historians write histories. After all both work with the data drawn from the society. However, Rushdie's characters often revolt against any dominant authorities. It is said that Rushdie also was against the notion of bending down in front of unjust authorities. He forwards a similar notion of history in *Grimus* and others.

When creative writers use fiction as a medium of expression in historical accounts, they may be able to allegorize and historiography. Just the way fictions are open to multiple interpretations; historical narratives also become a subject of

multiplicity. As readers we read history and interpret the text from our own point of view. Our interpretative strategies surely affect the way we understand historical narratives. Becker says, “the past is a kind of screen upon which we project our vision of the future” (34). It is almost like reading and decoding works of fiction. Our present undoubtedly affects our readings, be it history or fiction.

Regarding history, Vincent writes, “History is about the rich and famous, not the poor. History favors the articulate, not the silent . . . history is about assessing distortions, not copying out truths” (25). But Rushdie has an objection to this sort of history and historiography. In *Grimus* he makes it clear how our search for finality does not yield any result. Flapping Eagle’s dissatisfaction with the newly found land symbolizes this very fact.

Human subjectivity is inevitable to creep in the act of writing history as well as in the act of reading and interpreting history. History is a human construct so it inevitably contains human weaknesses and biases. Historians recreate the past that exists in their mind. Witnesses recreate the events that exist in their mind. *Grimus* also similarly recreates the past that exists in the mind. The past that *Grimus* represents is actually a recreated past. In this recreation, imagination plays a vital role. For example, Virgil Jones, in *Grimus*, says that a historian is a philosopher and a good reader of what has happened. He claims that historians also, knowingly or unknowingly, take sides. They are not only good observers but also good interpreters. They add meaning and values to what they write. They are such grounds where past and present interact. They have their own historicity and they deal with another history at the same time. In this act both affect each other and what they produce is after all a negotiation.

The epigraph Rushdie uses in *Grimus* is very meaningful. It is directly connected with the theme of the novel itself. Generally, writers use epigraphs in such a way that they capture the main idea of the text. *Grimus* suggests that like Flapping Eagle, the artist searches for freedom. Artists are always in search of better places and better ideas. This is also a fundamental human nature. Not only artists, but also an average man looks for newness, liberty, and joy. This is why *Grimus* is often interpreted as the history of man where its protagonist is persistently in search of new places, new histories, and new freedoms. This idea is implicit in the used epigraph.

Grimus breaks our notion of space and time as it takes us beyond that. Rushdie does so to suggest that past is not rigid, rather, it is a matter of perception and interpretation. *Grimus* shows that when historians use mythical narratives, these narratives get historicized. This act can also be understood simultaneously as history mythicized. In this sense, myth is an idealized form of historical truth.

Grimus places the mythical at such a place from where ideas of religion and spirituality can be scrutinized. The protagonist is placed in an imaginary location called Axona where our values and beliefs don't apply. Even our sense of time and place do not work there. This new secular kingdom of freedom questions our notions of nation and nationalism, god and heaven. This magical Calf Island symbolizes human desire for newness, change, and liberty.

This search of our protagonist is not just a search for a new place but also symbolically a search for a new history. This is also the quest of Rushdie himself. Rushdie's philosophy of history thus is that history is not monolithic. It should be free from the tyranny of single truth. Imagination and fantasy are inevitably a part of human heart so they are also a part of human history and their historiography. In so

doing Rushdie makes it clear how mythology can be a part of human history.

This Narrativized history, commingled with fact and fiction, is the thrust of the novel *Grimus*. This counter history tells us what history writing is and what possibilities does it contain. Since reality is a matter of perspective, what is real and what is imagined are almost impossible to know. They all are intertwined in historical narratives. Fictionality of history and historicity of text are the fundamental characteristics of historical writings

The characters in *Grimus* sooner or later realize that life should be understood in contradictions. Oppositional concepts such as reason and imagination, rationality and emotion, national and individual and so on make our living adventurous. Identity emerges out of the hodgepodge of these contradictions. Any kind of reductionism would necessarily negate many aspects of life and that sort of attempt would surely misrepresent the richness that human life entails. Any historiography that runs after rationality and absolutism excludes the voices of the margin, erases the important pages of history.

Regarding such gaps and fissures, Postcolonial historiography makes a strong case. It asks readers and writers to consider the marginalized voices that are ignored by the totalizing or mastering structures of narrative. It talks about finding alternative explanations of the stories other than what colonizers and national elites have prescribed. Rushdie, as a postcolonial thinker, resists colonialist historiography and posits his own unique model of history in *Grimus* and his other novels. His history of the nation differs from that of the colonialists in the sense that it uses narrative techniques, adding imaginative details where necessary, into otherwise historical archives.

The characters in *Grimus* problematize official historical claims. The dialogic approach used in *Grimus* provides a ground for an alternative historical reality. These alternative accounts destabilize any claims for authenticity and totality. The fragmentary life stories that each characters of the novel tell demand for a more democratic view of history, the history that is more inclusive and comprehensive. *Grimus* projects these pluralistic worlds mediated by fantasy. In this history-seeking novel, the central character, Flapping Eagle, seeks the truth of life, knowledge and new possible histories. Rushdie writes, “There are a million possible Earths with a million possible histories, all of which actually exist simultaneously” (*Grimus*53). In the novel, there are immortal figures who escape the oppression of the centralized system in Axona in order to re-create their own imaginary reality, the reality that is full of magic and supernatural elements.

In order to display an alternative method of societal organization and narrative construction, Rushdie uses fantasy, myth, and magical narratives. Purposefully, Rushdie uses magical realism as a tool to subvert the master narratives of the West. How authoritative was Axona is revealed when Virgil Jones says, “Language makes concepts. Concepts make chains. I am bound” (15). Historians must fight against this linguistic determinism in order to be able to see things in a new light. It becomes more apparent when Flapping Eagle, in the middle of the act of love making, says, “A single word, changing the course of history” (173). History is an interpretation and it depends on the perspective of the interpreter.

In *Grimus* every character is obsessed with the idea of his/her metamorphosis. This obsession is what drives these characters to their journey. The characters are moving, and they are propelled by the quest for a new world. For instance, the central

character, Flapping Eagle, breaks the routine of Axona and sets out in search of a new home, a home of vitality and communication.

The treatment of history in the novel questions the hegemonic traits of colonialist historiography. Flapping Eagle as a symbol of freedom represents hybridity, multiplicity and indeterminacy. He is the one who brings together all the contradictory aspects of life. If we take him as an embodiment of history, he symbolizes the dynamic nature of history itself. The narrator in *Grimus* says, “several times he changed the name he gave to people. His face was such, his skin was such” (32). Since everything is subject to reevaluation and interpretation, everything is bound to change. Metamorphosis is an inevitable trait of life. In this sense, *Grimus* is a story of a man’s identity and his journey through history.

Grimus represents two kinds of realities: materialistic and fictional. On the one hand there are hard facts of life and on the other hand there are human fantasies. Human fantasies also do have very important roles in our lives. They enrich our lives with colors or textures and make it worth living. *Grimus* also adopts the idea of literary recreation that gives readers new world and new hope.

In search of a better place, Flapping Eagle wanders here and there. He experiences many ups and downs in life. First, he goes through the tormenting life of Axona. Then he comes to the Calf Island, a monotonous place to live in. In this new place ruled by a magician, he sees new systems. Soon after he starts to think about an alternative place where he could be happy. Looking at things from multiple perspectives, he becomes a good educator and finally says, “I want to return to the human race” (*Grimus* 55). It means Rushdie in *Grimus* is asking readers to look at history from multiple perspectives and not remain satisfied with one single

interpretation. In this sense one may argue, *Grimus* is all about discovering truths through experiences.

In this novel Flapping Eagle, his sister and the other eternal birds are introduced as anti-historical figures since they are against the traditional notion of history and historiography. They are dynamic, and are always on the move. Each character in *Grimus* represents a particular view of life. Joe Kuortti claims, “The major problem of Flapping Eagle is that he is burdened with history. He is under the pressure of collective thoughts. He is destined to be destroyed by the forces of history” (65). Likewise, the forces of history affect all other characters in the novel.

Differences are often silenced by oppressive systems. Flapping Eagle had to exile himself from Axona because he refused to follow the rules and regulations of the dictator of Axona. Conformity was what he very much disliked. The supremo of Axona prescribed two laws – “the people of Axona had to chant his name as often as possible, and he instructed the inhabitants of Axona to be a race apart and have no doings with the wicked world” (*Grimus* 16). It was the system the ruler of Axona imposed upon its inhabitants. This centralized system does not accept differences. So Rushdie criticizes monolithic view of history.

The Rushdian version of narrative history does not claim to be an objective representation because he does not believe in this possibility. He denounces absolutism of historical truth. *Grimus* resists any totalizing narrative discourse. Being a blend of fact, fiction, and fantasy, the story hints that individuals exist simultaneously in different worlds at the same time, worlds outside and the worlds inside their brains. *Grimus* thus does not believe in transparent reality.

History as Magic and Fantasy in *Grimus*

Grimus represents reality but in a magical way. As a novel with fantasy at its heart, *Grimus* is a work of magic. Rushdie carries out his particular interest in magic to new heights in his subsequent novels too.

The title of the novel *Grimus* itself is a product of fantasy. It is in fact an anagrammatism of the word “Simurg”. It is a monstrous bird in Persian mythology that has the power of speech as well as a thinking brain. Rushdie in this way sets the tone to this entire magical novel by coining the title *Grimus*. It foreshadows that the novel has fantasy at its heart. But Rushdie does not just play with fantasy to please readers; rather, he tells history from this new mode of presenting reality.

Through fantasy Rushdie portrays a marvelous but queer world of magic in *Grimus* that enchants readers and makes them wonder for long. It is a convoluted fable about the human condition. *Grimus* posits a different worldview, a new possibility. It places the real against the magical, plausible against implausible. Rushdie points out that *Grimus* is, primarily a brilliant statement about the human condition in the repressive and prescriptive societies such as the Axona, the Phoenix and the town of K. Using the fantastic mode of story telling, Rushdie forwards themes such as the quest for identity, the quest for self-realization and the search for home.

Axona, the imagined place of the novel, is dystopian, ignorant, and conservative. It has its own prescriptive codes, superstitious values, and forbidden taboos. Its dwellers fear god and they follow the law of the land without questioning. Their god is very cruel and whimsical who makes them chant his name almost all the time, even while making love or eating food. This world at a subtle level reflects many nations that are run by cruel despots. In this sense this novel reflects the real

world we live in though it looks like an imaginary world with the help of fantasy as a mode of historical representation.

People like Flapping Eagle and Bird Dog may represent those segments of societies where rational beings live. They are the supporters of human freedom. Rushdie is also a vehement supporter of human freedom. His own desire for the just world may have been reflected in the novel in a very metaphorical way.

As the story tells us, the members of Axona follow rituals deeply and they all wanted to please the supernatural power, the quest vision. To be brave, they have to have blessings of god. Flapping Eagle undergoes the same process and aspires to please the quest vision. Though initially he denied this ritual for he was considered a pariah, an outcast. In this kind of restrictive and oppressive societies, one must resort to fantasy. This is the message Rushdie gives through the novel. So, this novel is not just a fantasy but it is also a meta-fantasy. Through fantasy, Flapping Eagle indulges in the “Quest-vision” and breaks the taboos of his repressive state. His journey from one place to another reveals the truth that he is in search of freedom and also identity. His story is also a story of victimization.

The world that Bird Dog often visits is known as the “outside world,” a world of strange things. This world is very prosperous and it symbolizes the western world itself. It is the world led by capitalism. People who inhabit this world have despair in their eyes though they have tremendous material comfort.

In Axona, Flapping Eagle is considered a hero. He has already acquired an identity. He finds Livia here with whom he has sex. No one can make fun of him in this world. Despite all these things, Flapping Eagle is soon bored in Axona too. His love for this place, as he realizes later on, is just his lust for Livia. Fortunately, he

inherits all of her wealth after her death and sets out to a new world with the newly acquired property. Flapping Eagle goes on in search of another world because of his dissatisfaction with what he has. He goes on in search of a new place, crossing rivers and seas.

Axona does not satisfy our protagonist because it was a closed society. Since he is blessed with immortality, he continuously searches for newness and new identity. But this immortality itself becomes a curse for Flapping Eagle for he does not find any place where he can satisfy himself. His search itself becomes a burden to him. He cannot accept the worlds that he encounters for they all are in a way ruled by despots.

Literally we cannot move from one world to another. This is why Rushdie resorts to magic or fantasy. Fantasy makes it possible to image new world and new order. Flapping Eagle finally reaches the town of K. It is an ideal world, a heaven. But it also has its own problems. Flapping Eagle says:

In a sense it was utopian, but how on earth had it become workable? The Cherkassoras were still aristocrats and Gribb was still Grib. Only in the matter of social organization did 'K' display these out-of-place fellow feelings; for the rest of it was a place divided into small groups, even of isolated individuals, with few of the festivities and group activities usually associated with tightly knit communities. (20)

In fact, this new place was in the grip of Grimus. He was a despot here. Peoples' differences collapsed here because they were taught in such a way that they all forgot everything else. People like Flapping Eagle came here in search of newness but they all got trapped. And the life here was monotonous.

Unlike other Utopian literature, the town of K is devised to highlight the plight of the victims like Flapping Eagle and the inhabitants of K. Rushdie probably wants to say that no land is perfect but it is human nature to search for a better place. The best thing that human beings can have is the land devoid of tyrants.

The novel represents three modes of human existence. Axona represents a totalitarian society where people must obey the unwise rules and regulations. Calf Island symbolizes an all-powerful, super human life. The third mode of human existence represented by the novel is that of simple human beings. At last Flapping Eagle represents this mode of human society. Flapping Eagle refuses superhuman and sub human modes of existence and at last wishes to go back to his own place, a place of ordinary human beings, full of weaknesses but still interesting to live in. Finally, Flapping Eagle's last wish to exist as an ordinary human being gives him a new identity.

Rushdie's imagination creates alternative worlds such as K and Phoenix. These new places are not just alternative worlds but also alternative models, alternative models of human societies and existence. Rushdie gives no specific and actual geographical location in *Grimus* in order to create his outlandish worlds and this very outlandishness highlights the possibility that possibilities exist. In order to communicate this sort of outlandishness, Rushdie chooses the magical mode of representation. In this sense, *Grimus* is a magical history of humanity and it also offers a new mode of historiography, i.e., history as fantasy.

In *Grimus*, Rushdie transgresses the rules of conventional historiography by exploring new possibilities through magic or fantasy. Rushdie's strange way of storytelling, i.e., telling the story through an imagined character who can tell us even

the stories of his past life proposes a new mode of storytelling. Our narrator of the story is about eight hundred years old. What a historian we have in *Grimus*! With this strange precondition, Rushdie sets a tone for his fantasy, a fantasy that is of course more than fantasy. Through fantasy, Rushdie creates these strange characters, the characters that are constantly changing. Almost like surrealists, Rushdie creates and develops them in the novel. This fantastic mode of storytelling provides Rushdie a ground to explore human condition, especially in repressive societies. Flapping Eagle assumes different identities in order to delve deeper into human psyche to understand them better. Rushdie here through magic analyzes the miserable condition of human beings in the autocratic society through the various fantastic figures and forms.

But what appears to be departure from the reality of the primary world consists of the reality of the alternative world that is portrayed through fantasy. Grimus, who is always surrounded by beings that are akin to mummified figures, is the masterstroke of this fantasy. Grimus's character is developed out of Flapping Eagle's consciousness. Most fanciful figures in the novel are Gorfs who live on the planet lit by Nus. They do not need food, water, or atmosphere. Such fanciful figures create a sense of wonder and hesitation in the minds of readers. The novel is a veritable mix of fact and fiction.

The setting of the novel is very strange. Like most of fantasy fiction, the functional units of the primary world are substituted with new phraseology. For example, "water crystal" in *Grimus* has been used as a substitute for T.V., whereas "Ion Eye" is a substitute for an advanced version of both a computer technology and palmistry. The "Stone Rose" is a combination of various things and it is the source of

power.

The novelist who wants to deal with the human condition in repressive societies must create a new language that adequately depicts the reality. Rushdie is preoccupied with reality. He has, therefore, coined an entirely new language, which is essential for his fanciful figures operating in the marvelous worlds. The fantastic language is, in a sense, not an invented but a distorted language. The linguistic manipulation is mostly confined to anagrammatism. The title of the novel *Grimus*, the words like “Grof,” “Nus”, “Yawykilm” “Thear” and “Nirvesu” and “Dota” are anagrams that are created using inversion method. Such devices of linguistic manipulation help to transgress the usual ground rules of the mimetic writing and to set up a new premise of magical writing.

It is fantasy which elevates *Grimus* from topicality to universality and makes it a story of all those who share Joe-Sue’s existence in the repressive society and delivers an account of the human condition. *Grimus*, thus, represents the beginning of a concept of literature as an orchestration of voices in which fact and fantasy are blended artistically.

History as Lies and Gossip in *Grimus*

Grimus, though taken as a science fiction by a large number of readers and critics, also forwards an argument that history is not and cannot be totally objective. History may contain lies and gossips as well. Historians are manipulative by nature. They deliberately manipulate the available data in order to meet their ends. They also insert lies and gossips into their historical narratives unwillingly or unknowingly. Sometimes their informants may pass such inauthentic information to them or at

times historical archives may contain lies and distortions. Rushdie's argument is clear in *Grimus* that history contains some amount of lies and gossip.

We may read *Grimus* as an allegory of modern man who is highly technologized and knows how to territorialize and de-territorialize societies and common knowledge. Rushdie himself was a victim of blurred territories and identities. Just like the character Flapping Eagle, Rushdie is an expatriate. He is a Pakistani, an Indian, and an Englishman at the same time. He calls himself an international citizen. He is also constantly in search of his own identity. He performs this search primarily through his writings. He is also moving from one place to another in his real life just like the character Flapping Eagle. This is why Rushdie does not fix *Grimus* to any particular location. We don't know what place he is talking about in *Grimus*. Behind this, he has a purpose. In fact, we all have this blurred territory and identity in this cosmopolitan era.

Indeed, *Grimus* is also a novel about history. It begins with a character named Virgil Jones. Jones is a solitary man. We find him in the beginning of the novel sitting in his rocking chair on a small beach nearby the Mediterranean Sea. He considers himself a great historian. Virgil Jones stands for an aspect of historiography in the novel.

Grimus gives us some information about Indian cultures and history as well. It also explores some of the Eastern and Western mythologies. It is a tall tale that includes creatures like "Gorfs" and "Flapping Eagle." Flapping Eagle drinks an elixir and becomes immortal. Then after he moves from one place to another for years. Thus, he becomes a living history, living for thousands of years. Flapping Eagle also represents an aspect of historiography in the novel.

If we closely observe Flapping Eagle, we will come to know that he is a highly adaptable man, almost like a chameleon. He sees things that ordinary people fail to notice. However, this living history says, "I want to grow old. Not to die; to grow old" (33). Through Flapping Eagle, Rushdie highlights the limitations of historians. Even if they are immortal, they do not comprehend all of the social events. They may misunderstand many things and events and communicate their mistaken views to their readers.

As Flapping Eagle tries to enter into the mystical world of Calf Island, he undergoes the Grimus effect. His consciousness almost breaks away. He goes through some sort of hallucinations, which are just Rushdian strategies to suggest the profound truth that there may exist many dimensions of knowledge. General people think that knowledge is one-dimensional. They often believe that truth is "one" and graspable. But Rushdie hints towards the possibility of multiple worlds and multiple dimensions. Once we try to enter into a new dimension, our previous framework may not work properly. Some may even go crazy. This idea can be easily related to the idea of history as well. Rushdie conceives history as multidimensional. If historians change the framework or the working procedures, they would come to understand the same events differently. So what history books write may not be absolutely correct. They may be also a kind of lies or distortions. In this regard, one can say that history is only a matter of perspective. In this light, any historian's claim to be an objective historian is a blatant lie. They propagate greater lies in the name of objective history.

Flapping Eagle's entry into this utopian town named K does not satisfy his soul. K is a wonderful place. The count is the titular head of this town. He is god here. This is a kind of perfect egalitarian society where people get what they want. But all

of its inhabitants here are obsessed with some idea. They are crazy over certain ideas. This obsession helps them to overcome the Grimus Effect, or dimension fever. This is a utopia that everybody desires to achieve but Flapping Eagle ultimately decides to quit this place too. He sees no variations here. The monolithic truth bores him. Everything is calculative and predictable in this town. In the name of homogeneity, plurality has been suppressed here. This is a kind of despotic country run by a powerful demigod Grimus. Rushdie's hero decides to quit this world.

It means Rushdie denies the idea of a single truth. Rushdie is against any so-called gods. He believes that monolithic history and its historians try to kill the multiple possibilities that exist in everything. They close their eyes to the richness that exists in the world. It would be just like shutting our eyes to the thousand splendid suns, by pointing towards a dim tiny star. These traditional historians in Rushdie's view try to cover the richness of the past, and this is what makes them outliers. If they had the courage to say that history is a many-headed hydra, which contains fact, fiction, magic, gossip, they would have been at least more honest. Rushdie through *Grimus* exposes the lies that traditional historians have been trying to hide from their readers.

In one episode of the novel, we find Flapping Eagle going towards a mountain. It was a very difficult journey but he finally reaches on the top with the help of a self-proclaimed historian Virgil Jones as in Dante's *Divine Comedy*. There, Flapping Eagle finds Grimus and his heavenly kingdom. But to his surprise, Flapping Eagle finds Grimus so much like himself. In fact Flapping Eagle finds Grimus to be his own alter ego. Readily Grimus accepts Flapping Eagle as his son and decides to handover all of his resources. Flapping Eagle then realizes that he had been

wandering here and there in the world for so many years but he had to reach this place, had to meet Grimus, and so on. Everything was already destined. He had been doing nothing but living somebody's plan. This realization of Flapping Eagle symbolizes one variant of historiography. These historians claim that history just unfolds God's plans. Historians do nothing; just try to understand God's motives. Flapping Eagle's rejection of the world of *Grimus* suggests that Rushdie also has objection to this model of history as well. These historians also pretend to be a kind of demigod who can read god's intentions.

What Rushdie is trying to say in *Grimus* is that there are many scholars who promise to give us the illusory paradise. The promise of God in the novel is just like the promise that many historians make to give their readers an authentic knowledge of the past, the present, and the future. Students of history must be aware of these traps. Any reader should be aware of this fact that historical narratives do contain some amount of lies and gossip. We must be very careful at the time of reading and interpreting history. Gods are liars and Paradise is, in a sense, a gossip.

For example, Flapping Eagle's decision, at last, to choose the essential natural condition of being a human who grows, ages, and dies symbolizes Rushdie's view of history and historians. Rushdie wants historians to be realistic and honest. Even if they tell lies, they must do it with honesty. In *Midnight's Children*, Rushdie makes this narrator tell a wrong date of Mahatma Gandhi's assassination. He makes his narrator to give us a lie about who wrote the Ramayana and why the Mumbadevi day is celebrated in India. It is not that Rushdie does not know these facts. He just wants his readers to be aware that such manipulations may come in any history books. He

tells us history, through his novels, so that readers would understand the relationship between history and novel. In this regard, William Walsh writes,

Combining the elements of magic and fantasy, the grimmest realism, extravagant farce, multi-mirrored analogy, and a potent symbolic structure; Rushdie has captured the astonishing energy of novel, unprecedented in scope, manner and achievement in the hundred and fifty years old tradition of the Indian novel in English. (86)

Walsh has understood *Grimus* as a novel that uses extravagant style to present down to earth realities of our everyday lives. Rushdie in *Imaginary Homelands* clarifies his position as a historian:

Writers in my position, exiles and emigrants or expatriates are haunted by an urge to look back even at the risk of being mutated into pillars of salt. But if we do look back, we do so, in the knowledge which gives rise to profound uncertainties that our physical alienation from India almost inevitably means that we will, in short, create fictions, not actual cities or villages, but invisible ones, imaginary homelands, Indias of minds. (102)

Any historian attempting to recreate the past may meet the above-mentioned hurdles. They would all create a version of the past and their versions would also contain fragments of truths, just like other versions. Their narratives would contain some truths and some lies. In *Midnight's Children*, the protagonist who calls himself a historian accepts, "Think of this: history in my version, entered a new phase on august 15th, 1947 but in another version, that inescapable date is no more than one fleeting instant in the age of darkness, Kaliyuga" (194).

Rushdie thus forwards a notion that history manifests itself in multiple forms. It does not have one face but many. One of its faces is lies and gossip. Some historical documents may include as less lies as they can, some may welcome as many lies as they want. Sanjay Suri comments over Rushdie's novels, especially *Midnight's Children*, as, "It is a history of India, Bangladesh, and Pakistan, but not history either. It is fiction, but closer to truth than many works of history might be. It is also a soap and opera. And it is also a story of . . . man" (3). For Rushdie, history and fiction are brothers and they have so many commonalities. They don't even survive alone. Thus, Rushdie (re) visions history in all its colors and nuances. He combines the ideas about history of various schools of historiography and blends them well. While doing so he formulates his own unique notion of history and literature. Rushdie can be a good model to any historian or any novelist.

Through the character of Virgil Jones, Rushdie's *Grimus* posits a fact that a historian can never be a neutral Olympian chronicler. Historians must participate in the parade of history. They must take part in the events that they describe. This is how history inevitably acquires lies and gossip in its accounts.

Rushdie succeeds in giving his readers an idea that historical representation can be actuated through various modes –factual mode, narrative mode, magical mode, or gossip mode. This is why some readers have read Rushdie's texts as novels where as some have read them as books of history. Some consider Rushdie a historian whereas some consider him a novelist. There are some readers who love calling Rushdie even a conjurer, a fabulist. Rushdie has also manifested himself in various forms, just the way he has manifested history in its various forms. He is a creator as well as a destroyer. He destroys the traditional notion of history and historiography

and creates a new historiography. To conclude, Rushdie's texts, including *Grimus*, can be interpreted as a modern fairy tale that defies the official versions of truths and attempts to draw a better map of reality.

Chapter VII

Rushdian Historical Prism

Salman Rushdie has been exploring, as well as exploding, the philosophy of history through his novels since long. Salman Rushdie had developed a keen sense of history as well as a new kind of scholarship in it when he was a student in Oxford University. Each of his major novels deals with the past, directly or indirectly and in many of his major novels historiography comes in the front, as the central motif. Salman Rushdie's notion of historiography is unique in the sense that it has been affected by the historiography of the East as well as the West. Not only that, his novel also exhibit a strong influence of postmodern and postcolonial theories. He seems to be always concerned with giving voice to the voiceless. For this purpose, his writings often subvert the mainstream writing trends, highlighting new possibilities. Rushdie posits four modes of history – history as chronicle, history as story, history as myth/magic, and history as lies and gossip. This dissertation forwards an argument that Rushdie, through his major novels, attempts to explicate his new notions of history, i.e., history as chutney, a mixture of many things.

In his novels, Rushdie fictionalizes history or let us say historicizes fiction in order to comprehend them better. He does it mainly by collapsing the boundary between fact and fiction. In order to do so, Rushdie uses many techniques such as the use of unreliable narrator, exaggeration, falsification of established notions by altering them, inserting subjective elements and making the readers aware of the impossibility of writing history objectively. Truly, Rushdie has envisioned history in its various forms. He has brought history and fiction together very cleverly in order to illustrate their relationships. He not only questions the monolithic view of history but

also gives a new model for historians and novelists to write history and novels.

Rushdie, through his novels, forces his readers to rethink about our understanding of the past. He indicates that most of the things that affect our lives take place in our absence. In this condition, we can never grasp our own life in totality. How can we understand the past as it really took place? These questions become very prominent in Rushdie's writings.

The first chapter of this dissertation is an introduction of Rushdie and his major works, in alignment with the ideas of history and its representations. This chapter serves the purpose of creating a background to delve deeper into Rushdie's world of literary creations. It does not just give a brief glimpse of the entire research work, but also discusses how Rushdie has tried to intervene the discourse of historiography with his own unique formulations of the notions of history and fiction. The first part of this chapter deals with the biographical details whereas the second part introduces various elements of the proposal such as hypothesis, objective of the study, scope of the study, implications of the study, literature review, delimitations, and so on.

The second chapter concentrates on the idea of representation itself. The first part of the chapter brings together the ideas of various critics and scholars since Plato to Post Modernism in order to conceptualize writing as an art of representation. In the second part of this chapter, historiography is introduced as a major mode of representation. It not only explores how history can be a mode of representation, but also presents a broad framework in order to interpret Rushdie's texts as historical documents.

The next chapter is a bit different in nature and its purpose for it attempts to postulate a syncretic model of history that would accommodate the major ideas of Rushdie on history and historiography. This new approach to viewing history has been developed by blending the ideas of some of the major schools of historiography. This chapter identifies four possibilities of history, being represented in Rushdian writings as: history as facts and figures, history as narratives, history as myth/magic, and history as lies/gossip. The major purpose of this chapter is to develop a syncretic method of viewing history that will fit into the Rushdian corpus of writings. Since Rushdie considers both novels and history as narratives, this chapter identifies four main colors of history in Rushdie's writings.

Chapter four, five, and six explore Rushdie's three prominent texts, *Grimus*, *Midnight's Children*, and *The Enchantress of Florence*, as the major basis in order to elucidate the theoretical approach developed in chapter three. This dissertation only concentrates on these three texts by Salman Rushdie in order to build a solid argument on the interface and mixing of history and fiction. This chapter shows how Rushdie gives a very comprehensive or accommodating definition of history as the sum total of fact, story, myth/magic, and gossip/lies.

The concluding chapter, chapter seven, attempts to summarize and synthesize the major ideas of this research work. It winds up with an argument that Rushdie envisions, history as well as novels, as the sum total of fact, story, myth/magic, and gossip/lies.

Historiography, as a mode of representation, uses various tools and techniques to represent reality. There is no consensus among historians over the methodologies to recover what has been already lost. Different schools of historiography have

attempted to define the issue of representation differently. Rushdie, as a postcolonial and postmodern writer, looks at the issues of representation from a very unique position. He has developed his own methodology of history and fiction in order to refute the Western hegemonic tradition of representing the non-west. In this sense, Rushdie's realism is a kind of counter realism. His way of representing history is a kind of alternative modality.

In Rushdie's understanding of history, individuals matter the most. History of any place can't be understood only in terms of its nation and cities. In fact, history has to be understood in relation to the people and their private lives. Eurocentric historiography focuses only on the public sphere. But domestic space is also equally, or even more, important to understand people and societies. Rushdie, as a postcolonial writer, attempts to explore this domestic space in his writings. In this regard, Rushdie's historiography has a wider frame, compared to the western historiographical tradition. For example, in *Midnight's Children*, Rushdie explores and represents Indian struggle before and after Independence through a character called Saleem Sinai. In fact, Saleem Sinai is a nobody in the mainstream history books of India. But in Rushdie's version, the fate of India is intertwined with the fate of Saleem. His personal stories are interwoven into the historical fabric of the nation. Thus, Rushdie envisions a new kind of history in *Midnight's Children*. Not only that Rushdie also injects magic into his narratives. Western historiography does not so easily accept magic as a part of history but, for Rushdie and even for the Eastern part of the world, it is. If people believe so much in such things, how can it be not a part of history? Rushdie uses magic also purposefully in order to subvert western traditions of representations. He wants to give colonizers a message that his people and his

country are not exactly what they have imagined. Because Rushdie starts with such premises, his writings certainly fall into the category of counter realism.

Moreover, Rushdie is not just a novelist, but also an accomplished historian. He does not just craft stories, but also designs history. In this regard, Rushdie is a fabricator, someone who plays with fact and fiction. For Rushdie, history contains fiction and fiction contains history. History and fiction are two fundamental colors of all writings. The question is not whether they contain fact and fiction, but to what proportions do the two intermingle and affect one another. For example, when a nationalist historian writes a history book with the statements like –‘my country, my people, and my pride’ –to what extent should we believe him/her? Undoubtedly s/he is swamped into the bogus War-saga. This is how historians fabricate. Rushdie is against such fabrications of history as the presentation of reality.

Another key element in Rushdian writings is memory. Memory plays an important role in Rushdie’s novels, for example, Saleem, the protagonist of *Midnight’s Children*, alters many factual data in the novel, sometimes deliberately and sometimes unknowingly. He forgets the date Gandhi was shot at and he also forgets the date of the election and contradicts them with his own timeframe. At times, he is aware of his errors and at times he is not. Despite the errors that he has made, he believes that his historical narrative will not be less true than any other historical accounts. He makes many errors because the history that he is trying to write has to grapple with his shortcomings. Since historians are also human beings, they have their own strengths and weaknesses. They can’t just escape human biases and shortcomings. They don’t have all historical data in their mind all the time. What they write will also be affected by their memory. That is why Rushdie calls history a

matter of memory. Just like other kinds of writings, historical truth also depends on perspectives. Memory creates its own truths and so do narratives.

Moreover, Rushdie has been living abroad since long. He has a strong memory of his homeland but his physical association with his native place is minimum. Yet, as a writer of diaspora, he often tries to capture his homeland as far as possible. Unlike other writers, he boldly asserts that his India or his Pakistan is just a version that exists in his mind. Due to a kind of homesickness, he often engages himself with the homeland with the hope that he would be able to reestablish links with his ancestors and home. His historical narratives are of course a kind of fiction because the content of his narratives is as much invented as found. But these historical accounts are of course not less trustworthy. Other historians also use memory as a tool to recreate the past. They also may be misled by their memory. Mostly they hide their weaknesses, and speak as if they are certain of what they write. But Rushdie does not do so. He tells us the secrets of writing history and fiction without trying to mask the fallibility of both these genres. This makes Rushdian versions of history, not less trustworthy, but in fact more acceptable.

In this sense, Rushdie, as a postmodern and postcolonial author, provides us with a de-totalizing view of history. His writings subvert the traditional definitions of history and fiction in order to open up the possibilities for multiple histories. He is against any kind of closures or dictatorships. Western Imperialistic model of history tries to give an overarching view of the past. Unlike them, Rushdie proposes multiplicity and plurality. He supports the idea of multiple stories or mini narratives.

One may even call Rushdian historiography an indigenous model of writing history. The Indian subcontinent has been practicing the oral tradition since long.

Writing and recording are the recent developments in this part of the world. Most of the ancient texts have been preserved in India orally. When someone tries to transfer the historical knowledge from one generation to another generation, they will often turn the historical information into beautiful stories with interesting plots. This is why history often comes to Indians as stories. Rushdie gets insights from these traditions and uses them to develop his own model of history. For example, in *Midnight's Children*, the narrator Saleem makes an error over who wrote the Mahabharata. He makes this error with purpose. Since the Indian tradition is primarily an oral tradition, what we listen from others may be wrong at times. The same things later on may become a part of our narratives and may even pass as true histories.

Because no human beings can grasp all of the reality, Rushdie asks us to embrace reality in multiple frames. If we use just one tool to capture this giant that we call history, we are doomed to fail. History is a multi-headed hydra. Due to this reason, historical truth is always deferred. It is because it has multiple appearances, we are always surrounded by multiple versions of the past. We are bombarded with multiple versions of the past also because history always comes to us mediated and it carries the historians' limitations and biases as well. Since subjectivity plays a vital role in historical writings, historians will certainly express their own point of view while writing about any historical event. For example, a historian writing in 18th century India would be different from a historian writing in 20th century India. The social contexts of the historians change their stories. Every historian is biased and prejudiced in some ways, and every historian is ignorant of at least some of the facts. The only way to avoid biases and prejudices may be to simply list facts, figures, and events without making any kind of commentary or conclusions no matter how

apparent they may appear. But this isn't history at all. It needs interpretations and individual interpretations vary. Therefore, history is, and always will be subjective. Since history can't escape perspectives and human biases, historical events always are viewed from one's own self-referential criteria and thus what one historian records may not be what another records, especially if the historians are from different cultures and contexts. Traditional historians try to be objective, but few can help describing events devoid of their own cultural biases. Our perspective influences not only our view of history but also subtly influences our view of many other matters.

Rushdie believes that human beings are connected to their histories. What is personal and what is national often can't be distinctly separated. We are influenced by history and history is also shaped by the ideology or the politics of the era. Rather than an absolute version of history, Rushdie endorses the idea of multiple histories. The individual nature of history suggests that there can be as many versions of history as many people there are. For example, Saleem Sinai, the narrator in *Midnight's Children*, thinks that the most important events that took place in India history coincide with equally important events in his own family. That is why Saleem believes that he had been mysteriously handcuffed to history. In this sense, the stories that Saleem narrates in *Midnight's Children* are in a sense his own stories. When national and personal get blurred in *Midnight's Children*, a new reality or an alternative reality comes forth. Salman Rushdie fictionalizes the history of India in *Midnight's Children* not just for shallow experimentation. He inserts fictional elements in his historical accounts in order to propose a new model of history. In this sense, fiction can be more real than a supposedly true fact. The way Rushdie views history and the way many other historians view history is very much different.

Rushdie has been influenced by New Historicist's notion of history and he also carries Post-colonial agenda in most of his writings.

Often the historical accounts prepared by government officials claim to be the absolute truths. Many historians before Rushdie wrote history of Indian subcontinent using the parameters developed by the colonialist historians before the 19th century. Colonizers had created a discourse of their own which was especially tailored for their own interest. Such historical documents make a false claim that they present events exactly as the events took place. Rushdie is not ready to accept such naive explanations because he believes that truth differs according to who said it and why and to whom. By developing a new modality of history writing, Salman Rushdie challenges the basic assumptions of colonialist historiography and its validity.

Rushdie, a widely read man, knows the theories of history and its philosophy. He has formulated his philosophy of history in connection with the theories like Marxism, Post Colonialism, and Post Modernism. He in fact bears a little bit of all these identities. He gives his characters differing views and opinions in order to provide his basic premises on history and fiction. He listens patiently to the arguments forwarded by different schools of history and historiography, but he has his own unique understanding of them. Against the backdrop of these various theories, he has developed his own comprehensive definition of history and fiction. For example, in *The Enchantress of Florence*, Rushdie takes his readers into a magical world. But this world is also a kind of reality, that had been hiding somewhere in the margins of official history. Rushdie just dug it out and presented to the readers. Rushdie has drawn many characters of this novel from books of history such as King Akbar, Uzbek Khan, Machiavelli, and so on. Even minor details of

Renaissance Italy and Mughal India contain researched information. They are not totally imaginative. He has done a lot of research, as he himself has made it clear that it is his most researched book so far. He has drawn a lot of ideas from official records. But of course he has manipulated them adroitly.

Rushdie uses fantasy and magic in his novels to criticize the notion of realities and history. Using fantasy as a technique of representation, Rushdie forces his readers to rethink about their understanding of existing world and our past. In his novels, the real often hides behind the fabric of fiction. His novels often place nation's politics at the center in order to explicate how all these complex arrays of political forces affect an individual. Rushdie strongly believes that it is through individuals that we should try to know the history of the nation. This is why most of his novels tell us personal history as well as the history of the nation. Since history oozes out of individuals' stories, history inevitably acquires personal biases and prejudices. In this sense, history is what an individual makes out of what he/she observes in the national orchestra. The same events may be interpreted and depicted differently by different persons. There is no unanimous version of any past event. There are only versions of the past. Versions are there because past gets reflected in many forms. Those historians who use multiple tools to recreate the past may be able to capture more reality in comparison to those who use only one or very limited methodology.

Rushdie is in favor of using multiple tools and techniques in the act of writing about the past. In *Midnight's Children* Rushdie writes: "Sometimes legends make reality and become more useful than the facts" (48). It shows that Rushdie treats history as a construct, made up of many contributing factors, and not just collected facts and figures. Similarly, in *Grimus*, Virgil Jones says that a historian is a

philosopher and a good reader of what has happened. He claims that historians also, knowingly or unknowingly, take sides. They are not good observers but also good interpreters. They add meaning and values to what they write. Historians are bridges of the past and the present. They have their own historicity and they deal with another history at the same time. In this act both affect each other and what they produce is after all a negotiation. Thus, for Rushdie, history is a product of negotiation, a negotiated act.

Another important factor that influence Rushdie's writings are the use of myths and legends. As myths and legends are our common reservoir of knowledge, they form our collective memory. Since history uses memory as an important aide, Rushdie uses myths and magic in his writings to excavate the layers of history. The use of myth and magic also helps Rushdie to search for alternative realities of human societies. Because authors use memory, as a tool to reflect our past societies, their writings, be it a story or history, contain lies and errors. Whatever truths writers communicate will be always incomplete in some sense. Historians often give us incomplete truth about our past. Rushdie has more faith in the novelist than in the historian. Or, to say it in other words, a good history is to Rushdie, a good novel. He believes that novelists can fill in the gaps that historians leave, here and there, in their historical writings. In *Grimus*, *Midnight's Children*, and *The Enchantress of Florence*, Rushdie does the same. He opens the world a bit more to us than what historians have so far done.

Rushdie's uniqueness lies in his fusion of mythos and logos. Myths represent our imaginative or speculative capacity whereas logos represent our capacity to reach to conclusions through rigorous reasoning. By making a fusion of mythos and logos,

Rushdie breeds a new genre of writing. His novels can be read as history books and vice versa. He effectively blurs the boundary between history and fiction and places them into a wider open horizon of meanings. In this sense, Rushdie has given Indian literary tradition, as well as the world literary tradition, a forward step towards a new horizon. While going through Rushdie's major novels, readers soon may recognize that his primary interest lies in the exploration of the political history of the Indian subcontinent, and myths that surround it. Rushdie does not just intend to reiterate the old stories of his nation; rather, he aims at excavating new stories, hidden beneath the available historical narratives. He approaches the history of his continent from new angles such as irony, allegory, metaphor, magic, and so on. In his narratives, history, culture, religion, politics, myths, gossip commingle in order to entertain as well as inform the readers.

Rushdie's philosophy of history can be understood in the light of what Laurence Lerner wrote; "Most novels are made from the mixture of memory, introspection, observation, and the use of the documents" (13). Rushdie's texts are also the mixture of all ingredients that Lerner mentioned. In *Midnight's Children*, Rushdie writes, "Memory is truth, because memory has its own special kind. It selects, eliminates, alters, exaggerates, minimizes, glorifies, and vilifies also; but in the end it creates its own reality" (292). Rushdie's novels also depict various kinds of Indian realities, though they are presented in strange ways. In *Midnight's Children* Rushdie uses the metaphor of "Chutnification." Saleem works in a pickle factory and he tries to prepare and preserve pickles, using different techniques. This very idea of preparing and preserving has been used in the novel as a metaphor of history writing. Rushdie believes that history is also very much like "Indian Chutney" for it contains

various ingredients such as fact, narrative, myth, magic, lies, gossip, and so on. All these components mixed in different quantities give history a shape. Through this central metaphor, Rushdie forwards his philosophy of history and fiction that they are also very much like the “Indian Chutney.” Using this domestic image of pickle making, Rushdie beautifully illustrates how history and fiction are prepared and preserved.

Rushdie uses palimpsest as an important technique to weave multiple stories in his novels. It is a process of covering up what already exists. Using palimpsest as a technique of writing, Rushdie conveys the idea that history or even fiction may contain layers of meanings. Rushdie uses this concept to display the multilayered and multicultural social reality of his subcontinent. Using this special technique, Rushdie attempts to capture the dynamism that exists in South Asian societies. Western historiographical traditions often fail to capture such complex realities because they are too rigid in their methodologies. But Rushdie devises his own philosophy of history and novels in order to open the world a bit more. He tries to represent history in its multiple forms in order to grasp the richness of the past. And the major forms of history according to Rushdie are: factual, narrative, magical, and propagandist. To sum up, history may come to readers as facts or chronicles, stories or narratives, fantasy or magic, and gossip or lies, or all pickled en masse.

Though this research work primarily focuses on one particular writer and his selected writings, its findings are applicable to other writers and their writings too. One may read even John Bagnell Bury’s *The Invasion of Europe by the Barbarians* (1928) as a collage of fact, stories, myth/magic, and gossip/lies. J. B. Bury may try his best to prove himself as a pure scientist, but his writings would certainly indicate

how he also creates fictions or his own version of reality. The idea posited by this dissertation may help readers to read and understand any other texts. For example, one may read V.S. Naipaul's writings as a combination of fact, story, myth/magic, and lies. This study therefore proposes a new method of reading fiction, history and other imaginative works.

As an illustration, let us again discuss some other novels by Rushdie himself. Besides the above-mentioned three novels, his other novels also place history at the center. For example, *Shame*, his third novel, primarily deals with the political history of Pakistan. It shows how people in power try to exploit history for their own vested political interests. This novel beautifully exposes the lies and manipulations that some of the officially sanctioned history books propagate. Rushdie, unlike other historians, has the courage to embrace the biases and distortions for he believes that history is after all just a testament to the human condition, nothing else. Because it is a human testament, it inherits all human weaknesses and strengths. Rushdie's *Shame* also hints at the possibility that history is not purely objective. It is not just made up of one ingredient. It is the collection of data, imagination, myth, magic, lies, and gossip.

Rushdie's fourth novel *The Satanic Verses* also deals with the issues of history and historiography. Though it primarily focuses on the sacred text the Quran and the prophet Muhammad, it symbolizes the various aspects of history. Rushdie comes in controversy after the publication of this novel because he unhesitatingly blends facts with fiction. Though he tried to defend himself saying that *The Satanic Verses* was/is a novel, not a book on history, the Muslim community reacted to it very differently. The Iranian government even declared a Fatwa against him. This particular instance makes it very clear that some of the readers read Rushdie's texts as novels whereas

some read these texts as history. In this regard one may assert that Rushdie has been able to blur the boundary between history and fiction. In Rushdie's writings, readers may be able to realize better what the New Historicists talk about by the historicity of text and the textuality of history. Though the novel deals with the characters such as Mahound, Gibreel, Saladen, it allegorizes the history of religion and the ancient world. In *The Satanic Verses* a reader of history may easily find little bits of documented history, a little bit of imagination, a little bit of myth & magic, and a little bit of lies & gossip. All these components have been blended adroitly in order to prepare the recipe of history.

Salman Rushdie's fifth novel *The Moor's Last Sigh* is also a work of historiographic metafiction where the author attempts to depict the real through the magical mode of representation. By using magic in order to recover the past, Rushdie, on the one hand, refutes the western historiographic tradition, and on the other hand, succeeds in giving a message that historical narratives contain not just facts but also author's biases as well as imagination. In *The Moor's Last Sigh* also Rushdie attempts to rewrite history from the perspectives of the common men. The novel portrays the dark aspects of Indian politics, where corruption looms large. Rushdie unhesitatingly uses folklores, legends, myths, superstitious beliefs, magic, gossips, and even lies into this narrative. In *The Moor's Last Sigh* Rushdie illustrates how history may come to readers in multiple faces. It becomes evident when the protagonist Zogoiby asserts:

The city itself, perhaps the whole country, was a palimpsest, Under world beneath Over world, black market beneath white; when the whole life was like this, when an invisible reality moved phantom wise beneath a visible fiction subverting all its meanings how then could Abraham's career have been any

different? . . . How trapped as we were in the hundred percent fakery of the real, in the fancy dress, weeping-Arab kitsch of the superficial, could we have penetrated to the full, sensual truth of the lost mother below? How could we have lived authentic lives? How could we have failed to be grotesque? (*The Moor's Last Sigh* 184-85)

Thus Rushdie imagines society as well as its history as multilayered, or multicolored. The richness of the past, as Rushdie believes, can't be grasped at once in one-dimensional frame. This is why Rushdie uses palimpsest to rewrite history.

Similarly, in *Shalimar the Clown*, Rushdie depicts Kashmiri conflicts and its intricate history. The novel tries to blur the boundary between history and story by equating personal history and national history. The novel gives us a counter history from a character's perspective. The characters of *Shalimar the Clown* can be read as the agents of change who challenge the traditional views of history as conclusive. By proposing a cyclical view of history, the novel foregrounds the notion of the interconnectedness of things and thus it reimagines "history" differently. In this new version of history, Rushdie again makes a kind of concoction of official data, imaginative details, myth, magic, gossip, and lies.

After reading Rushdie and his views on history and novels, it would be no more tolerable to any readers to believe blindly on any historians or novelists, or even journalists. Readers must use their prior knowledge and the critical brain in order to read and interpret any writings, be it literary or non-literary. This research work thus opens up an avenue for readers to read the texts written by other authors, or even Rushdie, in this new light. In the creative furnace of a writer like Rushdie, disparate

elements get fused into an imaginative whole; call it fable or fiction, history or tall tale.

To conclude, the principal focus of this work is the nature of historical representation as depicted in Salman Rushdie's fiction, where the old historical idea of the changelessness of history gives place to the historian's language about the past. Rushdie starts by positing a difference between representation and interpretation. Representation is concerned with reality, not with the text. Interpretation limits itself to the study of the text and is not interested in reality itself. The text as a whole is more than the sum of its components. The writing of history should begin with representation and then only go to interpretation. History reveals the truth. Rushdie's novels reveal important truths about reality, though the individual statements he makes may be totally false. The language in which history is represented is of paramount importance. Rushdie's representation of history argues about the continuity of cultural transformation and so presents an ideological history of real values in an intercultural and interdisciplinary perspective.

Rushdie's history is a "narrative." In this narrative, he engages with influences, with feminist concerns, with political ideas, with magical realism, and with the reader's relation to the text. The theories stand in a dialectical relation to each other, "deconstructing," theories and texts. The real subject of this narrative is the author's mind where Rushdie is preoccupied with different forms of social authority, a mingling of past and present, mythical allegories, and the systems of class. The major theoretical perspectives are borrowed from Marx, Nietzsche, and Freud. He takes concepts from these theories with each concept dealing with a person or a class to challenge the authority of historical precedent. Rushdie's true subject is,

therefore, history, primarily politico-religious-economic history. He delves into important economic movements of his times and charts out their historical developments. It elaborates the implied historical circumstances of his novel. In the end, Rushdie's characters recede into the background and historical processes occupy the foreground, or, in other words, character, and plot represent historical movements. In his fiction, Rushdie constructs a religious or political history in such a way that history becomes staged. The interdisciplinary investigation of history makes visible dominant discourses that represent elements of culture, including sexual, racial, and political differences. His fictive history shows how the writer uses his intellect and artistic skill to produce moments of transformative possibility. For instance, in *Midnight's Children*, Rushdie presents his argument on the basis of his researches in the history of British colonialism and the Indian government's efforts to raise the flag of nationalism to help the transition to an independent yet unified India. At the same time, he problematizes the idea of a unified Indian personality by depicting a diversity of experience in regard to class, gender, and cultural heritage. The novel brings together history, Marxist theories, Indian religious philosophy, and global politics into a cohesive whole. *Midnight's Children* delineates a transnational history of transgressive Indian performance.

The Indian diaspora is a major field of historical inquiry. But it still needs an intellectual identity. By only talking about people of Indian descent, a field does not attain its intellectual coherence. How does its history differ from, say African history in methodology? Rushdie attempts to answer this question in his work by bringing in the concepts of a comparative diaspora of Indian historiography, identity and culture, domination and resistance, and geo-social history of the Indian diaspora.

He demonstrates how Indian diaspora shows global connectedness as well as separation. He cautions against essentializing the Indian diaspora experiences and constructs an Indo-British identity. He compares the transition from colonialism to freedom in India and is concerned with the representation of South Asia over time and power relations among nations. He argues how Indian diaspora historiography will lose its significance if viewed wholly through the prism of racism, domination, and resistance. Such an approach, he posits, forbids the revelation of the people's complex and diverse past. This provides a valuable insight into historiographical arguments about epistemology and theory in diaspora history. Rushdie's genre of fiction emerges out of the dialectal exchange between the real and the imagined by the depiction of a new recognition of the surroundings. It does not predict the future but allegorizes the real in the present.

Rushdie's alternative history owes its delineation to surrealism and magical realism. His fictional genre, despite its strangeness, is not impossible antirealist literature but a representation of the estranged though real objects, a representation in which its referents are susceptible to representation, in the sense that representation takes place on the opposition between referentiality and fictionality. Consequently, his fictions read like poetry. The reader has necessarily to find some interpretive link between the artistic representation and its supposed referent in order to save the story from being simply fantastic nonsense, or erroneously thinking the dream as something real.

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